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On the general theory
of neuronal dynamics

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To my Licia, Cris and Martina

*The Brain—is wider than the Sky—
For—put them side by side—
The one the other will contain
With ease—and you—beside—*

*The Brain is deeper than the sea
For—hold them—Blue to Blue
The one the other will absorb
As sponges—Buckets—do*

*The Brain is just the weight of God
For—Heft them—Pound for Pound
And they will differ—if they do
As Syllable from Sound*

Emily Dickinson

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Chapter 1

Introduction

The story so far:
In the beginning the Universe was created.
This has made a lot of people very angry and been widely
regarded as a bad move.

Douglas Adams

The brain is arguably the most complex system known to man. Under the eyes of a physicist, brains show all the major complications that one can think of when it comes to building a theoretical description. At all scales, the brain is out-of-equilibrium, as any living system must be to avoid death. Moreover, there is no such thing as two truly identical neurons: heterogeneity is a fundamental element of the puzzle. A clear distinction between environment and system is only partially possible. This is due to the intricate feedback loops necessary to adapt and respond to what happens around us. Finally, neurons are stochastic and non-linear systems which certainly does not simplify the picture. On top of that, we have to consider a complication that is common to most scientific endeavors: the system is observed through a keyhole, only partial information is available or, in other terms, we have access in experiments to only a limited number of degrees of freedom.

Under these premises, it is natural to wonder whether it is even possible to tackle these problems with a reductionist approach let alone a first-principle reasoning. The unreasonable effectiveness [[Wig90](#)] of a mathematical description of the world is however surprisingly universal and it extended beyond traditional physics. The fil rouge of this work is precisely that, despite numerous difficulties, it is indeed possible to gain significant insights into the inner workings of neural systems adopting the powerful toolbox of physics.

Understanding the physics supported by networks of neurons is a necessary step in investigating some of the most outstanding mysteries of Nature such as memory, language, and consciousness. Physicists and mathematicians have had an interest in neuroscience for a long time. For example, it is difficult to underestimate key conceptual contributions by scientists of the caliber of Von Neuman and Turing [[VK12](#); [Tur+36](#)]. A more recent example dates back to some decades ago when a burst of research originated in the field of statistical mechanics starting with the seminal work of Amari and Hopfield [[Ama72](#); [Hop82](#)] that lay out the basis of attractor neural network theory. Back then the idea of storage of memories as an energy landscape was purely based on theoretical reasoning but it has now found a large consensus thanks to numerous experimental findings that support it [[KF22](#)].

Today we are living in a golden age of neuroscience thanks to unprecedented tech-

nological advances. It is now possible to trace and stimulate single specific neurons in behaving animals [Wu+15; CL11]. Vast networks have been mapped out, down to the level of counting every single synapse in a cube milliliter of cortical surface [Tur+22]. Consequently, the need for a unifying theoretical framework has become more pressing.

This thesis is an effort in that direction. Following the tradition of statistical physics, I will derive a general theory of neuronal population dynamics starting from first-principle i.e. relating single neuron features to the emerging neuronal network behaviour.

Our starting point will be a mean-field theory commonly referred to as the population density approach, that rests mainly in assuming an infinite number of neurons [AB97; KMS96]. This kind of theories were developed when it became clear that neurons process most of the information not alone but at a network level. A point of view highly at odds with the "neuron doctrine" put forward by some of the father of the neuroscience like Cayal, Adrian and Eccles. The paradigm shift to a population coding view justified a massive reduction of complexity, since the interest was non longer on single neurons but on the average activity of a circuit. Among the major achievements of this view there is for example the concept of balance state [SCS88; VS98]: a balance of excitation and inhibition is necessary to sustain irregular the kind of asynchronous activity which is commonly observed in experiments [Hai+06].

Most of the theoretical results refer to the statistics of stationary states or linerizable regimes. While those achievements fostered profound insights, neural circuits are constantly bombarded by external stimuli. Consequently, the transient dynamic and dynamic response are equally important and most open questions orbit around the dynamical non-stationary properties of neural populations.

In this work, we will concentrate on three main open questions, all deeply interconnected, regarding neuronal population dynamics. Universality, low dimensionality, and finite-size effects.

Thermodynamics taught us that despite the original large number of degrees of freedom the law that governs the evolution of mesoscopic quantities is often low dimensional. The same applies to neural populations, in fact, phenomenological models with few degrees of freedom, of neural activity have been proposed and used substantially in the literature [WC72; WW06]. Much fewer attempts were made in deriving such laws from first principles. The main obstacle in this path is the non-linear nature of the equations. To solve this moment-closure [Kue16] problem, several authors like [MPR15; SZT20] made ansatz that inevitably limit the applicability of the resulting theory to regimes that are not always clearly defined. An open question that will address here is then how to derive such a low dimensional theory valid in the most general case and what it tells us about neuronal dynamics.

The complexity inherent to biology led in the years to a proliferation of different models for the behavior of single neurons. The main discriminant is the level of detail included in the description, ranging from point processes such as the Integrate-and-Fire framework to the biologically realistic Hodgkin and Huxley model [HH52b]. When we look at the emergent behavior of such different models we find surprising similarities. In a way we could say that the large-scale neuronal dynamics appear to be practically universal, meaning that are weakly dependent on specific features or parameters and more related to the general mechanism at play. The sloppiness of models has been related to emergent, or effective, theories in different contexts [Qui+22] but, in neuroscience, the origin of this phenomenon has not been studied in detail and many questions remain to be answered.

We will focus here on two: what are the essential ingredients of single neurons that will lead to expected mesoscopic dynamics? Are all the parameters of the models uniquely determined by the observed activity?

Finally, cortical neural networks consist of a finite, albeit huge, number of neurons. It is common knowledge that finite-size impacts the predictions of mean-field theories. The main effect of a finite number of neurons is that mean activity alone is not enough to correctly describe the time evolution of the network. A common approach is then to go beyond mean-field theory and try to capture also endogenous fluctuations generated by finite-size effects. In weakly coupled networks we can use linear response theory, a tool, however, that fails close to bifurcations or in the non-linear regime. Coincidentally it is precisely in the non-linear cases that finite-size fluctuations are most prominent. A good example is the meta-stable activity regime commonly observed in neural recordings [Bri+22] where finite-size fluctuations induce transitions between different states and thus are an essential element in an accurate description of neuronal activity. Except for some remarkable results [BC13; SDG17b], a general self-consistent approach to include these effects in an extended mean-field theory is still lacking.

1.1 Overview

The thesis will be presented with the following structure:

- In Chapter 2 I will give a review of the most relevant results and open questions regarding the population density approach that is the basis of this work. I will also introduce the single-neuron model which will be the de facto first principle of the theory we will develop. Also several essential preliminaries concepts and tools are introduced.
- In Chapter 3 I will present the first original result: a "Rosetta stone" that relates two different methods of solving the continuity equation that describe the evolution of the population density. This bridge allows us to derive several analytical results and identities that will be essential in the following chapters.
- Chapter 4 illustrates one of the main results: the extension of the mean-field to a self-consistent theory of finite-size network of spiking neurons. Our theory is non-perturbative in the size N and applies even close to bifurcation and in non-linear regimes. We found that the correction to the mean-field theory are state-dependent and related to single neuron details. To prove its efficacy we study a case of stochastic-induced coherence.
- In Chapter 5 we will focus on the low-dimensional nature of the mean-field theory. We will demonstrate that dimensional reduction is possible thanks to a separation of time scales that is independent of single neuron details. Leveraging spectral expansion techniques we derive a low dimensional system for the population firing rate and discuss a number of interesting physical properties. We also demonstrate, in Chapter 6, a general relation between the firing rate and the moments of the population membrane potential density. This last result has a more broad scope since it shows how to use time scale separation in a general moment-closure problem.
- In Chapter 7 I will dwell deeper into the universality of the low dimensional theory we derived looking at two radically different single neurons models. We demonstrate

that despite those differences the population dynamics is remarkably similar and we discuss the origin of this universality and its possible implications.

- Chapter 8 is about degeneracy of those mean-field models. We found that the having access to the activity of the population is not enough to fully constrain the models discussed in this thesis. On the contrary a manifold of degenerate models can reproduce whit the same quality a given set of observed behavior. It is then important to understand the source of this degeneracy and what could be done to reduce it the most. This results are related to the concept of a universal theory previously discussed.

Finally I will conclude with on Outlook chapter where we summarize the results obtained and put the on a broader context. I will also highlights several open problems and future directions and what are the most relevant implication of those findings in both neuroscience and physics.

Chapter 2

Mean-Field theory of spiking neural networks

Living matter evades the decay to equilibrium.

Erwin Schrödinger

In this chapter I will review the most relevant results regarding the population density approach that allow to describe the emergent dynamics of a network of spiking neurons. First I will introduce the framework of Integrate-and-Fire neurons and from there I will stress the necessary assumptions that allows to derive a continuity equation for the population membrane potential density. I will also present the main experimental findings that support this framework and further elaborate on some key technical issues.

2.1 A theoretical model of neurons

Neurons are the fundamental units of a neural system, they transmit information through action potentials, stereotyped depolarizing potential that are also commonly referred to as spikes. The whole process of spike emission can be modeled with a non-linear equivalent circuit where the different conductances refer to different ionic channels [HH52a]. From a more general view neurons are an excitable system: the emission of a spike is a deterministic detour in the phase space that is initiated when the membrane potential reaches a threshold. This threshold however is dynamical since it is a function of the external current and state of the neuron [Fit55]. Assuming that the information is carried by the spike timing and not its shape we can greatly simplify the picture by disregarding what happens after the spike emission. Following Lapique [Lap07] we can assume a potential threshold θ and add to the model a reset boundary condition which brings the membrane potential to a value H after an absolute refractory period τ_0 :

$$V(t - \tau_0) = \theta \rightarrow V(t) = H$$

Paying the price of a discontinuous process we can thus implement an excitable dynamics even with one-dimensional system [Lin+04] which in turn will allow us to go much further analytically with respect to higher dimensional models like the one proposed by Fitzhugh and Nagumo [Fit55].

Integrate-and-Fire neurons are described by the following equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V} &= f(V) + I(t) \\ V(t - \tau_0) &= \theta \rightarrow V(t) = H \end{aligned} \tag{2.1}$$

The function $f(V)$ carries all the single neuron details and dictates the sub-threshold dynamics. It has been found that the best fit from single-neuron recording is achieved with a combination of a linear and an exponential function [Bad+08] but we will use as a benchmark the Leaky-Integrate-and-Fire (LIF) model where $f(V) = -\frac{V}{\tau_m}$. Despite analytical advantage the LIF neuron is capable of reproducing on the quantitative level the precise spike timing of real neurons and for this reason it is considered the best compromise between simplicity and accuracy.

The synaptic current $I(t)$ accounts for the change of voltage induced by the spike train incoming from the network. Here we are implicitly assuming a current-based view even though biologically it is more accurate to consider a change in the conductances mediated by presynaptic spikes. From a formal point of view this difference seems huge in fact conductance-based model have additional non-linearities and properties [Des+01]. However it can be demonstrated that most of the relevant features can be restored in current-based models by considering a state-dependent membrane decay time $\tau_m(t)$ [RG05; SHB22]. The limits of this approximation, especially in transient dynamics, are still an open problem but since the results I will present do not depend on this distinction, I will use current-based neurons based on their simplicity.

Summarizing, the membrane potential of current-based Integrate-and-Fire neurons evolve in time according to:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V}_i &= f(V_i) + \sum_{j,k} J_{ij} \delta(t - t_j^k) \\ V_i(t - \tau_0) = \theta &\rightarrow V_i(t) = H \end{aligned} \tag{2.2}$$

Where t_j^k is the k -th spike emitted by neuron j and J_{ij} is the synaptic weight of neuron j over neuron i . We can add additional degrees of freedom to equation 2.2 to take into account other important feature such axonal delays and adaptation as I will show in the following chapters.

2.2 Population density approach

Consider now a population of interacting neurons each following equation 2.2. Let us also assume for simplicity the population is homogeneous: neurons of the pool share same parameters. Following Brunel and Hakim [BH99], if the number of neurons N is huge, pairwise correlation between two random neurons in the network should be negligible. Under this assumption we can imagine the neural population as an ensemble of independent process all extracted by the same probability density $p(v, t)$. As usual however there is still some correlation which does not vanish in the limit $N \rightarrow \infty$: the average self-interaction which is felt by all neurons in the pool which is carried by a mean-field. In our context the mean-field is the population mean firing rate or activity, $\nu(t)$, which is defined as:

$$\nu(t) dt = \frac{\mathcal{N}(t)}{N}$$

where $\mathcal{N}(t)$ is the number of neurons in the population that emitted a spike in the interval $[t, t + dt]$. The time evolution of the population density $p(v, t, \nu)$ is governed by a master equation [Gar+85] which, in the continuous limit, we can write as:

$$\partial_t p(v, t) = -\nabla_v S_p(v, \nu(t)) \tag{2.3}$$

which we wrote as continuity equation and $S_p(v, t)$ is the probability flux.

Mean-Field theory gives always rise to non-linear continuity equation. The reason behind this is that the mean-field itself, that enters the continuity equation, is by definition a function of the full probability density $p(v, t)$. Using the definition, the firing rate is the probability flux across the spike emission threshold θ .

$$v(t) = S_p(\theta, t, v(t)) \quad (2.4)$$

The theoretical derivation of 2.3 rest on the law of large number, however it is not always possible to provide a rigorous derivation. From a formal point of view this is one the most urgent problem in the field since techniques like Van-Kampen size expansion [Kam07] or path-integral formalism cannot be implemented in Integrate-and-Fire networks due to the discontinuity induced by the reset mechanism. Some noteworthy exception can be found in [Bre10] where simpler models are considered. The practical advantage of a formal derivation would be to include perturbatively pairwise correlations but fortunately the typical scenarios in cortical networks fully justify the approximation we made. In fact cortical neurons have typically a large number of synaptic contacts, of the order $o(10^4)$. Of this connection only a small percentage, 10% [Mou97], is from neurons in the same network which means that neurons will mostly receive uncorrelated spikes. That been said, all the results I will present are rather general in the sense that can be applied with no conceptual change to general master equations even those that will be derived, potentially formally, in the future.

2.2.1 Diffusion approximation

The specific form of the master equation 2.3 depends on further assumptions made. Thanks to the fact that cortical neurons typically receive a large number of spike and that each spike contribution is actually small compare to the total amount, that is $J_{i,j} \ll 1$, a diffusion approximation is commonly assumed [Tuc05]. Moreover the exact strength of all synaptic couplings is not always accessible in experiments, so we will assume that J_{ij} is a random variable extracted from a probability distribution that we chose to be Gaussian:

$$Prob(J_{ij} \in [J_{ij}, J_{ij} + dJ]) = e^{-\frac{(J_{ij}-J)^2}{2J^2}} dJ \quad (2.5)$$

This is quenched randomness since in what follows the synaptic weight will not change during the dynamical evolution of the state variables of the network. As a consequence J is statistically independent from any other variable of the system. Note that this is no longer true when, for example, a learning process is involved [Fus02], but I will not treat this aspects in the thesis.

If the current term is adequately fast it is possible to think about the depolarization, $V_i(t)$, as a random walk, with particular boundary condition induced by the reset mechanism [GM64]. Integrating equation (2.2) for LIF neurons we get:

$$V_i(t) - V_i(0) = -\frac{1}{\tau_m} \int_0^t V_i(t') dt' + \frac{1}{\tau_m} \sum_{j=1}^N J_{ij} N_j(t) \quad (2.6)$$

where $N_j(t)$ is the number of incoming spikes from neuron j :

$$N_j(t) = \int_0^t \sum_k \delta(t' - t_j^{(k)}) dt' \quad (2.7)$$

Figure 2.1: Cartoon of the neuron's afferent current as the superposition of stochastic point processes and the limit to a diffusion process. On the top left diagram a schematic drawing of a target neuron with the synaptic contacts. Top right: illustration of the stochastic point processes of the spikes received from each pre-synaptic neuron, and the superposition of all of them. On the bottom sample trajectory of the neuron's membrane potential V for a discontinuous IF neuron model due to the instantaneous upward (downward) jumps upon reception of each excitatory (inhibitory) spike. On the right plot is the sample trajectory of the membrane potential V under diffusion limit, for a leaky integrate-and-fire neuron model driven by a white noise with same infinitesimal mean and variance as the Poisson process in the left plot. Taken from [GM03]

In stationary condition the frequency of emitted spikes from neuron j , ν_j , is constant and the emission process can be well approximated by Poissonian process [Tuc05]. Then the probability of emission of a spike in a infinitesimal time interval Δt is given by:

$$Prob[\exists k : t_j^{(k)} \in (t, t + \Delta t)] = \nu_j \Delta t$$

At this level it is clear that the evolution of the single neuron is correlated to the the frequency of emissions, ν_j , of all its presynaptic neurons in the pool.

Clearly this is a major complication. To make progress we follow Amit and Brunel [AB97] and make a strong simplification, arguably the key assumption of this approach, that the emission times of different neurons are uncorrelated. Surprisingly, this seems to be rather effective in usual neurons in the cortex. Typically the recurrent fraction of connections, among neurons in the same pool, is only 10-20 % and the average frequency of emission of single neurons is most of the time low both in resting and active state [AT92]. Moreover note that, from a theoretical point of view, the leakage term in the dynamics also contributes to decrease pair correlations because it forces the neurons to "forget" what happened at previous time. With this assumption we can then say that the noise component of the current, $I(t)$, by the theorem of Grigelionis [SM12] is itself a Poisson process being sum of uncorrelated Poisson process like (2.7).

Now we turn to the last issue with the theoretical characterization of the dynamics for

$V(t)$ i.e. the fact that is discontinuous. This is more a practical problem, in fact even though discontinuous dynamical system are often used to model natural phenomena, the number of analytical tools and results are fairly limited compared to continuous dynamical systems. To solve this complication we can perform a diffusion approximation in fact the Poissonian synaptic current for the Central Limit Theorem, tend to a Gaussian white noise, with same variance and mean, when the number of spikes per interval time is high. This is analgous to the approximation typically done in the treatment of shot noise [Gar+85], so at the same time the single single synaptic jump has to be small compared to overall current. The resulting continuous stochastic processes, which is δ -correlated in time, is the Wiener process $W(t)$ that is defined by the following properties:

- W has uncorrelated future increments such that, for $u > 0$, $W(t + u) - W(t)$ is uncorrelated to $W(s)$ for any $s \leq t$
- $W(t + dt) - W(t)$ follow a normal distribution with zero mean and variance dt .

The diffusion approximation consists in approximate, see figure (2.1), the discontinuous random walk of $V(t)$ using a continuous Wiener process, with same mean, $\mu(V, t)$, and variance, $\sigma^2(V, t)$, of the original stochastic process $V(t)$.

We note also that thanks to its Markovian nature, the Wiener process is fully characterized by the infinitesimal mean and variance that we still have to specify. For the membrane potential they are defined as:

$$\mu(x) \equiv \lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{E[V(t + \Delta t) - V(t) | V(t) = x]}{\Delta t} \quad (2.8)$$

$$\sigma^2(x) \equiv \lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{Var[V(t + \Delta t) - V(t) | V(t) = x]}{\Delta t} \quad (2.9)$$

with $E[*]$ and $Var[*]$ indicating expectation value and variance. The dynamic in the case of the LIF model, for an arbitrary neuron in the population, can then be formally written as the following Stochastic Differential Equation (SDE):

$$dV(t) = \left(\frac{-V(t)}{\tau_m} + \mu(V(t), t) \right) dt + \sigma(V(t), t) dW(t) \quad (2.10)$$

To determine the diffusive parameters we write the equation for time increments of the voltage from (2.6), identifying with K and K_{Ext} the recurrent and external number of synaptic contacts per single neuron and taking the expectation value:

$$E[\Delta V(t)] = - \int_t^{t+\Delta t} \frac{V(t)}{\tau_m} + \sum_{j=1}^K E[J_{ij} N_j(t)] + \sum_j^{K_{Ext}} E[J_{ij}^{Ext} N_j^{Ext}(t)]$$

That using the fact that J and $N(t)$ are uncorrelated becomes:

$$E[\Delta V(t)] = - \int_t^{t+\Delta t} \frac{V(t)}{\tau_m} + \sum_{j=1}^K J v_j \Delta t + K_{Ext} J_{Ext} v_{Ext} \Delta t$$

Analogous calculations leads to :

$$Var(\Delta V(t)) = \sum_{j=1}^K J^2 v_j \Delta t + K_{Ext} J_{Ext}^2 v_{Ext} \Delta t$$

So under diffusion approximation the infinitesimal mean and the variance appearing in the SDE (2.10) are:

$$\begin{aligned}\mu(V, t) &= J \sum_j^K v_j + K_{Ext} J_{Ext} v_{Ext} + I_{Ext}(t) \\ \sigma^2(V, t) &= J^2 \sum_j^K v_j + K_{Ext} J_{Ext}^2 v_{Ext}\end{aligned}\tag{2.11}$$

where J is the mean of the synaptic weights distribution and I_{ext} is the deterministic component of the afferent current. On the following we might refer to $\mu_{ext} = +K_{Ext} J_{Ext} v_{Ext} + I_{Ext}$ and $\sigma_{ext}^2 = K_{Ext} J_{Ext}^2 v_{Ext}$ as the moments of the part of synaptic current that comes from outside the population.

Cortical columns are mostly homogeneous networks of neurons [Mou97], so it is safe to say that all the neurons in our pool have roughly the same parameters as τ_m , H and θ but most importantly we assume that they all emit spikes at the same frequency, because they all receive the same amount of synaptic inputs:

$$v_j = v$$

So in the most general case the moments of the current $I(t)$ are:

$$\begin{aligned}\mu(V, t) &= KJv(t) + K_{Ext} J_{Ext} v_{Ext}(t) + I_{Ext}(t) \\ \sigma^2(V, t) &= KJ^2v(t) + K_{Ext} J_{Ext}^2 v_{Ext}(t)\end{aligned}\tag{2.12}$$

We end this section mentioning that several works have considered the effect of correlated spikes [Mor+02; DR17]. The main implication of correlations is loosing the Markovian property of the process $I(t)$ which clearly complicates a lot the theoretical description, however a Non-Markovian process can be embedded in a higher dimensional Markovian process which then allows to write a continuity equation of the same type of what I will describe in the following [Mat+19].

Finally the homogeneity hypothesis we made can be relaxed. Already in [BH99] it has been shown how to consider heterogeneity in some parameters such as the mean number of connections. In this case for example the mean firing rate $v(t)$ is no longer enough and we must include also its variance thus we will have a distribution of moments μ and σ^2 .

2.3 The mean-field limit

To study the spontaneous and perturbed dynamics of large neuronal population, such as neurons in the visual cortex of the cat [Rei+97] Knight introduced the population density approach [Kni00]. As discussed above, we may assume that, if the population is homogeneous, meaning same single-neurons parameters and average connectivity, all the neurons in the pool receive the same statistics in terms of the afferent current ($\mu(t)$ and $\sigma^2(t)$).

The key idea is to think that afferent input currents impinging on neurons in one population are essentially uncorrelated however an important remark must be made: a non-stationary $v(t)$ embodies the changes in time of the average statistical properties of the network synaptic current, and can correlate the activities of two given neurons. This should be regarded as a "trivial" correlation due to the input and is self-consistently taken into account in the mean-field approach we are presenting. Most importantly it does not

imply a breakdown of independent spiking times hypothesis which is at the heart of the formalism. The collective activity is still adequately described by a non-stationary Poisson process completely determined by the population firing rate ν . In other word neurons are independent, conditionally to the average emission rate. Thus, two neurons of the pool with same membrane potential at time t are indistinguishable.

In the limit of large $N \rightarrow \infty$ then the mean-field hypothesis consists in assuming that the probability of receive of a spike from a post-synaptic neuron is $\nu(t)dt$ in an interval $[t, t + dt]$: the same for all the neurons in the populations.

From a statistical point of view we then have N stochastic identical process, driven by uncorrelated noise, that follows the equation:

$$dV = \left[-\frac{V}{\tau_m} + \mu(\nu(t)) \right] dt + \sigma(\nu(t))dW \quad (2.13)$$

We can define the probability density function:

$$p(v, t)dv = Prob(V(t) \in [v, v + dv]) \quad (2.14)$$

which expresses the fraction of neurons at time t that have a membrane potential $V(t)$ in the interval $[v, v + dv]$.

The stochastic process (2.13) is Markovian, which implies that $p(v, t)$ suffices to provide the complete statistical description. Using the diffusion approximation it is possible to derive an equation for the time evolution of $p(v, t)$ that is called the forward Kolmogorov equation or more commonly the Fokker-Planck equation [Ris96]:

$$\tau_m \frac{\partial p(v, t)}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial v} [(v - \mu(t)\tau_m)p(v, t)] + \frac{\sigma^2 \tau_m}{2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial v^2} (p(v, t)) \quad (2.15)$$

The Fokker-Planck operator:

$$L(v, t) = -\partial_v [-v + \mu(v, t)\tau_m] + \frac{1}{2} \partial_v^2 [\sigma^2(v, t)\tau_m] \quad (2.16)$$

can be recast as the divergence of a probability flux $S_p(v, t)$:

$$L(v, t) = -\partial_v S_p(v, t)$$

such that Eq. (2.15) can be rewritten as a continuity equation like 2.3.

The Fokker-Planck equation must be complemented by the boundary conditions (b.c.) that arise from the details of our problem.

For the IF the b.c. must take into account the generation of the spike which is not automatically integrated in the equation of the dynamic and must be introduced with an *ad hoc* condition. We will also consider the possibility of a lower bound v_{min} for the potential v and of course we must enforce the normalization of the p.d.f..

The first condition is expressed by the fact that any realization of the stochastic process, $v(t)$, reaching the threshold θ disappears: θ acts as an absorbing barrier. The probability $p(v, t)$ can in general be non-zero thanks to the compensating probability flow that brings realizations in v .

This condition ceases to be true at θ since no flux from above is allowed i.e. in the IF model the membrane potential cannot be $v > \theta$, such that:

$$p(\theta, t) = 0 \quad (2.17)$$

After spike emission, $V(t)$ must restarts its random walk from the reset potential H and stay there for an absolute refractory period τ_0 . This means that each realization crossing θ is recovered, after a delay, from H so that no realizations are lost. Note that the normalization factor takes into account also the number of neurons in the refractory state:

$$\int_{v_{min}}^{\theta} p(v, t) dv + \int_{t-\tau_0}^t v(t') dt' = 1$$

Therefore a condition must hold for the conservation of the flux S_p such that the outgoing flux from θ is exactly compensated with an incoming extra influx at H

$$S_p(\theta, t - \tau_0) = S_p(H^+, t) - S_p(H^-, t) \quad (2.18)$$

With the shorthand notation $H^\pm = \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} H \pm \epsilon$. Note that we included here a period in which the neurons, after spike emission, are completely silent i.e. an absolute refractory period τ_0 . Finally we impose a reflecting barrier at $v_{min} \leq H$ implying that there is no flux crossing v_{min} :

$$S_p(v_{min}, t) = 0 \quad (2.19)$$

As a side note, the net probability flux induced by (2.18) introduces a "source", H , and a "sink", θ , complicating greatly the problem since it breaks detailed balance, a typical sign of far from equilibrium systems.

The spike emission rate, i.e. the instantaneous firing rate is given by the probability flux in θ :

$$v(t) = S_p(\theta, t) = -\frac{1}{2}\sigma^2 \partial_v p(v, t)|_{\theta} \quad (2.20)$$

Note that due to equation (2.12) the mean and variance of the synaptic current, μ and σ^2 , depend on the population firing rate. For this reason, the continuity equation is non-linear since the operator depend on the probability density: $L_v = L_v[p]$. As we will see in following chapters, this peculiar non linearity is actually the reason why it is indeed possible to reduce the dynamics of $p(v, t)$ to that of solely $v(t)$ without loss of information.

Note that if we chose different integrate-and-fire neurons, i.e. with an arbitrary $f(v)$ in equations 2.2, the Fokker-Planck equation would simply be:

$$\tau_m \frac{\partial p(v, t)}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial v} [(f(v) - \mu(t)\tau_m)p(v, t)] + \frac{\sigma^2 \tau_m}{2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial v^2} (p(v, t)) \quad (2.21)$$

2.4 Spectral expansion

In this section I will introduce a technical tool that will be used multiple times in the following. With the aim of deriving an equivalent description of the population dynamics in terms of $v(t)$, Mattia and Del Giudice [MD02] developed a spectral decomposition of p.d.f, $p(v, t)$, using the eigen functions of the Fokker-Planck operator, and obtained a cascade of Ordinary Differential Equations (ODE) that has been called Emission Rate

Equation (ERE). What follows is quite general and does not depend on the particular choice of $f(v)$ in (2.2), and hence in the IF neuron adopted.

The Fokker-Planck operator, L , has a set of eigenfunctions and associated eigenvalues defined by:

$$L|\phi_n\rangle = \lambda_n(t)|\phi_n\rangle \quad (2.22)$$

Where we introduced the inner product:

$$\langle\psi|\phi\rangle = \int_{v_{min}}^{\theta} \psi(v, t)\phi(v, t)dv$$

Both the spectrum and eigenfunctions are co-moving because they depend on time through $v(t)$. This is a major strength point of the approach since a co-moving basis will adapt to the changes of p . This in turn suggests that a limited number of eigenmodes are enough to approximate the time dependent solution of (2.15) compared to "static" expansion like a Fourier decomposition [Can+12].

Since L is non Hermitian [Ris96], the adjoint operator L^\dagger , defined by $\langle\psi|L\phi\rangle = \langle L^\dagger\psi|\phi\rangle$, has eigenfunctions $|\psi_n\rangle$ and eigenvalues $\tilde{\lambda}_n$ that are in general different from $|\phi_n\rangle$.

All $\phi_n(v, t)$ must satisfy the same boundary conditions of $p(v, t)$ while for the adjoint eigenfunctions [KMS96] it is sufficient to impose:

$$\psi_n(\theta) = \psi_n(H)e^{-\lambda_n\tau_0}$$

Which is need to cancel the boundary terms in the integral $\langle L^\dagger\psi|\phi\rangle$ where the adjoint operator is defined as:

$$L^\dagger(v, t) = [f(v) + \mu(v, t)\tau_m]\partial_v + \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2\tau_m(v, t)\partial_v^2$$

With this definitions $\{\phi_n, \psi_n\}$ form a complete biorthonormal set. After suitable rinormalization we have that $\langle\psi_n|\phi_m\rangle = \delta_{nm}$ and that the completeness assumption holds: $\sum_k |\phi_k\rangle\langle\psi_k| = \mathcal{I}$

The $p(v, t)$ can then be expanded as:

$$|p\rangle = \sum_n a_n|\phi_n\rangle \quad (2.23)$$

where $a_n = \langle\psi_n|p\rangle$ are the expansion coefficients some times refered to as eigen modes.

The dynamics of the expansion coefficients can be determined directly from the continuity equation [MD02]. Here we report it in vectorial form:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{\vec{a}} = (\mathbf{\Lambda} + \mathbf{C}\dot{v})\vec{a} + \vec{c}\dot{v} \\ \dot{v} = \Phi + \vec{f} \cdot \vec{a} \end{cases} \quad (2.24)$$

\vec{a} is the vector of the expansion coefficients.

The elements of equation (5.2) are defined as:

- $\{\mathbf{\Lambda}\}_{nm} = \lambda_n\delta_{nm}$ is the diagonal matrix of operator L eigenvalues.
- $\{\mathbf{C}\}_{nm} = \langle\partial_v\psi_n|\phi_m\rangle$ and $c_n = \langle\partial_v\psi_n|\phi_0\rangle$ are the coupling terms between non-stationary and stationary modes respectively.

- $f_n = -\frac{1}{2}\partial_v(\sigma^2(v, t)\phi_n(v, t))|_{v=\theta}$ is the n-th component of the flux across the threshold, for the non stationary modes.

$\Phi(\mu, \sigma^2)$ is commonly referred to as the current-to-rate gain function. It is particularly important because it allows us to determine the stationary solutions of the mean-field. In fact, by the definition we have that, in a stationary condition, the input rate must be equal to the output rate of the network hence if:

$$\Phi(\mu(v^*), \sigma^2(v^*)) = v^*$$

then v^* is the stationary firing rate reached by the population at time $t \rightarrow \infty$.

Finally I list some general properties that holds true for any continuity equation:

- $\lambda = 0$ is always part of the spectrum, i.e. we assume the the stationary probability distribution ϕ_0 to exist.
- $Re(\lambda_n) < 0$ since the solution $p(v, t)$ depends on the λ 's and has to converge for $t \rightarrow \infty$ to ϕ_0 , and it can happen only if the eigenvalues have positive real part.
- If λ is in the spectrum, then also λ^* is part of it being the operator L real.

Since the stationary solution coincides with zero eigenvalue eigenfunction:

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} p(v, t) = \phi_0(v)$$

. $a_0(t) = 1$ at every time because $\int_{v_{min}}^{\theta} \phi_0(v) dv = 1$. This constraint used in equation (5.1) leads to the following relation:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n(t) \int_{-\infty}^{\theta} \phi_n(v, v(t)) dv = 0$$

The orthonormality condition impose that $\psi_0(v) = 1$ thus the condition stated above can be rewritten:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n(t) \langle \psi_0 | \phi_n \rangle = 0$$

This is a sum of null terms since $\langle \psi_0 | \phi_n \rangle = 0$, which implies that the probability density normalization is guaranteed even if the spectral decomposition is truncated at any order of the expansion.

2.5 The Inter-Spike-Interval distribution

A key element of the theory I will develop is the single neuron Inter-Spike-Interval distribution (ISI). The ISI of cortical neurons has been sampled and studied in several works like [Ost11]. In the Physics community it has the name of first-passage time distribution which can be obtained by solving the backward Kolmogorov equation:

$$\partial_t \tilde{p} = L^\dagger \tilde{p}$$

where $\tilde{p}(x)$ gives the probability of reaching θ starting from x so clearly we have the following boundary condition:

$$\tilde{p}(\theta, t) = \delta(t)$$

For the processes like (2.13) the first-passage time distribution, namely $\rho(t) = \tilde{p}(H, t)$, can be solved in the Laplace domain:

$$s\rho = L^\dagger \rho$$

which has the general solution [Sie51]:

$$\rho(s) = e^{-s\tau_0} \frac{\psi(H, s)}{\psi(\theta, s)} \quad (2.25)$$

with $\psi(x, s)$ being the adjoint eigenfunction associated to the "eigenvalue" s . Note the interesting relation between the ISI distribution and the eigenvalues of the spectral expansion introduced above:

$$\rho(s = \lambda_n) = 1$$

. The n -th moment of the ISI, m_n can be computed as follows:

$$m_n = \int_{\tau_0}^{\infty} t^n \rho(t) dt = (-1)^n \frac{d^n \rho(s)}{ds^n} \Big|_{s=0}$$

In particular the first moment is the inverse of the gain-function:

$$\Phi(\mu, \sigma^2) = \frac{1}{m_1} \quad (2.26)$$

Chapter 3

A Rosetta Stone

Highly esteemed Professor Wien:

Unfortunately, almost everything that I reported to you, all too rashly, in my previous letters proved to be false upon closer examination.

Albert Einstein

Populations of spiking neuron models have densities of their microscopic variables (e.g., single-cell membrane potentials) whose evolution fully capture the collective dynamics of biological networks, even outside equilibrium. Despite its general applicability, the Fokker-Planck equation governing such evolution is mainly studied within the borders of the linear response theory, although alternative spectral expansion approaches offer some advantages in the study of the out-of-equilibrium dynamics. This is mainly due to the difficulty in computing the state-dependent coefficients of the expanded system of differential equations. Here, we address this issue by deriving analytic expressions for such coefficients by pairing perturbative solutions of the Fokker-Planck approach with their counterparts from the spectral expansion. A tight relationship emerges between several of these coefficients and the Laplace transform of the inter-spike interval density (i.e., the distribution of first-passage times). ‘Coefficients’ like the current-to-rate gain function, the eigenvalues of the Fokker-Planck operator and its eigenfunctions at the boundaries are derived without resorting to integral expressions. For the leaky integrate-and-fire neurons in particular, the coupling terms between stationary and nonstationary modes are also worked out paving the way to accurately characterize the critical points and the relaxation timescales in networks of interacting populations. The results that we derive in this chapter are essential to understand both the low dimensional dynamics in the mean-field limit and the corrections due to a finite size, i.e. number of neurons, that we will address in the following chapters.

3.1 Relaxation dynamics from the renewal theory

In what follows we aim at using the relaxation dynamics of an uncoupled set of neurons and the response to small perturbations of a coupled network as a ‘Rosetta stone’. This will allow us to translate some key expressions with a closed form in both linear response and renewal theory into compact and manageable sum of series and state-dependent coefficients for the spectral expansion approach. The results of this effort pave the way to a further exploitation of the spectral expansion to investigate the out-of-equilibrium dynamics of spiking neuron networks.

Note also that most of the results here reported are true for general integrate-and-fire neurons network. So unless specified, we will implicitly refer to the Fokker-Planck equation 2.21.

Under stationary condition and in presence of synaptic current fluctuations ($\sigma \neq 0$), the collective firing rate $\nu(t)$ of a set of uncoupled IF neurons always approaches an equilibrium point ν_0 . Note that for uncoupled neurons the mean and variance of the synaptic current, μ and σ^2 , do not depend on the population firing rate $\nu(t)$. Due to the reset mechanism following the emission of a spike, IF neurons are Markovian renewal processes. As such, ISIs separating two consecutive spikes do not depend on the ISIs occurred before. Finding the probability $\rho(t)dt$ to have an ISI in the interval $[t, t + dt]$ is a first-passage time problem [Tuc05], since it requires to know when $V(t)$ crosses the threshold θ for the first time starting from $V(0) = H$. With this initial condition, the ISI density can be interpreted as the probability of first-spike occurrence $\rho_1(t) \equiv \rho(t)$, leading to recursively define the density $\rho_k(t)$ of the time until the k -th emitted spike as

$$\rho_k(t) = \int_0^t \rho(\tau) \rho_{k-1}(t - \tau) d\tau. \quad (3.1)$$

This ‘renewal equation’ [Tuc05; Ger+14] allows to derive the so-called ‘hazard’ function, i.e., the mean density of spikes emitted by an isolated IF neuron at time t

$$\nu(t) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \rho_k(t), \quad (3.2)$$

which in turn is equivalent to the relaxation to equilibrium of the firing rate $\nu(t)$.

The firing rate in Eq. (3.2) has a straightforward Laplace transform $\nu(s) \equiv \int_0^{\infty} \nu(t) e^{-st} dt$. Indeed, being $\rho_k(t)$ a convolution, Eq. (3.1) reduces to

$$\rho_k(s) = \rho(s) \rho_{k-1}(s) = \rho(s)^k.$$

Introducing it in Eq. (3.2), $\nu(s)$ results to be

$$\begin{aligned} \nu(s) &= \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \rho_k(s) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \rho(s)^k = \frac{1}{1 - \rho(s)} - 1 \\ &= \frac{\rho(s)}{1 - \rho(s)}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.3)$$

This equation establishes a direct nonlocal relationship between the firing rate of a homogeneous pool of independent neurons and the ISI density of a single cell [CM77; Ger+14].

3.1.1 Relaxation dynamics from the spectral expansion

The firing rate $\nu(t)$ of the mentioned set of independent neurons can be alternatively derived by expanding the density $p(v, t)$ in Eq. (4.1) as

$$p(v, t) = \sum_n a_n(t) \phi_n(v),$$

where $\phi_n(v)$ are the eigenfunctions of the operator Fokker-Planck operator L defined in equation 2.22.

$$a_n(t) = \langle \psi_n | p \rangle = \int_{v_{\min}}^{\theta} \psi_n(v) p(v, t) dv$$

are the projections of p on the same modes (i.e., eigenfunctions). The infinite set $\{\psi_n(v)\}$ with $n \in \mathbb{I}$, is an orthonormal basis of a non-Hermitian space such that $\langle \psi_n | \phi_m \rangle = \delta_{nm}$ [KMS96; MD02]. Here, $\psi_n(v)$ are the eigenfunctions of the adjoint operator $L^\dagger = (F + \mu)\partial_v + \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2\partial_v^2$ defined as $\langle L^\dagger \psi_n | \phi_n \rangle \equiv \langle \psi_n | L \phi_n \rangle$: $L^\dagger \psi_n = \lambda_n \psi_n$. The ‘expanded’ p in the Fokker-Planck equation leads to the following equivalent dynamics for the projections a_n :

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\vec{a}} &= \mathbf{\Lambda} \vec{a} \\ \nu &= \Phi + \vec{f} \cdot \vec{a}, \end{aligned} \quad (3.4)$$

where the contribution due to the stationary mode ($n = 0$ with $\lambda_0 = 0$) has been isolated, and a matrix formalism has been adopted such that $\{\vec{a}\}_n = a_n$ and $\{\mathbf{\Lambda}\}_{nm} = \lambda_n \delta_{nm}$ with $m, n \neq 0$ [KMS96; MD02]. The current-to-rate gain function

$$\Phi(\mu, \sigma) = S_{\phi_0}(\theta) = -\frac{1}{2}\sigma^2\partial_v^2\phi_0 \Big|_{v=\theta} \quad (3.5)$$

is the flux of realization crossing θ under stationary condition, i.e., the asymptotic firing rate ν_0 . The flux due to the nonstationary modes (ϕ_n with $n \neq 0$) are instead the elements of the infinite vector \vec{f} , which can be conveniently set to $f_n = 1/\tau$ [DR17].

The linear system 3.4 has a straightforward solution having constant coefficients (μ and σ do not depend on time):

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{a}(t) &= e^{\mathbf{\Lambda}t} \vec{a}(0) \\ \nu(t) &= \Phi + \vec{f} \cdot \vec{a}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.6)$$

As all neurons have a starting membrane potential $V(0) = H$, $p(v, 0) = \delta(v - H)$ and the initial value of the projections result to be

$$a_n(0) = \langle \psi_n | p(v, 0) \rangle = \psi_n(H).$$

Written explicitly, Eq. (3.6) gives the relaxation dynamics

$$\nu(t) = \Phi + \frac{1}{\tau} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \psi_n(H) e^{\lambda_n t}. \quad (3.7)$$

3.1.2 ISI moments and sums in the spectral expansion

A first sum of coefficients from the spectral expansion results by setting $t = 0$ in the relaxation dynamics (3.6):

$$\Phi = -\vec{f} \cdot \vec{\psi}_H \equiv -\frac{1}{\tau} \sum_{n \neq 0} \psi_n(H), \quad (3.8)$$

where we took into account that $\nu(0) = 0$. This is a novel expression to carry out the current-to-rate gain function $\Phi(\mu, \sigma)$ for any IF neuron model and it is a first example of the relation between the ISI distribution and the spectral quantities of the Fokker-Planck operator.

We anticipate that this is only a particular case of a more general result. Indeed, the Laplace transform $\nu(s)$ from the renewal theory in 3.3 can be directly compared to the one resulting from the firing rate equation 3.4. In this case we have

$$\begin{aligned} s \vec{a}(s) - \vec{a}(0) &= \mathbf{\Lambda} \vec{a}(s) \\ \nu(s) &= \frac{\Phi}{s} + \vec{f} \cdot \vec{a}(s), \end{aligned}$$

leading to $\vec{a}(s) = (s\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{\Lambda})^{-1}\vec{\psi}_H$, and eventually to

$$v(s) = \frac{\Phi}{s} + \vec{f} \cdot (s\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{\Lambda})^{-1}\vec{\psi}_H. \quad (3.9)$$

Recalling Eq. (3.3) and comparing the two transform $v(s)$ we obtain:

$$\frac{\rho(s)}{1 - \rho(s)} - \frac{\Phi}{s} = \vec{f} \cdot (s\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{\Lambda})^{-1}\vec{\psi}_H \equiv h(s), \quad (3.10)$$

highlighting a tight relationship between the ISI density $\rho(t)$, the eigenvalues λ_n and $\vec{\psi}_H$.

From Eq. (3.10) other sums can be worked out recalling that the ISI moments $\langle (-t)^k \rangle = \lim_{s \rightarrow 0} \frac{d^k \rho(s)}{ds^k}$. We then perform the same limit on both hand sides of the equation resorting to the l'Hôpital's rule and finding that

$$\lim_{s \rightarrow 0} h(s) = \frac{\Phi \langle t^2 \rangle - 2 \langle t \rangle}{2 \langle t \rangle}.$$

Here, considering that the gain function $\Phi = 1/\langle t \rangle$ and that $h(0) = -\vec{f} \cdot \mathbf{\Lambda}^{-1}\vec{\psi}_H$, we obtain

$$h(0) = \frac{c_v^2 - 1}{2} = -\frac{1}{\tau} \sum_{n \neq 0} \frac{\psi_n(H)}{\lambda_n}, \quad (3.11)$$

where $c_v = \sqrt{\langle t^2 \rangle - \langle t \rangle^2} / \langle t \rangle$ is the coefficient of variation of the ISIs.

We remark that other sums can be worked out deriving by s both hand sides of Eq. (3.10) and taking the limit $s \rightarrow 0$. Indeed, in this limit the derivatives of $h(s)$ reduce to

$$\left. \frac{d^k h}{ds^k} \right|_{s \rightarrow 0} = -k! \vec{f} \cdot \mathbf{\Lambda}^{-(k+1)} \vec{\psi}_H = -\frac{k!}{\tau} \sum_{n \neq 0} \frac{\psi_n(H)}{\lambda_n^{k+1}}$$

for any $k > 0$.

3.1.3 Eigenvalues λ_k and eigenfunction values $\psi_k(H)$

We can further exploit (3.10) by making use of the Cauchy's residue theorem. Indeed,

$$\text{Res}_{s=\lambda_k} h(s) = \text{Res}_{s=\lambda_k} \frac{\rho(s)}{1 - \rho(s)} = \psi_k(H) \quad (3.12)$$

for $\lambda_k \neq 0$. This allows us to work out from the Laplace transform of the ISI probability density the value of the k -th eigenfunction of L^\dagger at $v = H$. In this way $\psi_k(H)$ can be found without explicitly knowing neither the analytic expression for $\psi(v, s)$ nor the exact value of the λ_k . As $s = \lambda_k$ are poles of $h(s)$, a generic line integral of $\rho/(1 - \rho)$ around each eigenvalues will give $\psi_k(H)$.

Note that, being $h(0)$ in Eq. (3.11) a finite function of the ISI c_v , $h(s)$ has no poles in 0. Thus, the above residue of $h(s)$ in $s = \lambda_0 = 0$ – the eigenvalue of the stationary mode – is 0. This allows to derive from Eqs (3.10) and (3.12) an alternative expression for the current-to-rate gain function:

$$\Phi = \text{Res}_{s=0} \frac{\rho(s)}{1 - \rho(s)} = \psi_0(H). \quad (3.13)$$

In principle, this general result leads to work out novel analytic expressions for the gain functions of specific neuron models, as we will show later.

Similarly, the eigenvalues λ_k can be obtained without resorting to a often complicated minimization procedure as

$$\frac{\text{Res}_{s=\lambda_k} s h(s)}{\text{Res}_{s=\lambda_k} h(s)} = \frac{\lambda_k \psi_k(H)}{\psi_k(H)} = \lambda_k. \quad (3.14)$$

3.1.4 Spectral equation for λ_k from $\rho(s)$

The link between the spectrum of L^\dagger and $\rho(s)$ pointed out by Eq. (3.10) should not be surprising as $\rho(t)$ is the density of a first-passage time. As such, $\rho(t)$ conditioned to have $V(0) = H$ and $V(t) = \theta$, solves the backward Kolmogorov equation [CM77; Tuc05]

$$\partial_t \rho = A(H) \partial_H \rho + \frac{1}{2} B(H) \partial_H^2 \rho = L_H^\dagger \rho,$$

with boundary condition $\rho(t)|_{H=\theta} = \delta(t)$. In our case of study $A(H) = f(v) + \mu|_{v=H}$ and $B(H) = \sigma^2$. For the sake of clarity, we write explicitly the dependence of the operator L_H^\dagger on the initial value of the membrane potential.

Performing the Laplace transform of both hand sides of the above equation we obtain

$$-\rho(t)|_{t=0} + s\rho(s) = L_H^\dagger \rho(s)$$

with $\rho(s)$ the Laplace transform of the ISI density implicitly depending on θ . In the case of interest, $H < \theta$ and no spikes are emitted at $t = 0$ such that $\rho(t)|_{t=0} = 0$ and the above equation reduces to

$$(L_H^\dagger - s)\rho(H, s) = 0,$$

where we made explicit the dependence of ρ on the initial potential H . As pointed out in [Sie51], this is exactly the same equation for the eigenfunctions $\psi_k(v) = \psi(v, \lambda_k)$ provided that $s = \lambda_k$ leading to the equivalence:

$$\rho(H, s) = a(s)\psi(H, s).$$

The arbitrary function $a(s)$ can be derived taking into account the boundary condition $\rho(\theta, t) = \delta(t)$ leading to $\rho(\theta, s) = 1$ and hence to $a(s) = 1/\psi(\theta, s)$, allowing to recover the known relationship [Sie51]

$$\rho(s) = \frac{\psi(H, s)}{\psi(\theta, s)}. \quad (3.15)$$

Following [PGS20], this equation allows to derive a spectral equation to determine the eigenvalues λ_k . Indeed, from the boundary condition associated to the conservation of flux of realizations exiting from θ and reentering in H after the emission of spike, we have $\psi(H, \lambda_k) = \psi(\theta, \lambda_k)$ [KMS96; Kni00; MD02]. Incorporating this constraint into Eq. (3.15) we eventually have

$$\rho(\lambda_k) = 1, \quad (3.16)$$

i.e., yet another way to compute the eigenvalues of the Fokker-Planck operator in (2.21).

3.1.5 Normalization factor of eigenfunctions $\psi_k(v)$

As summarized at the beginning of this Section, the spectral expansion of the population density relies on the assumption that the eigenfunctions $\psi_k(v)$ and $\phi_k(v)$ are orthonormal, i.e.,

$$\langle \psi_n | \phi_m \rangle = \int_{v_{\min}}^{\theta} \psi_n(v) \phi_m(v) dv = \delta_{nm}.$$

Such condition is guaranteed by normalizing the generic solution of the equation $(L^\dagger - \lambda_k)\tilde{\psi}_k = 0$ by a factor Z_k in order to have $\psi_k \equiv \tilde{\psi}_k/Z_k$ and

$$Z_k = \langle \tilde{\psi}_k | \phi_k \rangle = \int_{v_{\min}}^{\theta} \tilde{\psi}_k(v) \phi_k(v) dv.$$

This integral expression requires to know explicitly the eigenfunctions of both L and L^\dagger . Not only, even when they are available, a closed form of this integral is difficult to be obtained. Hence, its numerical evaluation is required even when the integration domain is infinite, as usually $v_{\min} \rightarrow -\infty$, eventually making the computation of Z_k demanding.

Even in this case, a way out to this issue is offered by the residue theorem starting from the knowledge of $\rho(s)$. Indeed, inserting Eq. (3.15) into Eq. (3.12) we have

$$\text{Res}_{s=\lambda_k} \frac{\tilde{\psi}(H, s)}{\tilde{\psi}(\theta, s) - \tilde{\psi}(H, s)} = \psi_k(H) = \frac{\tilde{\psi}_k(H)}{Z_k},$$

where we took into account that the normalization factor does not depend on v and thus the equivalence $\psi(H, s)/\psi(\theta, s) = \tilde{\psi}(H, s)/\tilde{\psi}(\theta, s)$ holds. Putting out from the residue computation the numerator which becomes $\tilde{\psi}(H, s) \rightarrow \tilde{\psi}_k(H)$, the following expression results

$$\text{Res}_{s=\lambda_k} \frac{1}{\tilde{\psi}(\theta, s) - \tilde{\psi}(H, s)} = \frac{1}{Z_k} \quad (3.17)$$

giving the normalization factor as a limit expression without computing any integral or knowing $\phi_k(v)$. This equation can be further developed, as the limit underlying the residue can be solved resorting to the l'Hôpital's rule eventually leading to have

$$Z_k = \tilde{\psi}'_k(\theta) - \tilde{\psi}'_k(H), \quad (3.18)$$

with $\tilde{\psi}'_k(v) = \partial_s \tilde{\psi}(v, s)|_{s=\lambda_k}$. The above integral expression of Z_k thus reduces to a combination of derivatives of the eigenfunction $\tilde{\psi}(v, s)$. Given this integral-free normalization factor, from Eq. (3.13) an analytic expression for the current-to-rate gain function can be worked out:

$$\Phi = \frac{\tilde{\psi}_0(H)}{\tilde{\psi}'_0(\theta) - \tilde{\psi}'_0(H)}. \quad (3.19)$$

We now apply all the previous results to the specific case of LIF neurons that we will use as benchmark in the following chapters.

3.1.6 Density $\rho(s)$ and gain $\Phi(\mu, \sigma)$ for notable neurons

The simplest model is the perfect IF (PIF) neuron introduced in [GM64] in which the membrane potential $V(t)$ is a diffusion Wiener process with drift, i.e., $F(V) = \mu$. In this model ISI moments are finite only if $\mu > 0$, and the ISI density $\rho(s)$ is an inverse Gaussian whose Laplace transform is [DS53; CM77; Tuc05]

$$\rho_{\text{PIF}}(s) = \exp \left[\frac{\theta - H}{\sigma^2} \left(\mu - \sqrt{\mu^2 + 2\sigma^2 s} \right) \right]. \quad (3.20)$$

From this, the first and second moments of the ISI result to be $\langle t \rangle = 1/\Phi = (\theta - H)/\mu$ and $\langle t^2 \rangle = \sigma^2/(\mu^2 \Phi)$ [Tuc05].

A generalization of the PIF neuron model is the one in which a reflecting barrier at $v_{\min} = 0$ is incorporated, allowing to have finite moments of the ISI also for $\mu \leq 0$. The model was introduced as a former 'neuromorphic' implementation in VLSI circuits of an IF neuron [Mea89]. This VLSI IF (VIF) neuron has a closed form of $\rho(s)$ [FM99]:

$$\rho_{\text{VIF}}(s) = \frac{\zeta(s) e^\xi}{\zeta(s) \cosh[\zeta(s)] + \xi \sinh[\zeta(s)]} \quad (3.21)$$

with $\xi = \theta\mu/\sigma^2$ and $\zeta(s) = \sqrt{\xi^2 + 2s\theta/\sigma^2}$, fixing the reset potential at the reflecting barrier $H = v_{\min} = 0$.

The standard, and widely used, leaky integrate-and-fire (LIF) neuron with $F(V) = -V/\tau$ has also a closed form for the Laplace transform of the ISI density [Sie51; CR71]:

$$\rho_{\text{LIF}}(s) = \frac{\sqrt{e^{x_r^2}} \mathcal{D}_{-s}(-\sqrt{2}x_r)}{\sqrt{e^{x_t^2}} \mathcal{D}_{-s}(-\sqrt{2}x_t)} \quad (3.22)$$

with $x_t = (\theta - \mu\tau)/\sigma\sqrt{\tau}$ and $x_r = (H - \mu\tau)/\sigma\sqrt{\tau}$. $\mathcal{D}_\nu(z)$ is the parabolic cylinder function solution of the Weber differential equation [DLM17].

From Eq. (3.15) we can rewrite $\rho(s) = \tilde{\psi}(x_r, s)/\tilde{\psi}(x_t, s)$ simplifying the normalization factor, thus allowing to derive the eigenfunctions $\tilde{\psi}(x, s)$ for the mentioned IF neurons. For the specific case of the LIF neuron we have

$$\tilde{\psi}_{\text{LIF}}(x, s) = e^{\frac{x^2}{2}} \mathcal{D}_{-s}(-\sqrt{2}x), \quad (3.23)$$

which for the stationary mode $s = 0$ reduces to $\tilde{\psi}_{\text{LIF}}(x, 0) = 1$ [DLM17]. With this we can compute the current-to-rate gain function Φ_{LIF} from Eq. (3.19):

$$\Phi_{\text{LIF}}(x_r, x_t) = \frac{1}{\tilde{\psi}'_{0,\text{LIF}}(x_t) - \tilde{\psi}'_{0,\text{LIF}}(x_r)}, \quad (3.24)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\psi}'_{0,\text{LIF}}(x) &= \partial_s \tilde{\psi}_{\text{LIF}}(x, s) \Big|_{s=0} \\ &= -e^{\frac{x^2}{2}} \mathcal{D}_0^{(1,0)}(-\sqrt{2}x) \\ &= \frac{\pi}{2} \text{Erfi}(x) + x^2 {}_2F_2\left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}; \frac{3}{2}, 2; x^2\right). \end{aligned} \quad (3.25)$$

Here $\mathcal{D}_0^{(1,0)}(z) = \partial_\nu \mathcal{D}_\nu(z) \Big|_{\nu=0}$, $\text{Erfi}(x)$ is the imaginary error function and ${}_2F_2(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, x)$ is the generalized hypergeometric function defined in [DLM17]. To derive such expression we used the explicit formula for $\mathcal{D}_\nu^{(1,0)}(z)$ in [Bry08] valid in the limit $\nu \rightarrow 0$. Note that expanding ${}_2F_2$ in series, the mean output frequency previously derived in [RS69; CR71] is recovered.

In Fig. 3.1 we compare this new expression and the standard current-to-rate gain function from [Joh68; RS79]

$$\Phi_{\text{LIF}}(x_r, x_t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi} \int_{x_r}^{x_t} e^{u^2} [1 + \text{erf}(u)] du}. \quad (3.26)$$

As expected the two Φ_{LIF} overlap perfectly. However, we remark that the numerical computation of Eq. (3.24) is more demanding and its stability weakens for relatively small variances σ^2 .

3.1.7 Eigenvalues and relaxation $\nu(t)$ of LIF neurons

Given for these example neurons the eigenfunctions $\psi(v, s)$, we can directly test the validity of some the general equations derived in this Section. To do that we first compute the eigenvalues λ_k . From Eq. (3.16), for the PIF neuron they result to be [PGS20]

$$\lambda_n = -2\pi^2 \frac{\sigma^2}{(\theta - H)^2} n^2 + i2\pi\Phi n. \quad (3.27)$$

Figure 3.1: Comparison of the current-to-rate gain function Φ_{LIF} from the standard Eq. (3.26) (solid) and the novel Eq. (3.24) (dashed) for two example synaptic-current variance $\sigma^2\tau = 1$ mV and 4 mV (green and blue, respectively). Φ_{LIF} is functions of the current moments as $x_t = x_t(\mu, \sigma)$ and $x_r = x_r(\mu, \sigma)$ (see main text). Neuron parameters are $\tau = 20$ ms, $\theta = 20$ mV and $H = 0$.

As under strongly drift-dominated regime [$\mu \gg F(\theta)$] both LIF and VIF neurons are well approximated by a PIF model, it is not surprising to see that the above expression has been previously worked out in both [AV93; KMS96; Kni00] and [MD02], respectively. Equation (3.27) can then be exploited as an initial guess of λ_n in order to identify a suited line integral to work out the actual eigenvalues from Eq. (3.14). Note that, in the regimes dominated by the current fluctuations σ , λ_n are no more well approximated by Eq. (3.27) as they are real [MD02]. Besides, for LIF and VIF neurons with $v_{\min} < H$, an additional set of real λ_k exists [Aug+17]. These λ_k can be found and computed by searching along the real axis ($\text{Im } s = 0$) the non-zero residues in Eq. (3.14).

In Fig. 3.2(a) the eigenvalues (circles) computed, as an example, for set of uncoupled and identical LIF neurons is shown. As remarked, we have both complex conjugate couples and real λ_k . The eigenvalues are found at the intersection of the solution of both the real and imaginary part of the spectral equation $\rho_{\text{LIF}}(s) = 1$ (red and blue curves, respectively). This confirms the reliability of the approach we introduced. Note that, also the eigenvalue $\lambda_0 = 0$ of the stationary mode is shown. In Fig. 3.2(b) a wider set of λ_k ($M = 100$) computed in the same way is plotted. On one hand the complex conjugate eigenvalues are distributed along a rotated parabola, as expected from Eq. (3.27). On the other hand, the real λ_k display a non-uniform distribution.

With the availability of such a large number of eigenvalues for the LIF neuron, we can test the rate of convergence of some of the series derived in this Section. First we look at the relaxation dynamics of $v(t)$ given by Eq. (3.7). Not surprisingly, as previously described in [MD02; SOA13; PGS20], by increasing the number M of summed modes the accuracy in reproducing $v(t)$ at shorter time scales improves [Fig. 3.2(c)]. The modes included are sorted by $-\lambda_k$ covering decreasingly timescales ($-1/\lambda_k$). For instance, as the second couple of complex conjugate λ_k in Fig. 3.2(a-b) is $\lambda_k\tau \approx -5$, the case $M = 2$ accurately reproduces $v(t)$ as $t \gg \tau/5 \approx 4$ ms (compare light-red and black curves).

Note that, at $t < -1/\lambda_M$ the estimated $v(t)$ from the corresponding sum of M terms

Figure 3.2: Eigenvalues λ_k and relaxation dynamics of the firing rate $\nu(t)$ of an uncoupled set of LIF neurons. (a) Distribution of λ_k , roots of the spectral equation $\rho_{\text{LIF}}(s) = 1$ (circles). Red and blue curves, separate solutions of $\text{Re } \rho_{\text{LIF}}(s) = 1$ and $\text{Im } \rho_{\text{LIF}}(s) = 0$, respectively. (b) Same as (a) for a wider set (100) of λ_k computed as the ratio of residues in Eq. (3.14) with line integrals around the approximated guesses of the eigenvalues (see text). (c) Relaxation dynamics of $\nu(t)$ as in Eq. (3.7) including a finite number M of eigenmodes (those with greatest $\text{Re } \lambda_k$). Only the real part of the sum is taken, as with $M = \{2, 4, 8, 16, 32, 64\}$ not all the complete pairs of complex conjugate λ_k are necessarily selected. Red dashed line, stationary firing rate $\Phi_{\text{LIF}}(\mu, \sigma) = 11.8$ Hz. Neuron parameters: $\tau = 20$ ms, $\theta = 20$ mV, $H = 0$ mV, $\mu\tau = 17$ mV and $\sigma\sqrt{\tau} = 4.5$ mV.

in Eq. (3.7) blows up. This means that in the limit $t \rightarrow 0$ we need a rapidly increasing number of modes to have an accurate estimate of $\nu(t) \rightarrow 0$. This is the limit when Eq. (3.7) reduces to Eq. (3.8), meaning that the latter does not appear to be a convenient way to compute $\Phi_{\text{LIF}}(\mu, \sigma)$. To make this argument clearer, in Fig. 3.3(a), for different $\Delta t \ll 1/\Phi$, such that $\nu(\Delta t) \simeq 0$, we show how slowly the sum in Eq. (3.7) approximate Φ_{LIF} (red-dashed line). For the cases plotted ($\Delta t = \{8, 4, 2\}$ ms), M rapidly diverges in order to well approximate the asymptotic firing rate (red-dashed line, $M = \{6, 13, 31\}$,

Figure 3.3: Rate of convergence of the series giving the gain function Φ and coefficient of variation c_v of the ISI for LIF neurons. (a) Φ_{LIF} estimated from Eq. (3.7) considering $\nu(\Delta t) \simeq 0$ for $\Delta t \ll 1/\Phi_{\text{LIF}} \simeq 85$ ms. The sum $\tau^{-1} \sum_{n=1}^M \psi_{n,\text{LIF}}(H) e^{\lambda_n \Delta t}$ is computed by varying the number of modes M sorted by $-\lambda_k$. Different Δt are tested: 2 ms, circles; 4 ms, squares; 8 ms, diamonds. Dashed red line, Φ_{LIF} as in Fig. 3.2(c). (b) c_v^2 computed from Eq. (3.11): $1 - 2\tau^{-1} \sum_{n=1}^M \psi_{n,\text{LIF}}(H) \lambda_n$. The sum is computed as in (a). Dashed red line, $c_v^2 = 0.35$ resulting from the ISI moments computed from the derivatives of the Laplace transform $\rho_{\text{LIF}}(s)$. Neuron parameters as in Fig. 3.2.

respectively). A limited rate of convergence is also apparent in Fig. 3.3(b), where the coefficient of variation c_v of the ISI for the same LIF neurons computed from Eq. (3.11) is shown by varying the M modes summed. We will come back to the truncation to a limited number of modes in Chapter 5.

3.2 Linear response as a 'Rosetta stone'

Since now, we focused on a set of uncoupled spiking neurons. In other words, the expressions we derived pertain to the single-neuron domain. However, a similar approach facing the spectral expansion and the perturbative description of the population dynamics can be further extended. In this Section we focus on this aspect, complementing our 'Rosetta stone' approach to the case of the linear response theory of networks of spiking neurons. The aim is to derive a closed formula for the integrals giving the coupling coefficients appearing in the spectral expansion when neurons in the network are synaptically coupled. In other words now the moments of the moments of the synaptic current (2.12) will depend on the population firing rate since the average synaptic weights $J \neq 0$.

3.2.1 Linear response from spectral expansion

Under the 'extended' mean-field approximation [AB97], the drift and diffusion coefficients of the Fokker-Planck equation for a network of coupled spiking neurons are function of the firing rate ν . This because both the infinitesimal mean and variance of the synaptic current depend on the network activity: $\mu = \mu(\nu)$ and $\sigma^2 = \sigma^2(\nu)$. In this general framework the dynamics of the projection coefficients $a_k(t)$ and of $\nu(t)$ result to be [KMS96; MD02]

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\vec{a}} &= (\mathbf{\Lambda} + \mathbf{C}\dot{\nu}) \vec{a} + \vec{c} \dot{\nu} \\ \nu &= \Phi + \vec{f} \cdot \vec{a} \end{aligned} \quad , \quad (3.28)$$

where in addition to the coefficients found in Eq. (3.4), the coupling terms between modes are defined as $\{\mathbf{C}\}_{nm} = \langle \partial_\nu \psi_n | \phi_m \rangle$ and $\{\vec{c}\}_n = \langle \partial_\nu \psi_n | \phi_0 \rangle$ for any $m, n \neq 0$.

The couplings can in general affect both current moments μ and σ^2 independently, and perturbations of the input received by the neurons in the network can be a combination of the following changes

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(t) &= \mu_0 + \epsilon_\mu(t) \\ \sigma^2(t) &= \sigma_0^2 + \epsilon_{\sigma^2}(t) \end{aligned} \quad ,$$

In what follows, only the input changes $\epsilon(t)$ up to the first order are taken into account (i.e., $o(\epsilon^2) \simeq 0$).

Under this approximation, the Fourier transform of Eq. (3.28) leads to the Fourier transfer function $H_\epsilon(\omega)$ of the firing rate [MD02; MD04]

$$H_\epsilon(\omega) \equiv \frac{\nu_1(\omega)}{\epsilon(\omega)} = \partial_\epsilon \Phi + i\omega \vec{f} (i\omega \mathbf{I} - \mathbf{\Lambda})^{-1} \vec{c}_\epsilon, \quad (3.29)$$

where $\nu_1(\omega) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (\nu(t) - \nu_0) e^{-i\omega t} dt$ is the Fourier transform of the firing rate fluctuating around $\nu_0 = \Phi(\mu_0, \sigma_0)$, $\epsilon(\omega)$ is the same transform for $\epsilon(t)$ and $\{\vec{c}_\epsilon\}_n = \langle \partial_\epsilon \psi_n | \phi_0 \rangle$. With this notation we generalize the derivatives associated to the input changes as $d/d\epsilon$, which eventually should be replaced by either $d/d\mu$ or $d/d\sigma^2$.

3.2.2 Eigenfunction ψ_n from Fokker-Planck equation

The same transfer function $H(\omega)$ can be worked out directly from the Fokker-Planck (2.15) [Gam+98], a perturbative approach adopted in the study of spiking neuron networks (see for instance [Bru+01; LS01]). For example, in networks of LIF neurons for which analytical results can be carried out, we start rescaling the membrane potential V as

$$x = \frac{V - \mu_0 \tau}{\sigma_0 \sqrt{\tau}}, \quad (3.30)$$

leading to simplify the Fokker-Planck equation (2.15) into:

$$\partial_t p(x, t) = \partial_x(xp) + \frac{1}{2} \partial_x^2 p \equiv L_x p.$$

As above, μ_0 and σ_0 do not depend on time and set the fixed point around which perturbations are studied. For the sake of simplicity we set $\tau = 1$. A different unit time can be adopted simply multiplying by τ all the variables like μ_0 , σ_0^2 , $v(t)$ and λ_n .

In general, the spectral equation $(L_x - \lambda_n)\phi_n = 0$ is a second-order differential equation which can be recast into the general form

$$k_2(x) \frac{d^2 \phi_n}{dx^2} + k_1(x) \frac{d \phi_n}{dx} + k_0(\lambda_n) \phi_n = 0 \quad (3.31)$$

where ϕ_n result to be a combination of two fundamental (i.e., independent) solutions $f_1(x, \lambda_n)$ and $f_2(x, \lambda_n)$ of the same equation. The coefficients a , b and d of the combination are determined by solving a linear system determined by the boundary conditions of the problem (see for instance [DR17]):

$$\phi_n(x) = \begin{cases} a f_1(x, \lambda) + b f_2(x, \lambda) & x_r < x < x_t \\ d f_2(x, \lambda) & x < x_r \end{cases},$$

where we arbitrarily impose $f_2(x, \lambda_n) \rightarrow 0$ in the limit $x \rightarrow x_{\min}$. The threshold x_t and the reset x_r values comes from Eq. (3.30) by setting $V = \theta$ and $V = H$, respectively.

The eigenfunctions $\psi_n(x) = \psi(x, \lambda_n)$ of the adjoint Fokker-Planck operator L_x^\dagger can be derived from the same fundamental solutions of Eq. (3.31). They rely also on the Wronskian $W(x) = f_1'(x) f_2(x) - f_1(x) f_2'(x)$ which can be in general expressed as [DLM17]

$$W(x) = C e^{-\int \frac{k_1(x)}{k_2(x)} dx}, \quad (3.32)$$

being a solution of the differential equation $W'(x) = -k_1(x)/k_2(x)$ solvable up to a constant factor C . Note that although W depends on f_1 and f_2 it does not depend on λ_n and for the LIF neuron we have $W_{\text{LIF}}(x) = e^{-x^2}$.

As mentioned above, to derive the adjoint eigenfunctions two boundary conditions must be taken into account: i) $\psi_n(x_t) = \psi_n(x_r)$ and ii) $\psi_n(x)$ must be smooth on all the domain of x [KMS96; Kni00; MD02]. With these conditions the adjoint eigenfunctions are in general

$$\psi_n(x) = \psi(x, \lambda_n) = \frac{f_2(x, \lambda_n)}{Z_n W(x)}, \quad (3.33)$$

being it a solution of the spectral equation $(L_x^\dagger - \lambda_n)\psi_n = 0$ if Eq. (3.32) is also taken into account [DR17]. The normalization factor Z_n is the same as the Eq. (3.17).

3.2.3 Linear response from Fokker-Planck equation

To derive a closed formula for the transfer function $H_\epsilon(\omega)$ directly from the Fokker-Planck equation we follow the perturbative approach exploited in [BH99; Ric07] to the study of IF neuron networks. In this framework Eq. (4.1) with the standardized variable x can be decomposed by developing in Taylor series the probability density

$$p(x, t) = \phi_0(x) + \epsilon(t)p_1(x) + o(\epsilon^2).$$

The eigenfunction ϕ_0 is the stationary probability density when the input current has constant moments μ_0 and σ_0 . As a consequence, the firing rate $\nu(t)$ is

$$\nu(t) = \Phi - \frac{1}{2}p_1'(x_t)\epsilon(t) + o(\epsilon^2),$$

where p_1' is the derivative with respect to x . The transfer function we are looking for results to be

$$H_\epsilon^{(P)}(\omega) = \frac{\nu_1(\omega)}{\epsilon(\omega)} = -\frac{p_1'(x_t)}{2}. \quad (3.34)$$

Considering that also the operator L_x depends on ϵ we can write it as $L_x = L_{x0} + \epsilon(t)L_{x1} + o(\epsilon^2)$ leading to

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\epsilon}p_1 &= L_{x0}\phi_0 + (L_{x0}p_1 + L_{x1}\phi_0)\epsilon + o(\epsilon^2) \\ &\simeq (L_{x0}p_1 + L_{x1}\phi_0)\epsilon \end{aligned}$$

The Laplace transform of both hand side of this equation affects only $\epsilon(t)$, leading to the disappearance of its transform $\epsilon(s)$:

$$s p_1(x) = L_{x0}p_1(x) + F_0(x) \quad (3.35)$$

with $F_0(x) = L_{x1}\phi_0$. As in [BH99], from this equation $p_1(x)$ can be derived as the sum of two solutions: the homogeneous equation $(L_{x0} - s)p_1 = 0$, which is the same as our usual spectral equation with $s = \lambda_n$, and a particular solution $Q(x, s)$ to be determined:

$$p_1(x) = \begin{cases} a f_1(x) + b f_2(x) + Q(x) & x_r < x < x_t \\ d f_2(x) + Q(x) & x < x_r \end{cases}.$$

For the sake of clarity, the dependency on s here is implicit. As in the above derivation, the usual boundary conditions lead to a system of linear equations in a , b and d to be solved. After some algebra and referring to Eq. (3.33) (see Appendix A for details), we found that:

$$p_1'(x_t) = \frac{W_{Q, f_2}(x_t)}{W(x_t)Z} - \frac{W_{\Delta Q, f_2}(x_r)}{W(x_r)Z} \quad (3.36)$$

where the Wronskian $W(x)$ is from Eq. (3.32), $\Delta Q(x) = \lim_{\delta \rightarrow 0} Q(x + |\delta|) - Q(x - |\delta|)$ and $W_{f, g}(x) = f'(x)g(x) - f(x)g'(x)$. We remark that this formula is valid in general for any IF neuron model. Besides it depends only on the particular solution $Q(x)$ and on the eigenfunction ψ , as from Eq. (3.33) $f_2(x) = \psi(x) Z W(x)$ with $Z(s) = Z_n|_{\lambda_n=s}$. As above all these function implicitly depend also on s and then on the eigenvalues if $s = \lambda_n$.

Equation (3.36) can be further simplified by resorting to the method of the variation of constants such that the particular solution can be written as a combination of the fundamental solutions of Eq. (3.31):

$$Q(x) = A_1(x)f_1(x) + A_2(x)f_2(x),$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} A_1(x) &\equiv -2 \int_{-\infty}^x \frac{f_2(y)}{W(y)} F_0(y) dy \\ A_2(x) &\equiv 2 \int_{-\infty}^x \frac{f_1(y)}{W(y)} F_0(y) dy \end{aligned} .$$

After some substitutions we can derive a much more compact expression:

$$p'_1(x_t) = -2 \frac{\int_{-\infty}^{x_t} \psi(y) F_0(y) dy}{\psi(x_t) - \psi(x_r)} . \quad (3.37)$$

It is interesting to note that from this general result arises the relationship between the dynamic response ($p'_1(x_t)$), the statistics of the single-neuron first-passage time ($\psi(x)$) and the stationary state (F_0).

3.2.4 Matching the transfer functions to derive c_{n0}

For the specific case of the LIF neuron and considering an input change affecting only the drift μ , we have $F_0(x) = -\phi'_0(x)/\sigma_0$. The related particular solution of Eq. (3.35) can be verified to be [BH99]

$$Q_\mu(x, s) = -\frac{\phi'_0(x)}{\sigma_0(s+1)} .$$

Recalling that $\nu_0 = \Phi = -\phi'_0(x_t)/2$, we remark that $Q_\mu(x_t, s) = 2\nu_0/[\sigma_0(s+1)]$ highlighting the direct link between $Q(x)$ and the flux of realizations $S_{\phi_0}(x)$ under stationary condition. Making use of all this information in Eq. (3.36) (see Appendix A for details), we can derive p'_1 and hence from Eq. (3.29), the transfer function of the modulated drift $\mu(t)$ of the input current

$$H_\mu^{(P)}(s) = \frac{\nu_0}{\sigma_0(s+1)} \frac{\partial_x \psi(x_t, s) - \partial_x \psi(x_r, s)}{\psi(x_t, s) - \psi(x_r, s)} . \quad (3.38)$$

where $\partial_x \psi(x, s)$ are the derivative computed at x . With a similar derivation detailed in Appendix A, the transfer function of the perturbations to the variance $\sigma^2(t)$ result to be

$$H_\sigma^{(P)}(s) = \frac{\nu_0}{\sigma_0^2(s+2)} \left(s - \frac{x_t \partial_x \psi(x_t, s) - x_r \partial_x \psi(x_r, s)}{\psi(x_t, s) - \psi(x_r, s)} \right) . \quad (3.39)$$

These two expressions are due to [BH99] for the modulation of μ and to [LS01] for the modulation of σ^2 . Interestingly, [LS01] incorporates the explicit expression of $\partial_x \psi$ which, from [DLM17], is

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_x \psi(x, s) &= \sqrt{2} \psi(x, s-1) + 2x \psi(x, s) \\ &= e^{\frac{x^2}{2}} \left(\sqrt{2} \mathcal{D}_{1-s}(-\sqrt{2}x) + 2x \mathcal{D}_{-s}(-\sqrt{2}x) \right) . \end{aligned}$$

As under the mean-field approximation we know that both the mean and the variance of the input current depend on the firing rate ν , from these expressions the rate-to-rate transfer function $H_\nu(s)$ can be eventually carried out:

$$H_\nu(s) = H_\mu(s) \frac{d\mu}{d\nu} + H_\sigma(s) \frac{d\sigma^2}{d\nu}$$

We conclude deriving an expression for the coupling coefficients between nonstationary and stationary modes $c_{n0}^{(\epsilon)} = \{\vec{c}_\epsilon\}_n$ found in Eqs. (3.28) and (3.29). To this purpose we

note that the transfer function $H_\epsilon(s)$ (where $s = i\omega$) derived with the spectral expansion approach, can give

$$\text{Res}_{s=\lambda_k} H_\epsilon(s) = \lambda_n c_{n0}^{(\epsilon)}.$$

Due to the equivalence between this $H_\epsilon(s)$ and $H_\epsilon^{(P)}(s)$ from the above perturbative approach, we can carry out an explicit expression for the coupling coefficients as

$$c_{n0}^{(\epsilon)} = \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \text{Res}_{s=\lambda_k} H_\epsilon^{(P)}(s).$$

To compute the residues from Eqs. (3.38) and (3.39), we point out that the spectral equation Eq. (3.16) can be expressed directly in terms of adjoint eigenfunction: $\psi(H, \lambda_k) = \psi(\theta, \lambda_k)$. From this we have

$$\text{Res}_{s=\lambda_k} \frac{1}{\psi(\theta, \lambda_k) - \psi(H, \lambda_k)} = 1,$$

which straightforwardly leads to

$$c_{n0}^{(\mu)} = \frac{\nu_0}{\sigma_0 \lambda_n (\lambda_n + 1)} (\psi'_n(x_t) - \psi'_n(x_r)) \quad (3.40)$$

and to

$$c_{n0}^{(\sigma)} = -\frac{\nu_0}{2\sigma_0^2 \lambda_n (\lambda_n + 2)} (x_t \psi'_n(x_t) - x_r \psi'_n(x_r)). \quad (3.41)$$

Remarkably, as for the LIF neuron we have

$$\psi_n(x) = \frac{e^{x^2/2}}{Z_n} \mathcal{D}_{-\lambda_n}(-\sqrt{2}x), \quad (3.42)$$

once we know the eigenvalues λ_n , the expressions for both $c_{n0}^{(\mu)}$ and $c_{n0}^{(\sigma)}$ are closed formulas, not requiring any integral on the x -domain. Finally, recalling the dependence on ν of the moments of synaptic current in Eq. (2.11), the coupling coefficients in the firing rate equation Eq. (3.28) are

$$\begin{aligned} c_{n0} &= \langle \partial_\nu \psi_n | \phi_0 \rangle \\ &= \frac{d\mu}{d\nu} c_{n0}^{(\mu)} + \frac{d\sigma^2}{d\nu} c_{n0}^{(\sigma)}, \\ &= \tau K J \left(c_{n0}^{(\mu)} + J(1 + \Delta^2) c_{n0}^{(\sigma)} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (3.43)$$

where we reintroduced explicitly τ .

Back to the general case of arbitrary spiking neuron, we can use Eq. (3.37) to find a general formula for $c_{n0}^{(\epsilon)}$. If we compute the residue of H_ϵ at the eigenvalues we find an alternative integral expression:

$$c_{n0}^{(\epsilon)} = -\frac{\int_{-\infty}^{x_t} \psi_n(y) F_0(y) dy}{\lambda_n} \quad (3.44)$$

This expression is much simpler than the definition that involves derivatives respect to the parameter ϵ . We also mention that this result can be derived alternatively, directly from the Fokker-Planck equation as we show in the Appendix.

3.3 Conclusion

Here, by carrying out and pairing the dynamics of the firing rate $\nu(t)$ derived from two different approaches, we found novel analytic expressions for the coefficients underlying the spectral expansion of the population density $p(v, t)$. In the case of an uncoupled set of spiking neurons, we used the renewal theory in combination with the spectral expansion approach by pairing the relaxation dynamics of $\nu(t)$ – part of our ‘Rosetta stone’ – eventually obtaining sums of series in closed form. More specifically, we uncovered a new expression of the current-to-rate gain function $\Phi(\mu, \sigma)$ in Eq. (3.8) as series of the adjoint eigenfunctions evaluated at the reset potential $\psi_n(H)$. We also found a tight relationship between the moments of the ISI distribution and a suited combination of the $\psi_n(H)$ and the eigenvalues λ_n of the Fokker-Planck operator. We remark that all these findings are model-independent highlighting the descriptive power of the spectral expansion and further extending recent results reported in [PGS20].

From the same side of our Rosetta stone, we found an alternative way to compute both $\psi_n(H)$ and λ_n . Indeed, relying on the residue theorem, Eqs. (3.12) and (3.14) show how to obtain from the Laplace transform $\rho(s)$ of the ISI density both these coefficients. Notably, these equations provide a great advantage in practical terms to estimate numerically the eigenvalues λ_n even when their analytic expressions are not available. This is due to the fact that usually eigenvalues results from the numerical search of the roots of the spectral equation (3.16) [MD02; PGS20], or of the zeros of numerically derived functions [Ost11; Aug+17]. Evaluating residues instead requires computation of a limit or of a line integral around the border of a domain centered around some rough guess for λ_n . The expected computational advantages resulting from this residue-based approach can pave the way to effective implementations of the spectral expansion formalism in the numerical integration of the network dynamics of spiking neurons.

For the specific case of LIF neurons, we also derived additional analytic expressions for the coupling coefficients c_{n0} involved in the evaluation of both the out-of-equilibrium dynamics and the critical points of coupled networks via the firing rate equation (3.28). Here we resorted to the linear response to a small perturbation of the input as the other side of our Rosetta stone. Pairing the perturbative response carried out from the spectral expansion approach and directly from the Fokker-Planck equation, we finally obtained Eqs. (3.40) and (3.41). These expressions for c_{n0} result to involve only the eigenfunctions at the reset potential $\psi_n(H)$ and the eigenvalues λ_n . These coefficients in turn appear to be tightly linked in Eq. (3.10) to the ISI density $\rho(t)$ of isolated cells. In other words the coupling coefficients are the expression of a single-neuron feature valid under stationary condition, rather than being a direct function of the synaptic efficacy J . Although this may appear as a contradiction, we remark that in Eq. (3.43) these single-neuron features in $c_{n0}^{(\epsilon)}$ mainly play a modulatory role of the synaptic coupling KJ , which is fully taken into account in the mean-field expressions for the current moments $\mu(\nu)$ and $\sigma^2(\nu)$.

In the framework of the spectral expansion of $p(v, t)$, approximated expressions for $c_{n0}^{(\mu)}$ has been previously derived in [KMS96], finding

$$c_{n0}(\mu) \simeq \frac{\nu_0}{\lambda_n + 1} C(\mu)$$

for networks of LIF neurons working in drift-dominated regime ($\mu\tau > \theta$) and with small synaptic noise ($x_t \gg 1$). This is perfectly compatible with what we derived here and reported in Eq. (3.40), provided that $C(\mu) = (\psi'_n(x_t) - \psi'_n(x_r)) / (\sigma_0 \lambda_n)$. Note that our result has a more general applicability being valid also under subthreshold noise-dominated regime ($\mu\tau < \theta$). Another expression for $c_{n0}^{(\mu)}$ has been recently presented also

in [PGS20]. In this case the spectral expansion approach targeted the refractory density, leading to obtain for a network of renewal neurons with Poissonian ISIs and a refractory period τ_0 , the following expression

$$c_{n0}(\mu) = \frac{\partial_\mu \Phi}{\lambda_n + (1 - \tau_0 \lambda_n) \nu_0} \xrightarrow{\tau_0 \rightarrow 0} \frac{\partial_\mu \Phi}{\lambda_n + \nu_0}.$$

This equation appears to be qualitatively different from our Eq. (3.40). A possible explanation of such disagreement on one hand may reside in the fact that LIF neurons are not Poissonian processes. On the other hand, this might highlight a qualitative difference in the population dynamics described by the refractory density approach compared to the classical one focused on the evolution of the membrane potential density.

Note that, our derivation of the coupling terms c_{n0} for LIF neurons can in principle be applied to other IF neuron models. We expect in this case qualitatively similar results, confirming that the ISI density-based coefficients $c_{n0}^{(\epsilon)}$ eventually modulate the system response with strength proportional to KJ . We also draw the reader attention to the fact that here we did not report any expression for the coupling coefficients C_{nm} between nonstationary modes ($n, m \neq 0$). They are involved in the nonlinear response of the neuronal network playing a role when the time derivative \dot{v} of the firing rate is relatively large and the density $p(v, t)$ is significantly different from the stationary one (ϕ_0) [MD02]. Provided that such constraints are not violated, the network dynamics can be fully described by taking into account the only coefficients of the spectral expansion we studied, even when the firing rate is driven outside equilibrium [Aug+17].

Regarding the applicability to the out-of-equilibrium dynamics, we further point out that all the mentioned coefficients depend on the infinitesimal moments μ and σ of the synaptic current. This means that under the extended mean-field approximation that leads to Eq. (2.11), all the coefficients depend from time to time on the activity $\nu(t)$ of the network. Here μ and σ must be interpreted as parameters. Indeed, it is true that our Rosetta stone approach allowed us to carry out these spectral expansion coefficients from the quasi-equilibrium dynamics (linear response and relaxation in uncoupled sets), i.e., considering μ and σ as fixed. Nonetheless, for a given μ and σ they contribute to faithful represent a snapshot of the moving basis $\{|\phi_n\rangle\}_{n \in \mathbb{I}}$ onto which the density $p(v, t)$ is projected. The basis moves as the drift and diffusion terms in the Fokker-Planck equation (4.1) vary describing a sequence of stochastic processes (i.e., the membrane potentials of the neurons) locally homogeneous in time. We believe this is an important point to stress. Starting from the linearizable (quasi-equilibrium) dynamics of spiking neuron networks, the spectral expansion coefficients can be derived paving the way to describe the same system outside equilibrium. The analytical results that we developed in this chapter are essential for different aspects that we will face in the following chapters.

Chapter 4

Self-consistent stochastic dynamics for finite-size networks of spiking neurons

Thanks to my fortunate idea of introducing the relativity principle into physics, you (and others) now enormously overrate my scientific abilities, to the point where this makes me quite uncomfortable

Albert Einstein

Despite the huge number of neurons composing a brain network, ongoing activity of local cell assemblies is intrinsically stochastic. Fluctuations in their instantaneous rate of spike firing $\nu(t)$ scale with the size of the assembly and persist in isolated network, i.e., in absence of external sources of noise.

Although deterministic chaos due to the quenched disorder of the synaptic couplings underlies this seemingly stochastic dynamics, an effective theory for the network dynamics of a finite assembly of spiking neurons is lacking. Here, we fill this gap by extending the so-called population density approach including an activity- and size-dependent stochastic source in the Fokker-Planck equation for the membrane potential density. The finite-size noise embedded in this stochastic partial derivative equation is analytically characterized leading to a self-consistent and non-perturbative description of $\nu(t)$ valid for a wide class of spiking neuron networks. Power spectra of $\nu(t)$ are found in excellent agreement with those from detailed simulations both in the linear regime and across a synchronization phase transition, when a size-dependent smearing of the critical dynamics emerges.

Complex systems in statistical physics deal with a huge number N of interacting bodies like molecules leading to have wide applicability of effective mean-field theories. However, the finite size (e.g., volume) of the system can have a significant impact in the emergent collective dynamics [Kam07]. This can be due to the fact that finite systems have surfaces and volumes affecting the system behavior when for instance phase transitions are approached [Che+97; Hwa+04].

In some cases the presence of a finite number of elements can be incorporated as a stochastic field whose fluctuation size depend on N [Kaw94; Dea96]. In this way, the continuum formalism valid in the thermodynamic limit may result to be effective in the description of small-scale phenomena across phase transitions [Dur+17].

Biological and ecological systems can be even more challenging as they may incorporate peculiar boundary conditions and heterogeneity in space and time posing them continuously outside equilibrium [PL99; GCR14]. This is the case of biological networks

of neurons for which the probability current (see below) does not vanish even under stationary condition when it matches the frequency of spikes emitted per neuron, i.e. the firing rate ν [Kni72; AV93; BH99; FM99].

In this chapter I will show that finite-size fluctuations can be effectively taken into account in this challenging system via a self-consistent definition of the noise to be embedded into the mean-field population dynamics.

4.1 Population density and mean-field approximation

We have already seen that in the thermodynamic limit ($N \rightarrow \infty$), networks of single-compartment spiking neurons have collective dynamics statistically described by the probability density $p(v, t)$ of realizations with membrane potential v at time t [AV93; KMS96; BH99; FM99], obeying the Fokker-Planck equation (2.21) which, including the source term from the boundary condition (2.18) can be written as:

$$\tau_m \partial_t p(v, t) = -\partial_v S_p(v, t) + \delta(v - H) \nu(t). \quad (4.1)$$

In this continuity equation the density p changes according to the divergence of the probability current

$$S_p = (F + \mu \tau_m) p - \frac{1}{2} \partial_v (\sigma^2 \tau_m p)$$

and to the source of realizations reentering in the reset potential H after emitting a spike by crossing the emission threshold θ . This flux of neurons is the firing rate $\nu(t) = S_p(\theta, t)$.

In ‘current-based’ LIF neurons, both moments are independent from V . Such diffusion approximation of the current holds in the limit of large number K of presynaptic contacts and small average synaptic efficacy J [Ric76; Tuc05]. This is the case of cortical networks where $K \sim 10^4$ and $J \ll \theta$ [DAA02; Mar+15]. No assumptions are made about the statistics of single-neuron spike trains, neither on their renewal nature nor on the stationarity of the moments μ and σ^2 . This because synaptic currents result from a superposition of a large number K of uniformly sparse point processes (i.e., the spike trains of presynaptic neurons) which eventually converge to a inhomogeneous Poisson process [Gri63; Tuc89]. In the diffusion limit this point process is approximated by the above Gaussian noise allowing in turn to address the general case of network activities far from equilibrium.

In this framework also the mean-field approximation holds such that all neurons of a homogeneous network can be seen as independent realizations of the same stochastic process (same F , μ and σ) [AB97]. Synaptic interactions are incorporated in the ν -dependent moments of the current, which in current-based models like LIF neurons are given by equations (2.12).

Why are finite-size fluctuations important? Having a finite number N of neurons emitting spike trains $S_i(t) = \sum_k \delta(t - t_{i,k})$, leads to a fluctuating rate $\nu_N(t) = \sum_{i=1}^N S_i(t)/N = \mathcal{N}(t)$ of action potentials fired per unit time and per neuron. According to the aforementioned central limit, $\mathcal{N}(t)$ is an inhomogeneous Poisson process with mean $N \nu(t)$, such that $\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \nu_N(t) = \nu(t)$. Infinitesimal mean and variance of ν_N are ν and ν/N , respectively, and for large enough N (~ 100) like those observed in cortical minicolumns [Mou97], holds the Gaussian approximation

$$\nu_N(t) = \nu(t) + \sqrt{\frac{\nu(t)}{N}} \Gamma(t) \equiv \nu(t) + \eta(t). \quad (4.2)$$

Here, the finite-size noise $\eta(t)$ results from a modulation of a white noise $\Gamma(t)$. The correlation structure of η will be self-consistently derived in the following. Taking into account the fluctuating ν_N into Eq. (2.11), the moments of the input current (i.e., the mean-field) are no longer deterministic [BH99]. Fluctuations of the mean μ have relative size

$$\text{Var}[\mu(\nu_N)]^{1/2}/\text{E}[\mu(\nu_N)] = 1/\sqrt{N\nu}$$

of about 10% in cortical networks of interest where $\nu \sim 1$ Hz [Wat+16]. Remarkably, such variability is of the same order of the changes in μ associated with the coding of sensorial stimuli [PI09] or other relevant information [Rig+13], which usually involves only a sparse set of tuned neurons with variations of few Hz in their firing rates. Thus, finite-size fluctuations may have a not negligible impact disturbing or nonlinearly amplifying the encoding dynamics of cortical networks.

How can finite-size fluctuations be incorporated? To understand the impact of such fluctuations, according to [BH99] we incorporate the stochastic moments $\mu_N \equiv \mu(\nu_N)$ and $\sigma_N \equiv \sigma(\nu_N)$ directly into 2.15. The resulting stochastic Fokker-Planck equation describes now an infinite set of independent neurons all driven by the same fluctuating mean-field. Differently from other stochastic Smoluchowski equations [Kaw94; Dea96] and their coarse-grained versions [Cha08; Cha15], stochasticity here appears as an additional probability current with drift and diffusion coefficients differently affected by $\eta(t)$. Not only, this additional source of noise must be incorporated as a fluctuating source of realizations in H [MD02]. This is due to the fact that the finite flux of neurons crossing the threshold θ reenters at the reset potential, eventually leading to

$$\tau_m \partial_t p = -\partial_v [(F(v) + \mu_N \tau_m) p] + \frac{1}{2} \partial_v^2 (\sigma_N^2 \tau_m p) + \delta(v - H) \nu_N(t). \quad (4.3)$$

We remark that this stochastic Fokker-Planck (SFP) equation is nonlinear as both μ_N and σ_N depend on the density p via the firing rate ν .

4.2 Self-consistent derivation of $\eta(t)$

To determine the statistical features of $\eta(t)$ we refer to the specific case of a set of N uncoupled neurons ($J = 0$) driven by a stationary external input ($\dot{\mu}_{\text{ext}} = \dot{\sigma}_{\text{ext}} = 0$). In this case neurons are renewal processes, and the probability density $\rho(t)$ of their inter-spike intervals (ISI) fully characterize the statistics of the spike trains they emit [CM77], see Chapter 2 and 3. Pooling together these spike trains gives $\nu_N(t)$ (see above) such that its power spectral density is [Lin06; Ger+14]

$$P_v^{(\text{RT})}(\omega) = |\hat{\nu}_N(\omega)|^2 = \frac{\nu_0}{N} \text{Re} \left[\frac{1 + \hat{\rho}(\omega)}{1 - \hat{\rho}(\omega)} \right]. \quad (4.4)$$

Here $\hat{\rho}(\omega) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \rho(t) e^{-i\omega t} dt$ and $\hat{\nu}_N(\omega)$ are the Fourier transform of $\rho(t)$ and $\nu_N(t)$, respectively, and $\nu_0 = 1/\int_0^{\infty} t \rho(t) dt$ is the mean firing rate, i.e., the inverse of the mean ISI.

This exact result must be also obtained from Eq. (4.3). To carry out the power spectral density $|\hat{\nu}_N(\omega)|^2$ in this case we resort to the spectral expansion approach introduced previously giving:

$$P_v^{(\text{SE})}(\omega) = \left| 1 + \vec{f} \cdot (i\omega \mathbf{I} - \mathbf{\Lambda})^{-1} \vec{\psi}_H \right|^2 |\hat{\eta}(\omega)|^2 \quad (4.5)$$

The derivation of which can be found in Appendix B. If the finite-size noise is assumed to be white, $|\hat{\eta}(\omega)|^2 = \nu_0/N$, it leads to an overestimate of the power spectral density at relatively low- ω at least under ‘suprathreshold’ regime, i.e., when neurons emit spikes even if $\sigma = 0$ [MD02].

Figure 4.1: Normalized power spectra of the finite-size noise η for N uncoupled LIF neurons with firing rate ν_0 . (a) $|\hat{\eta}(\omega)|^2 N/\nu_0$ as a function of the mean synaptic current μ . σ is chosen to keep the mean firing rate unchanged at $\nu_0 = 20$ Hz. (b) In noise-dominant regime ($\mu\tau < \theta = 20$ mV) finite-size noise is essentially white (bottom). In drift-dominant regime, power is low at low- ω as ISIs are more regular ($c_v < 1$). In both cases, a two-dimensional Markovian embedding (black) faithfully reproduces theoretical spectra (red) from Eq. (4.6).

In this framework, the crucial observation is that for any IF neuron model, the series in Eq. (4.5) can be summed as a function of $\hat{\rho}(\omega)$, thanks to the results in Chapter 3 we have in fact that:

$$\vec{f} \cdot (i\omega\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{\Lambda})^{-1} \vec{\psi}_H = \frac{\hat{\rho}(\omega)}{1 - \hat{\rho}(\omega)} - \frac{\nu_0}{i\omega}$$

Using it in Eq. (4.5) and requiring the equivalence

$$P_v^{(\text{SE})}(\omega) = P_v^{(\text{RT})}(\omega)$$

we obtain with Eq. (4.4) a self-consistent expression for the power spectrum of η :

$$|\hat{\eta}(\omega)|^2 = \frac{\nu_0}{N} \left[1 - \left| \frac{(i\omega + \nu_0)\hat{\rho}(\omega) - \nu_0}{\nu_0\hat{\rho}(\omega) + i\omega - \nu_0} \right|^2 \right]. \quad (4.6)$$

This equation is one of the main results of this thesis for multiple reasons. First of all it is model independent, meaning that the specific Integrate-and-Fire neuron only enters the equation through the ISI distribution ρ . Secondly this result is exact or in other words non-perturbative. Finally it shows how corrections to the mean-field limit are strongly related to single neuron details.

In the limit $\omega \rightarrow \infty$, $\hat{\rho}(\omega) \rightarrow 0$ and the finite-size noise is white-like with variance ν_0/N . For $\omega \rightarrow 0$, the l.h.s. of Eq. (3.10) reduces to $-\vec{f} \cdot \mathbf{\Lambda}^{-1} \vec{\psi}_H = (c_v^2 - 1)/2$, see Chapter

3, function of the coefficient of variation c_v of the ISIs, leading to

$$|\hat{\eta}(0)|^2 = \frac{\nu_0}{N} \frac{4c_v^2}{(1 + c_v^2)^2}. \quad (4.7)$$

These limits suggest a sigmoid-like power spectra of the finite-size noise which is confirmed in LIF neurons [Fig. 4.1(a)]. For this type of neuron models

$$\hat{\rho}(\omega) = \frac{\sqrt{e^{x_r^2 - x_t^2}} \mathcal{D}_{-i\omega}(-\sqrt{2}x_r)}{\mathcal{D}_{-i\omega}(-\sqrt{2}x_t)}$$

with $\mathcal{D}_\nu(z)$ the parabolic cylinder function, $x_t = (\theta - \mu\tau)/\sigma\sqrt{\tau}$ and $x_r = (H - \mu\tau)/\sigma\sqrt{\tau}$ [Sie51].

As the firing regimes moves from noise- to drift-dominated (i.e., from sub- to suprathreshold) regimes by increasing the mean current μ , the sigmoidal shape becomes increasingly more apparent. Indeed, ISIs are more and more regular leading to a decrease of their c_v , and hence to a lower power $|\hat{\eta}(0)|^2$.

4.3 Markovian embedding of $\eta(t)$

Having derived in Eq. (4.6) the correlation structure of the finite-size noise for a set of uncoupled neurons under stationary condition a question arises: can we generalize this result to networks of synaptically coupled neurons and far from equilibrium?

To answer this question we remark that the spectra from Eq. (4.6) shown in Fig. 4.1 are flat (white noise-like) with a power reduction at low- ω possibly resulting by subtracting a Lorentzian-shaped function. Following [VL19], such kind of spectra are very well approximated by two-dimensional Ornstein-Uhlenbeck processes $\vec{u}(t)$ driven by and interfering with the same white noise $\Gamma(t)$:

$$\begin{aligned} d\vec{u} &= \mathbf{A} \vec{u} dt + \mathbf{B} \Gamma dt^{1/2} \\ \eta &= \vec{1} \cdot \vec{u} + \sqrt{\frac{\nu_0}{N}} \Gamma \end{aligned} \quad (4.8)$$

In Fig. 4.1(b) we show that this Markovian embedding faithfully reproduces the correlation structure of $\eta(t)$ in the simple case of \mathbf{B} with only one non-zero element, $B_{11} = \sqrt{\nu_0/N}$, and of a three-parameter \mathbf{A} being $A_{11} = A_{22}$. Instead of fitting $\{A_{11}, A_{12}, A_{21}\}$, we carry them out analytically as in [VL19] by matching the power of η from Eq. (4.8) with the exact one in Eq. (4.6) at the frequencies: $\omega = \{0, \pi, 2\pi\}\nu_0$. The parameters change according to μ and σ leading to a state-dependent $\mathbf{A}(\mu, \sigma)$.

This dynamical description of $\eta(t)$ in principle allows to overcome the renewal hypothesis, as the memory embedded in the network activity is reintroduced via the dependence on $\nu(t)$ of the current moments in Eq. (2.11). We then conjecture that taken together Eqs. (4.2, 4.3) and (4.8) provide a complete statistical description of the dynamics of finite-size networks of spiking neurons giving the positive answer to the above question.

Effectiveness of the stochastic network dynamics To test this conjecture, we use as a workbench a network of excitatory LIF neurons with a distribution of transmission delays of the emitted spikes. In the thermodynamic limit $N \rightarrow \infty$, the chosen network displays a supercritical Hopf bifurcation as the synaptic coupling KJ is increase. This happens

Figure 4.2: Bifurcation analysis of the network of LIF excitatory neurons ($N \rightarrow \infty$) studied in Figs. 4.3 and 4.4 at varying synaptic efficacies J . (a) Real and imaginary parts of the poles $sd_{\pm 1}$ and st_1 of $\nu(s)$ solving Eq. (4.10). Weakly coupled networks (small KJ , blue range) have a stable focus in ν_0 . Beyond $KJ \simeq 11$ mV (red) limit cycles arise via a codimension-1 supercritical Hopf bifurcation. (b) Numerical integration of the Fokker-Planck equation with $p(v, 0) = \delta(v - H)$ for $KJ = \{5, 10, 12\}$ mV pointed out in (a) (top arrows). The fixed point at $\nu_0 = 20$ Hz is kept constant by setting $\mu \tau = 21$ mV and $\sigma \tau^{1/2} = 2.665$ mV, and changing μ_{ext} and σ_{ext} according to J . Other parameters: $K = 10^3$, $\tau = 20$ ms, $\theta = 20$ mV, $\delta_{\text{min}} = 2$ ms and $\tau_{\delta} = 1$ ms.

through the destabilization of an equilibrium point with firing rate $\nu_0 = 20$ Hz eventually giving rise to a limit cycle.

More in details, in the network the spikes are exchanged with the distribution of axonal delays δ defined as $g(\delta) = e^{-(\delta - \delta_{\text{min}})/\tau_{\delta}}/\tau_{\delta}$ vanishing for any $\delta < \delta_{\text{min}}$, and with mean delay $\langle \delta \rangle = \tau_{\delta} + \delta_{\text{min}}$, see also Appendix B. Delayed couplings in an excitatory network can give rise to limit cycles, making it an ideal workbench to test our theoretical framework. We then focus on a codimension-1 Hopf bifurcation by changing the synaptic efficacy $J > 0$ and keeping fixed the firing rate $\nu_0 = \Phi(\mu, \sigma)$. That is done by imposing constant moments $\mu(\nu_0)\tau = 21$ mV and $\sigma(\nu_0)\sqrt{\tau} = 2.665$ mV. According to Eq. (2.11), it requires then to vary both μ_{ext} and σ_{ext} as a function J .

Following [MD02], the stability of the equilibrium point is evaluated by linearizing Eq. (B.1) in the limit $N \rightarrow \infty$ ($\eta \rightarrow 0$). To this purpose we set $\nu(t) \simeq \nu_0 + \nu_1(t)$ with $\nu_1(t) = O(|\vec{a}|)$ and neglect higher-order terms $O(|\vec{a}|^2)$. The firing rate equation then reduces to

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\vec{a}} &= \mathbf{\Lambda} \vec{a} + \vec{c} \dot{\nu}_1 \\ \nu_1 &= \Phi' \tilde{\nu}_1 + \vec{f} \cdot \vec{a} \end{aligned} \quad (4.9)$$

where all coefficients and eigenvalues are now computed in $\nu = \nu_0$, $\Phi' = \partial_{\nu} \Phi|_{\nu=\nu_0}$ and $\tau_{\delta} \dot{\nu}_1 = \nu(t - \delta_{\text{min}}) - \tilde{\nu}(t) = \nu_1(t - \delta_{\text{min}}) - \tilde{\nu}_1(t)$ to take into account the distribution of

delays δ . As done above for Eq. (3.4), the Laplace transform of the firing-rate perturbation $\hat{v}_1(s)$ can be worked out given that $\hat{v}_1(s) = \hat{v}_1(s) e^{-s\delta_{\min}} / (1 + s\tau_\delta) = \hat{v}_1(s) \hat{g}(s)$. The poles of $\hat{v}_1(s)$ determine the stability of the equilibrium point. Once $\hat{v}_1(s)$ is made explicit, the poles are the zeros of its denominator:

$$1 - \hat{g}(s) \left[\Phi' + s\vec{f}(s\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{\Lambda})^{-1}\vec{c} \right] = 0. \quad (4.10)$$

As shown in [MD02], these zeros are well approximated by taking into account only the two leading eigenmodes (i.e., with smallest $-\text{Re}(\lambda_n)$, here $n = -1, 1$), such that

$$s\vec{f}(s\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{\Lambda})^{-1}\vec{c} \simeq \frac{s}{\tau} \left(\frac{c_{+10}}{s - \lambda_{+1}} + \frac{c_{-10}}{s - \lambda_{-1}} \right). \quad (4.11)$$

With this in Eq. (4.10) we have a third degree equation for s with the solutions $s^* = \{\text{sd}_{\pm 1}, \text{st}_1\}$ shown in Fig. 4.2(a). As we set $\mu\tau > \theta$, the equilibrium point v_0 is in a suprathreshold regime and the first two eigenvalues are $\lambda_{\pm 1} \simeq -2(\pi\sigma/\theta)^2 \pm 2\pi v_0$ [AV93; KMS96; MD02]. With this guess we compute the exact $\lambda_{\pm 1}$ by finding the numerical solution of the characteristic equation $\psi_\lambda(\theta) = \psi_\lambda(H)$ [KMS96; MD02]. Known the eigenvalues, the coefficients c_{n0} for the LIF neuron have an analytic expression in terms of parabolic cylinder functions, see Chapter 3. The poles s^* are eventually computed by making use of these $\lambda_{\pm 1}$ and $c_{\pm 10}$.

In Fig. 4.2(a), for small enough synaptic couplings KJ , all poles have negative real parts. The equilibrium point is then a stable focus ($\text{sd}_{\pm 1}$ are complex conjugates) as shown in the two example networks with $KJ = 5$ and 10 mV [Fig. 4.2(b)-top]. By further increasing KJ , the focus destabilizes at about 11 mV via a supercritical Hopf bifurcation giving rise to a stable limit cycle, as shown in Fig. 4.2(b)-bottom ($KJ = 12$ mV).

In weakly coupled networks with relatively small KJ , finite-size noise induces stochastic perturbations of $v_N(t)$ around a stable focus amenable to linear response theory. This is the case of our example network with $KJ = 5$ mV for which the power spectrum of v_N can be carried out as a linear transformation of the finite-size noise [MD02; MD04]:

$$P_v(\omega) = |\hat{v}_N(\omega)|^2 = |\hat{H}_v(\omega)|^2 |\hat{\eta}(\omega)|^2. \quad (4.12)$$

Here $\hat{H}_v(\omega)$ is the Fourier transfer function characterizing the linear response to sinusoidal modulations of the input firing. $\hat{H}_v(\omega)$ is analytically known for LIF neurons [BH99; LS01]. In Fig. 4.3(a)-top we show a remarkable agreement between such Eq. (4.12) and the power spectral densities $P_v(\omega)$ estimated from both the simulations of spiking neuron networks (SNN, [Far+20]) and the numerical integration of the SFP Eq. (4.3). To compute the SFP integration we extended a standard deterministic approach [Aug+17] by incorporating the Markovian embedding (4.8) of $\eta(t)$. SFP integration for different network sizes N confirms in Fig. 4.3(a)-bottom what expected from the linear theory, that is, the spectrum shape does not change with N once normalized by the variance v_0/N . The equivalence in these case between SNN simulation and SFP integration is also apparent in the direct comparison of $v_N(t)$ time series. Indeed, in Fig. 4.3(b) no differences emerge and both time series display a variance scaling as $1/N$, as expected.

By further increasing the synaptic coupling KJ , the mentioned supercritical Hopf bifurcation is approached (Fig. 4.2 in Appendix) and finite-size networks have $P_v(\omega)$ no longer fully described by linear theory [i.e., Eq. (4.12)]. The mismatch is apparent in Fig. 4.4(a)-top as an unpredicted second-harmonic peak at $\omega/2\pi \simeq 2v_0$ arises in SNN simulations. On the contrary, the SFP integration display an excellent match. Despite such footprint of nonlinear dynamics, SNN and SFP keep displaying a remarkable overlap not only in P_v but also in the stochastic dynamics of $v_N(t)$ shown in Fig. 4.4(b) where

Figure 4.3: Power spectra $P_v(\omega)$ (a) and firing rates $v_N(t)$ (b) of weakly coupled networks ($KJ = 5$ mV) with varying size N . (a) Top, $P_v(\omega)$ from the numerical integration of the stochastic Fokker-Planck equation (SFP, pink), the equivalent spiking neuron network (SNN) simulation (black) and linear perturbation theory (dashed blue from Eq. (4.12)) ($N = 10^4$). Dashed black, white noise with variance v_0/N . Bottom, normalized spectra of v from SFP of networks with different N ($= 10^3, 10^4, 10^5$). (b) $v(t)$ from SNN simulations (black) and SFP varying N ($= 10^3, 10^4, 10^5$) (left). Right, related histograms of $v(t)$. Other parameters as in Fig. 4.2.

coherent oscillations become more and more apparent as N decreases. The ongoing finite-size fluctuations of v in this case continuously stimulate the oscillating relaxation of the stable focus which is relatively slow due to the nearby critical point [see Fig. 4.2(b)-middle]. The N -dependent coherence of the fluctuation-driven oscillation is even more apparent in the increase of power of the second-harmonic peak in smaller networks 4.4(a)-bottom].

The same remarkable match between SFP and SNN is shown in Fig. 4.4(c)-top beyond the Hopf bifurcation ($KJ = 12$ mV) when a stable limit cycle is expected at $N \rightarrow \infty$. Global oscillations in this case are strongly nonlinear, giving rise to several high-order harmonic peaks. In this case finite-size noise contribute to dephase the oscillations limiting their coherence in time [Fig. 4.4(d)]. According to this, the resonant peaks in $P_v(\omega)$ have power lowering with decreasing N [Fig. 4.4(c)-bottom].

4.4 Conclusions

The agreement found between SFP and SNN in a synchronization phase transition is an encouraging evidence that the stochastic population dynamics we derived in Eqs. (4.2, 4.3)

and (4.8) has the potential to faithfully describe out-of-equilibrium networks composed of a finite number N of spiking neurons. Indeed, it is important to stress that the theoretical framework we introduce is not perturbative and takes into account the point-like (spike-

Figure 4.4: Power spectra $P_v(\omega)$ (a,c) and firing rates $v_N(t)$ (b,d) of strongly coupled (nonlinear) networks with varying size N . (a, b) $KJ = 10$ mV, mean-field dynamics predicts a stable focus at $v_0 = 20$ Hz. (c, d) $KJ = 12$ mV, networks beyond a supercritical Hopf bifurcation with a stable limit cycle. See Figs. 4.2 and 4.3 for additional details.

based) nature of the cell-to-cell interactions. Furthermore, the correlation structure of $\eta(t)$ here results from the spiking statistics of isolated neurons, implying that finite-size noise is not J -dependent.

As the self-consistent derivation of $\hat{\eta}(\omega)$ in Eq. (4.6) is exact, it is valid for any N and hence also for extremely small networks. However, in addition to this ‘non-perturbative’ results, we assume that $\eta(t)$ is generated by the embedding in Eq. (4.8). In doing so, we consider in Eq. (4.2) that $v_N(t)$ is a Gaussian process. This approximation assumes that on the characteristic time scale τ of the population dynamics, the number of spikes emitted by the network has to be large ($N \gg 1/\nu\tau$). When this condition is violated, the Gaussian $v_N(t)$ has a not negligible likelihood to be ‘unrealistically’ negative. This poses a lower bound to the minimum size of the networks we can describe. A possible workaround to this limitation is to take into account the exact expression $\eta(t) = v_N(t) - \nu(t) = \mathcal{N}(t) - \nu(t)$, where $\mathcal{N}(t)$ is a Poisson process with mean $N\nu(t)$. In this case, Eq. (4.8) should be replaced with an equivalent embedding valid for stochastic point processes.

Finite-size fluctuations can elicit nonlinear phenomena like coherent oscillations even when – in the $N \rightarrow \infty$ limit – equilibrium points are expected to be stable. The size of the network is then a structural feature capable to amplify a rhythmic activity which would be otherwise damped. This results holds without imposing a bifurcation to the system. The fingerprint left by this phenomenon is the onset of a second-harmonic peak in the power spectrum of the neuronal activity. Interestingly, in brain networks of behaving animals these kind of resonant peaks have been observed both during sensory processing [GT08] and in working memory tasks [Pes+02]. Rhythmic activity and its coherence across networks has been hypothesized to make information transmission effective [Fri15] and to establish distributed and dynamic patterns underlying several cognitive functions [EFS01]. In this framework, oscillations induced by finite-size fluctuations may have a role in establishing a cognitive-relevant state of the network without necessarily being critical. Alternative approaches dealing with finite-size networks of spiking neurons are those relying on the refractory density method (RDM) [SC19]. Neurons in this case are quasi-stationary renewal processes and the population dynamics is fully described by the probability density of a single-cell to be into a refractory state [Ger95; Ger00]. In the RDM, the integro-differential equation governing the population activity at the mesoscopic scale can incorporate fluctuations to describe a finite number of neurons [SDG17a; SLS21]. However, the renewal hypothesis underlying RDM may in principle limit its applicability by making our theoretical framework preferable in dealing with out-of-equilibrium conditions. In conclusion, we remark that the theoretical framework we developed applies to a wide class of spiking neuron models, and the same approach can be extended to other systems with a finite size. Indeed, the inclusion of fluctuations in population density theories has the potential to further advance our understanding of noise-driven out-of-equilibrium dynamics [Das+12; Dur+17]. This is the case of metastable dynamics in presence of rotational components due to broken detailed balance observed both in neuronal networks and in other biological systems [Lyn+21; Bri+22].

Chapter 5

Low dimensional dynamics of spiking neural networks

When you change the way you look at things, the things you look at change

Max Planck

In the previous chapter we discussed the importance of finite size effects in the mean-field dynamics and how this can be included self consistently. Finite-size fluctuations however are clearly only a part of the picture and it is essential to understand the behaviour of neural population in the limit of infinite size $N \rightarrow \infty$. For this reason from this chapter through the end of the thesis we will implicitly talk about infinite populations. The collective dynamics of neuronal networks can be complex even when simplified point process like integrate-and-fire (IF) neurons are considered for modeling, due to the high-dimensionality of the system and the quenched randomness in the synaptic couplings. Despite several decades of efforts, a general expression for the dynamics of the population firing rate $\nu(t)$ independent from neuronal models and dynamical regimes expressed is still lacking. Here, we move in this direction by deriving a low-dimensional mean-field dynamics of $\nu(t)$ (i.e., the network activity) valid for a wide class of IF neurons and outside equilibrium. To this purpose we focused on the evolution of the population density of neuron membrane potentials which in these networks is fully captured, as discussed in Chapter 2, by a Fokker-Plank (FP) equation. Relying on the first modes in the state-dependent spectral expansion of the FP operator we introduced in the previous chapters, we derive the 2nd-order ODE for the mean firing rate. In this framework the $\nu(t)$ dynamics naturally incorporates the strength of the synaptic couplings and synaptic delays. The agreement between theory and simulations is shown both under noise- and drift-dominant regimes in networks of LIF neurons.

5.1 Introduction

The brain is possibly the most complex system known to man. The complexity arises mainly from three factors: the heterogeneity of the biological parameters that characterize every single neuron, the huge number of them and the fact that neurons are non linear dynamical systems. Understanding how ensembles of neurons organize and operate in concert to produce the emergent cognitive behavior observed in the animal kingdom, is a key quest of modern neuroscience.

Since the seminal work of Wilson and Cowan [[WC72](#)], Amari [[Ama72](#)], and many

others, it was clear that in order to understand such complexity some kind of coarse-graining, or dimensional reduction, was necessary. Instead of describing the whole system composed of many neurons and their connections, using mean-field theory, they obtained dynamical systems that model entire neural population. One of the main issue was that such models were partially phenomenological making obscure the link between the different spatial scales.

In recent times a great amount of efforts in the theoretical neuroscience community has been made to derive such population model, at a mesoscopic scale, starting from first principle. In particular major steps forward were made considering simplified version of single neuron model called Integrate-and-Fire (IF). Despite their simplicity IF neurons can reproduce all the repertoire of dynamics [GMD07] observed in experiment and can even be used for a quantitative match with in-vivo and in-vitro data [Bad+08]. Different approach were used to derive low dimensional models of neural population however in order to close the mean field equation different assumption were made. As a consequence the models derived have a limited range of applicability for example, in [MPR15] only deterministic neurons are considered, while in [SOA13] the non-linear phenomena as limit cycle are not captured. In this chapter we present a theoretical framework based on [MD02] and on the Fokker-Planck equation for the population membrane potentials distribution. It can be used to show that a separation of time scales is indeed a general feature of population density models. Then we proceed in deriving a low dimensional ODE for the mean firing rate of the population that is valid in any regime even in out of equilibrium context. Our approach can be applied to any Integrate-and-Fire neuron model and shows quantitative match with detailed simulations of spiking neural network. Moreover since the derivation is from first principles, the relation between mesoscopic quantities and single neuron details can be derived. For example we found previously unreported behavior of population decay time and angular frequency.

5.1.1 The formalism

Equation (2.21) is computationally demanding to solve numerically, especially if one consider multiple coupled populations. Even if such solution is available, extract general conclusions is a challenging task. However using the Emission Rate Formalism (ERE) developed in [MD02] the Fokker-Planck equation can be recast in a formally infinite many ODE's and from that some general properties, regarding for example the stability of solutions, can be found. We will use the same framework to prove that one can reduce greatly the dimensionality of the problem to just a couple of degrees of freedom.

The idea is to expand $p(v, t)$ along the basis the eigenfunctions $\{\phi_\lambda(v)\}$ of the operator $L[p]$:

$$p(v, t) = \sum_n^{\infty} a_n(t) \phi_{\lambda_n}(v) \quad (5.1)$$

the coefficients of the expansion are the projection of $|p\rangle$ on the basis of the adjoint operator L^\dagger , $\langle\psi_\lambda|$ i.e.:

$$a_n(t) = \langle\psi_{\lambda_n}|p\rangle$$

and truncate the expansion (5.1) to a given order. An aspect that is crucial in the success of the dimensional reduction, is that, in contrast to standard spectral expansion such as Hartree-Fok method, this is a moving basis since both the eigenfunctions and the spectrum $\{\lambda_n\}$ are state dependent trough the firing rate $v(t)$. This fact will have two consequences: first the spectral expansion can be used also in out-of-equilibrium cases and secondly that this basis will adapt to the instantaneous state of the system. It implies that the bulk of the

probability distribution $p(v, t)$ will be taken into account by the state-dependent stationary solution $\phi_0(v, \nu(t))$, suggesting the possibility that a small number of extra modes will be necessary to describe the remaining part. The ERE equation can be obtained using (5.1) in the Fokker-Planck combined with (2.20) and reads:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{a}_n &= \lambda_n a_n + c_{n0} \dot{\nu} + \sum_m c_{nm} a_m \dot{\nu} \\ \nu &= \Phi(\nu) + \frac{\sum_m a_m}{\tau_m} \end{aligned} \quad (5.2)$$

where Φ is the single neuron gain function, or stationary firing rate which we defined in Chapter 2, τ_m is the membrane time constant and the coupling integrals c_{nm} are defined as:

$$c_{nm} = \langle \partial_\nu \psi_n | \phi_m \rangle$$

To move on from here and characterize the spectrum $\{\lambda_n\}$ I will show specific results regarding the Leaky Integrate-and-Fire (LIF), typically considered as gold standard for both its accuracy in explaining experimental data and relative analytic tractability. This amount to chose the drift term as: $f(v) = -\frac{v}{\tau_m}$ however most of the basic structure of the spectrum that we will show, were obtained using intuition based on the simplified EIF model VIF [FM99]. Moreover computational study [Aug+17] shows that also for the EIF model $f(v) = \frac{-v+\Delta e^{v/\Delta}}{\tau_m}$, where the spectrum is both qualitatively and quantitatively very similar to the one showed here. This suggest that the spectrum in it's architecture is more related to the common boundary conditions than to the single neuron details, we will come back to this interesting aspect in Chapter 7.

5.2 The spectrum of the LIF

We have shown in Chapter 3 that, independently on the the IF model, the characteristic equation to solve to find the eigenvalues is given by (3.16). Its solution are reported in Figure 5.1A were we can distinguish two classes of eigenvalues, those that bifurcate to complex conjugate that we refer to as Drift-Dominated (DD) and those that are always real or Noise-Dominated (ND). We found that the bifurcation is located close to $\mu^* = \frac{\theta-H}{2}$. It can be shown analytically, see Appendix C, that above μ^* the λ^{ND} decays to $-\infty$ while for the DD eigenvalues we have

$$\lambda_n^{DD} \approx -2 \left(\frac{n\pi\sigma}{\theta} \right)^2 + i2n\pi \frac{\mu - \mu^*}{\theta}$$

below μ^* the gap between two successive eigenvalues will remain approximately close to 1. Those two result are important since they show that there is a clear hierarchy of eigenvalues which in turn implies a hierarchy of modes, the most dominant of which are those closest to have zero real part.

In Figure (5.1) B we show, in the two different regime, how this hierarchy is reflected on amplitude of the coefficient expansion in a strongly coupled case. The coefficients were obtained by numerically solving $p(t, v)$ and projecting it in the eigenbase. We found that

$$|a_n| \approx e^{Re(\lambda)}$$

in a strongly non-linear and open regime in fact in this case the network is both synaptically coupled and forced by an external current. This result is the same as what would be obtained from the uncoupled population case that can be solved analytically. The conclusion then

Figure 5.1: The separation of time scales in the spectral expansion. Top panel shows the Drift-Dominated Eigenvalues in red and the Noise-Dominated regime in blue. The spectral gap between two successive eigenvalues implies an exponential distance between successive eigenmodes a_n in both level of σ (Middle panel). The populations considered here were highly coupled, with time depend external current. In the bottom panel it is shown how the zeroth mode and the first three mode are capable to reconstruct the firing rate $\nu(t)$ into these two regimes.

is that due to both the spectral hierarchy and the state-dependent nature of the expansion, a truncation of (5.1) to the lowest modes is justified.

The specific behavior of the eigenvalues found, reported also for the VIF [MD02] and the EIF [Aug+17], is responsible for a separation of time scales in the dynamics of the system. To be more precise if we decide to keep only the first n modes in the expansion, we are actually neglecting all the dynamics that are faster than:

$$\tau_n \sim -\frac{1}{\text{Re}(\lambda_n)}$$

However since the real part of the eigenvalues shows clear gaps between successive modes a limited number of them is sufficient to obtain quantitative match with microscopic simulation.

That been said when truncating the expansion some care has to be taken since there are region of intersection between the two family of eigenvalues, and also the fact that if the dominant eigenmode is complex one has to consider also its conjugate.

We found that, except for fast transient, two eigenmodes are sufficient to reproduce both the transition to and the stationary states. Interestingly in [SZT20] the authors arrived at a similar conclusions i.e. that two degree of freedom are sufficient to describe the population dynamics, but using a completely different approach based on maximization of entropy and moment closure.

Moreover we found that (5.2) can be further simplified. The truncation of (5.1) clearly implies that the dynamics of a_n will depend only on it self and on the few other a_m considered. However using the orthonormality condition, $\langle \psi_n | \phi_m \rangle = \delta_{nm}$, it can be shown that the auto-coupling coefficients c_{nn} is typically dominant with respect to all the others: $c_{nn} \gg c_{nm}$. The effect of such autocoupling coefficients is to effectively renormalize the eigenvalues: $\Lambda_n = \lambda_n + c_{nn} \dot{v}$. To summarize, if we consider the first dominant ND (β) and DD (γ, δ) eigenvalues only, the ERE system is well approximated by:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{a}_\gamma &= \Lambda_\gamma(v, \dot{v})a_\gamma + c_{\gamma 0} \dot{v} + (c_{\gamma \delta} a_\delta + c_{\gamma \beta} a_\beta) \dot{v} \\ \dot{a}_\delta &= \Lambda_\delta(v, \dot{v})a_\delta + c_{\delta 0} \dot{v} + (c_{\delta \gamma} a_\gamma + c_{\delta \beta} a_\beta) \dot{v} \\ \dot{a}_\beta &= \Lambda_\beta(v, \dot{v})a_\beta + c_{\beta 0} \dot{v} + (c_{\beta \delta} a_\delta + c_{\beta \gamma} a_\gamma) \dot{v} \\ v &= \Phi(v) + \frac{a_\beta + a_\delta + a_\gamma}{\tau_m} \end{aligned} \quad (5.3)$$

The dynamical system (5.3) in its form is completely general and it's valid for any IF model and in any regime given that the distinction between noise dominated and drift dominated eigen modes is given and, most importantly, that the spectral gap is present. I will show now that starting from it one can derive using (5.1), a dynamical system that involves only mesoscopic variables, such as the mean membrane potential or the population firing rate.

5.3 Uncoupled Population

Since we have seen that even in a strongly coupled population far-from-equilibrium, the hierarchy of eigenvalues gives all the information about the dominant time scales, the uncoupled population case will be very useful to understand the effective dimensionality of the system. Note that when the neurons in the network are uncoupled the moments of the synaptic current (2.12) are independent on the population firing rate. Following

Figure 5.2: Population decay time **A** and angular frequency **B** of an uncoupled population as a function of the moments of the synaptic current μ and σ as defined in equation (5.5). The angular frequency can be null also for high drift $\mu \gg \theta$ while decay time can show non monotonic behaviour, as shown in the bottom panels, where the match with detailed simulation is reported.

[Mat16] we will consider only the first dominant eigenmode (first two if it's complex). Starting from (5.3) and remembering that in this case all the coupling constants are null, the dynamical system can be rewritten in a ODE for the firing rate only:

$$\tau_0^2 \ddot{v} + 2\tau_0 \dot{v} = (1 + \omega_0^2 \tau_0^2)(\Phi - v) \quad (5.4)$$

where Φ is the single-neuron gain function and the population decay time and angular frequency depend on the first two eigenvalues:

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_0 &= -\frac{2}{\lambda_1 + \lambda_2} \\ \omega_0^2 &= -\frac{(\lambda_1 - \lambda_2)^2}{4} \end{aligned} \quad (5.5)$$

The uncoupled population is then damped oscillator, but τ_0 and ω_0 depends on the synaptic current moments (μ, σ). The results on the spectrum of previous section are useful to infer information about measurable physical quantities. In particular the presence

Figure 5.3: Weakly coupled case. On the left panels the decay time and angular frequency vs the mean current μ at fixed stationary firing rate of $\nu_0 = 5$ Hz. The color code indicates the strength of the synaptic coupling KJ from inhibitory -5 (dark blue) to excitatory 5 (dark red). On the right panels $\mu\tau_m$ is kept constant at 16 mV. The result on non linear fit parameters of the firing rate from the Fokker-Planck and low dimensional integration is shown. The perturbative result of the theory prediction (black dotted) is in good agreement with direct estimation.

of the ND eigenvalues induce a non-monotonicity in σ on the decay time because the real part of dominant eigenvalue has a different behaviour as a function of σ for the two different families of eigenvalues. To the best of our knowledge this counter-intuitive fact that the population response become slower upon increasing the variance of synaptic current was never reported before. In fact one would expect that increasing the noise in the system would lead to a faster decoherence, hence a faster response to external stimuli.

5.3.1 Weakly coupled limit

The decay time τ and angular frequency ω of the neural population depend also on the type and strength of the synaptic coupling. The main limitation of phenomenological models as the Wilson-Cowan one [WC72], is the lack of such relations between mesoscopic parameters, that differently from here are usually assumed constant, and it is not clear how mesoscopic features depends on single neurons details. In this section we will prove that the population properties get "renormalized" by the recurrent coupling in a universal way that is related only to the mean-field approximation.

For simplicity let's assume the population to be homogeneous, i.e. all the synapses are of the same kind and of fixed strength J . Since for the moment we want to study the property of the network subjected to step-wise stimuli and far from non linear regime, we can drop the auto-coupling term in (5.3) but keep the coupling with stationary mode c_{n0} . The reason is that the between-modes coupling c_{nm} are multiplied by terms like $a_n(t)v(t)$ which are of order $o(a^2)$ and thus are responsible for non-linear effects that we will consider in the following sections.

After some algebra the low dimensional model for the firing rate is derived:

$$\alpha_2(v)\ddot{v} + \alpha_1(v)\dot{v} = \Phi(v) - v \quad (5.6)$$

Now the coefficients of the ODE depend on the firing rate through the coupling coefficients:

$$\alpha_1 = -\frac{\lambda_1 + \lambda_2}{\lambda_1 \lambda_2} \left(1 - \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial v} - \frac{\frac{c_{10}}{\lambda_1} + \frac{c_{20}}{\lambda_2}}{\tau_m \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_1} + \frac{1}{\lambda_2} \right)} \right)$$

$$\alpha_2 = \frac{1}{\lambda_1 \lambda_2} \left(1 - \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial v} - \frac{c_{10} + c_{20}}{\tau} \right)$$

Applying standard linearization we can obtain expression for "effective" τ and ω valid close to the fixed point:

$$\tau(v) = \frac{2\alpha_2(v)}{\alpha_1(v)}$$

$$\sim \tau_0(1 + KJ\tau_m A(\mu, \sigma) + o(J^2))$$

$$\omega^2(v) = \frac{1 - \partial_v \Phi}{\alpha_2(v)} - \frac{1}{\tau^2(v)} \quad (5.7)$$

$$\sim \omega_0^2 + KJ\tau_m \left(\frac{2A(\mu, \sigma) + B(\mu, \sigma)}{\tau_0^2} + B(\mu, \sigma)\omega_0^2 \right)$$

where $A(\mu, \sigma), B(\mu, \sigma)$ are functions of the mean and standard deviation of the synaptic current (see Appendix) whose specific form depends on the type of I.F. neuron used, nonetheless the general form (5.7) is universal and depends only on the mean-field prescription. For the LIF population with excitatory (inhibitory) coupling, Fig. 5.3, we found that the decay time is greater (lesser) than the uncoupled case while the opposite holds for the angular frequency however this picture is state-dependent as I will show below. Similar relations involving other physical quantities can be obtained using the framework here presented and can be used to predict experimental results or to better understand population dynamics data.

Another interesting phenomenon is reported in Fig. 5.4. We found that the state-dependent correction, further modulated by KJ , to the uncoupled τ_v is monotonic in μ and σ , the same does not hold for ω_v . Surprisingly the correction $\Delta\omega(\mu, \sigma)$ shows non-monotonic behaviour and even change of sign.

This is particularly relevant since it means that values of μ and σ exist for which the coupling of the network does not affect ω_v independently of the level of KJ (and the sign). Direct integration of Fokker-Plank equation supports this peculiar finding.

5.4 Strongly coupled population

As we showed at the beginning the truncation of the expansion can be carried out even in out-of-equilibrium regime independently of the strength or type (excitatory or inhibitory) of the recurrent coupling.

Previous attempts [SOA13] while very successful in linear or quasi-linear regimes, failed in reproducing typical non-linear phenomena such as limit cycles in single population (see also [Aug+17] for detailed analysis), despite being observed in direct integration of

Figure 5.4: State dependent correction to population angular frequency. Figure (A) shows the non monotonic behaviour of the correction to the uncoupled ω that is further modulate by the strength of synaptic coupling KJ (see equation 5.7). Here we have a fix $\sigma\sqrt{\tau} = 2.66$ [mV]. On figure B we report the result from the integration of the Fokker-Planck as a function of KJ for three different values of $\mu\tau$: 20.78 (squares), 21.56 (triangle) and 23.33 (hexagon) [mV]

the Fokker-Planck equation and detailed spiking simulations. The simplest case is to consider only one eigenmode in the expansion. This is strictly correct only when the dominant eigenvalue is real. Then we can use the single ERE equation to obtain the following dynamical system for the firing rate:

$$\dot{v} = \frac{\Phi(v) - v}{\tau(v)} \quad (5.8)$$

where the state-dependent coefficient, τ , is:

$$\tau(v) = -\frac{1 - \partial_v \Phi - \frac{c_{10}(v)}{\tau_m} - c_{11}(v)(v - \Phi(v))}{\lambda(v)}$$

This one dimensional system is in good agreement with microscopic simulations whenever we are in noise-dominated regime. It consists in an improved version of Wilson-Cowan rate model. However in this case, not only τ is state-dependent, but we have a direct relation with microscopic parameters.

In drift-dominated regime the dominant eigenmode is complex which implies at least a two-dimensional system. Also in this case we found good agreement with a relative error of order 5% between theory and simulation as it is shown in Fig. 5.5.

Following the same step of above while keeping all the c coefficients, a non linear equation for the firing rate can be obtained. To get closer to real networks we will also consider the possibility of having an exponential distribution of synaptic delay time, governed by the time constant τ_D : $g(t) \sim e^{-t/\tau_D}$ where τ_D is mean delay time.

From the microscopic point of view we are saying that neurons in the network will receive spikes with a random delay extracted from the distribution $g(t)$. As for the mean-field theory description, this effect can be included in the dynamical system as an additional degree of freedom for a low pass filtered version of the firing rate \tilde{v} [Mat+19]. After some algebra the ODE can be written as:

Figure 5.5: Effect of excitatory coupling. Figure A shows the effect of excitatory coupling in neural population at a drift dominated regime ($\nu_\infty = 40$ Hz, $\mu_\infty = 27.4$ mV). The coupling strength is equal to $KJ = 5, 8, 10$, from top to bottom. The match between microscopic simulation and eq. (5.9) is shown. The same variation of coupling was adopted in B but the population is in noise-dominated regime ($\nu_\infty = 5$ Hz, $\mu_\infty = 8$ mV). In this case we used the one dimensional model eq. (5.8.)

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_2(\nu, \tilde{\nu})\dot{\tilde{\nu}} + \alpha_1(\nu, \tilde{\nu})\dot{\nu} &= \Phi(\tilde{\nu}) - \nu + F(\nu, \tilde{\nu}) \\ \dot{\tilde{\nu}} &= \frac{\nu - \tilde{\nu}}{\tau_D} \end{aligned} \quad (5.9)$$

The analytical expression for the non linear coefficients and extra force, α_1 , α_2 and F . can be found in Appendix.

It is worth noting that, the bifurcation diagrams of Fig (5.6) where derived using the weakly coupled variant of the previous section, however the auto-coupling terms proved to be crucial to reach a quantitative match with detailed simulation.

We found that, for excitatory population, increasing sufficiently the recurrent coupling J will lead to an Hopf bifurcation and the insurgence of limit cycles. This shows, contrary to what is typically found in literature, that coherent oscillations can develop at the single population level without including another inhibitory population [SOA13] ore a third degree of freedom, such as adaptation currents [Aug+17]).

For the inhibitory coupling no limit cycles were found, however when including constant synaptic delay coherent oscillation arise as shown in [BH99]. When the coupling reaches the critical values that correspond to $\partial_\nu \Phi > 1$ the fixed point loses is stability. The same result was found and discussed in [MD02; MD04].

5.5 Non-linear dynamics

In [MPR15] it was shown how it is possible to derive analytically, trough a Lorentzian Ansatz, a bidimensional dynamical system for the firing rate and mean membrane potential, in the case of a fully deterministic population of QIF neurons, that is $f(v) = -v^2$ in equation 2.2. The authors also showed how such dimensional reduction holds even in the presence of a time-dependent external inputs. Tuning the strength of the recurrent coupling and the frequency of the external sinusoidal current, chaotic motion was observed. On the

Figure 5.6: Bifurcation diagram for excitatory population. The color code indicate the nature of the dominant eigenvalue of the stability matrix. The red and violet indicates stable nodes, while in gray the limit cycles. The brown region of top panel correspond to $\partial_v \Phi > 1$ where the fixed point loses its stability (Saddle node bifurcation). Bottom panel is made keeping constant coupling $KJ = 14$ mV and varying the moments of the external current

contrary in [SOA13] is argued that a smooth stimulation can in principle elicit all the time scale of the system invalidating the hypothesis of separation of time scales. However, in Fig 5.7 we show how the low dimensional model responds to different kind of external stimuli. The quantitative and qualitative match obtained with both detailed simulation of spiking neural network and direct integration of the Fokker-Planck equation is a further proof of the fact that, the relevant time scales remain the same even in presence of periodic smooth stimulation contradicting the argument put forward in [SOA13]. We believe that the success of the theory is not an accident. In fact as already stated above the spectral expansion on which the ERE formalism relies is state dependent, which implies that all the eigenfunctions but most importantly the eigenvalues $\lambda(\mu(t), \sigma(t))$ will rapidly adapt to time dependent stimuli. Since we show that the spectral gap between successive eigenvalues is fairly ubiquitous in the plane (μ, σ) the separation of time scales will still be valid even in out-of-equilibrium scenarios typically observed in vivo-like context.

We conclude this section by considering the coupling with an external excitatory pool that has a sinusoidal firing rate $\nu_{Ext}(t)$, this leads to two effects: an extra force term in (5.9) $F_{Ext}(\nu_{Ext})$ and also an explicit time dependence in the moments of the synaptic current i.e.:

$$\begin{aligned}\mu_{Ext}(t) &= K_{Ext} J_{Ext} \nu_{Ext}(t) \\ \sigma_{Ext}^2(t) &= K_{Ext} J_{Ext}^2 \nu_{Ext}(t)\end{aligned}$$

Figure 5.7 we show that also for a population of LIF neurons in similar condition of chaotic-like motion as the one shown in [MPR15] is found on a wide range of parameter, given that the coupling KJ is strong enough. This result adds to a series of facts that we believe are pointing toward some kind of universality at the mesoscopic, i.e. population, level dynamics. Moreover the phase space portrait of low dimensional model, Fokker-Planck, and spiking simulation is remarkably close even in the chaotic regime.

5.6 Conclusions

In this chapter we showed that it is possible to identify a separation of time scales in models of population of Integrate-and-Fire neurons. This separation of time scales is intimately related to the general hierarchical structure of eigenvalues of the operator of the Fokker-Planck equation that governs the dynamics of the distribution of membrane potentials in the pool. The general features of the eigenvalues depends more on the boundary condition of the problem than on the specific single neuron model used, hinting to some kind of emergent universal behavior at the mesoscopic scale. Using the ERE formalism, i.e. a state dependent eigen-basis, we proved that a low dimensional dynamics, in terms of population variable as the mean firing rate, can be obtained.

The low dimensional dynamics is in good agreement at the quantitative level with detailed simulation of spiking neural networks even in out-of-equilibrium and non linear scenarios. In particular the case of the uncoupled population can be remapped to an oscillator with relaxation time and angular frequency that depend on the mean and standard deviation of the synaptic current of the population. In such regard we observed previously unreported behavior of the decay time upon increasing the variance of the current. The same picture can be extended using quasi-linear approximation even in presence of synaptic coupling and we derived analytically the correction to the mesoscopic parameter parameters for both inhibitory and excitatory populations.

We studied also the effect of an exponential distribution of synaptic delays and the non linear dynamics of the mean firing rate going beyond linearizable regimes. In particular

Figure 5.7: Panel A shows shows the match between detailed simulation (black) Fokker-Planck integration (blue) and full low dimensional theory Eq. 5.9, in a strongly non-linear regime and external stimulus. Increasing the external firing rate ν_{Ext} frequency **B** we observe deterministic chaos and also in this case the low dimensional theory capture the behaviour accurately as shown in the bottom panels where the phase space portrait is reported. The detailed simulation was performed with $N=10^4$ neurons while all the other parameters were set as the drift-dominated case of Figure (5.5) but with $KJ = 14$ mV.

we show that Hopf (and saddle node) bifurcation can occur upon increasing the synaptic coupling, giving birth to limit cycles even without additional degree of freedom such as another inhibitory population or adaptation currents contrary to what was previously reported in literature.

Furthermore when an external periodic drive is added, we observed chaotic dynamics of the firing rate and, surprisingly, also in this highly non-linear and non-stationary case we had quantitative good match with detailed spiking simulation, even at the level of state space attractors.

For the sake of simplicity we did not include the effects of adaptation currents however as was showed in previous works [GMD07; Mat+19] the present framework can be extended with no fundamental complication. The same goes for the absolute refractory time that here we have assumed to be null. Also in this case the Fokker-Planck equation can take it into account and for this reason also the state dependent eigenbasis that we have used in this paper can be applied.

Another important direction for further theoretical development is to include finite size effects. These kind of fluctuation are particular evident in in-vivo data and can have drastic effects on the firing rate dynamics. In Chapter 4 we proved that the mean-field theory can be extended to include self consistent fluctuation and that in this case as well the effective dimensionality is fairly low.

Finally considering large ensembles of the population model here studied, can give insight on how large scale neural networks work. For example combining it with reservoir computers techniques, our model can help to understand how to train biologically realistic spiking neural network to reproduce the neural activity observed in cognitive task.

Biology is complex. Large set of parameters are very often required to fit the experimental data but most importantly the number of degree of freedom is generally very high. The main curse of dimensionality is to mine the understanding of the result produced by theoretical models and consequently to reduce their prediction power. For this reason since the seminal work of Wilson-Cowan much effort was made by many authors to produce a general low dimensional model to describe the coarse-grained behavior of cortical columns that are believed to be the real computational unit of the brain. Most of the times however the assumptions made to close the equation limit their general applicability. On the contrary in this chapter we presented a general theoretical framework that can be used to approximate the dynamics of such neural network in a very wide range of situation, independently on the single neuron model, and also to obtain low dimensional dynamical system of population variables that can be measured in experiments.

Chapter 6

Population membrane potential dynamics

Simplicity is the ultimate sophistication

Leonardo da Vinci

A novel approach to moment closure problem is used to derive low dimensional laws for the dynamics of the moments of the membrane potential distribution in a population of spiking neurons. Using spectral expansion of the density equation we derive the non linear relation between the moments, such as the mean potential, and the population firing rates. This expression relies of the dominant eigenvalues of the evolution operator that in turns are related to the moment of the single neuron Inter-Spike-Interval distribution. Contrary to previous attempts our system can be applied both in Noise- and Drift-dominated regime and both for weakly and strongly coupled population. We demonstrate the applicability of the theory for the case of Leaky-Integrate-and-Fire neural population where closed analytical expression can be found. We investigate the linear and non-linear dynamical regimes and compare it with direct integration of the population density equation. In particular we found new profound differences in the non-linear response due to an external periodic drive depending on whether the modulation is trough the mean or the variance of the total synaptic current.

6.1 Introduction

Deriving from first principle the dynamical laws governing the average behaviour of large and complex system has always been at the center of theoretical efforts in physics and not only.

Mean field theories are typically preferred since they relate the different scales considered, e.g. the firing rate activity population will depend on the main features of the single neuron, but closing the system has always proved to be changeling due to the non.linear and out-of-equilibrium nature of neural systems. As a result this strategy traditionally rests on a number of approximations that reduce the applicability of the theory. For example in [MPR15] the authors derived elegant dynamical laws for Quadratic spiking-neuron populations, valid however only for purely deterministic synaptic currents a condition far from biological neurons. On the contrary this restriction is not present in [SOA13] where a model valid for any spiking neurons network was derived, The limitation in this case is in the incapability of properly capture coupling effects. A generalized framework that can explain without significant restriction the complex repertoire of dynamics expressed by

neural population has been presented in Chapter 5 but we do not know yet how to infer the population membrane potential from the previous approach. This is an important missing link since many experiments measure proxy of average membrane potential and not firing rate. Moreover some additional features of the dynamics, like adaptation, could be relied on these degrees of freedom and not the firing rate.

For this reason in this Chapter we will show how it is possible to combine time scales separation and moment closure approaches to obtain effective low dimensional equations for the moments of the membrane potential and the firing rate of a network of spiking neurons. Our approach is general and can be applied to any single neuron model, moreover we can capture well even fast transients, non-linear regime and out-of-equilibrium behaviour and maybe most importantly noise-dominated regimes. Using our theory we investigate both linear and non-linear regime. In the latter case we found new interesting phenomena for the non-linear response to a periodic external signal. In particular we found profound differences depending on how the modulation is fed to the population i.e. through the mean or the variance of the total synaptic current. Moreover due to the non-linearity of the system hysteresis effects have been observed: multiple stable oscillatory regimes, i.e. with different amplitudes, can be expressed by the same neural population. We present the results choosing as single neuron the Leaky Integrate-and-Fire (LIF) since it is completely closed analytically.

The structure of the chapter is as follows: we first introduce the general framework of population density approach with a particular reference to the extended mean-field theory. Then we proceed in deriving the expressions for the dynamic response in the linear regime and compare it with the exact theoretical result. In this context we also discuss the stability of the stationary states of the model and also derive robust analytical approximations for the dominant eigenvalues of the continuity equation operator that allows to close analytically, for LIF neurons, the dynamical laws. Finally we study and test our model in strongly non-linear regime with a focus on a number of new phenomena that arise when we couple the system with external time-varying sources.

6.2 Firing rate and membrane potential

Consider a population of Leaky Interacting Integrate-and-Fire neurons.

Instead of solving in time the full continuity equation a common approach in statistical physics is to look at the time evolution of its moments. From equation 2.15 it is possible to derive an infinite system of ordinary differential equations for the standard moments:

$$\begin{aligned}
 m_k(t) &= \int_{\alpha}^{\theta} v^k p(v, t) dv \\
 \tau \dot{m}_1 &= -m_1 + \mu + \beta_1 \nu \tau \\
 \tau \dot{m}_k &= -k m_k + k \mu m_{k-1} + \beta_k \nu \tau + \frac{k(k-1)}{2} \sigma^2 m_{k-2}
 \end{aligned} \tag{6.1}$$

Where we defined $\beta_k = (H^k - \theta^k)$. If the reset mechanism was not included in the model the system would have been fully closed thanks to the Gaussian nature of the problem. In other words it would have been possible to truncate the dynamical system up to the second moment without losing any information. In our context however the firing rate $\nu(t)$ depends, in an unclear way, on all the moments of the distribution so we face a moment-closure problem [Kue16]. The solution we propose here is to use a new approach

that rests on the spectral expansion of the Fokker-Planck operator \mathbf{L}_v defined as $\partial_t p = \mathbf{L}_v p$.

The firing rate $v(t)$ can be written as the sum of the eigenmodes

$$a_n(t) = \int_{\alpha}^{\theta} \psi_n(v) P(v, t) dv$$

$\psi_n(v)$ being the adjoint eigenfunction of \mathbf{L}_v :

$$v(t) = \Phi(\mu, \sigma^2) + \frac{1}{\tau} \vec{1} \cdot \vec{a}$$

Where Φ is the current to rate Gain Function which for the LIF model is eq. (3.24). In the same way we can define the moment projection matrix

$$U_{kn} = \int_{\alpha}^{\theta} v^k \phi_n(v) dv$$

where $\phi_n(v)$ is the eigenfunction of \mathbf{L}_v . We can use \mathbf{U} to get an alternative expression for \vec{a} that in turns allows us to derive the main result of this chapter: the relation between the moments of $p(v, t)$ and the population firing rate $v(t)$

$$v(t) = \Phi(\mu, \sigma) + \frac{1}{\tau} \vec{1} \cdot \mathbf{U}^{-1}(\vec{m} - \vec{m}_0) \quad (6.2)$$

Note that this expression is valid for any IF neuron given the proper Φ and \mathbf{U} . Since is a direct consequence of the spectral expansion it is actually valid even for different kind of operators \mathbf{L}_v .

The relation between firing rate and moments of membrane potential is only apparently linear, in fact all the terms depend on μ and σ that are in turn function of the firing rate itself.

A great advantage of using LIF neurons is that both the stationary moments \vec{m}_0 and the projection matrix \mathbf{U} can be calculated analytically without knowing the actual eigenfunctions $\phi_n(v)$. More precisely equation (6.2) depends only on μ, σ and the the eigenvalues used λ_n . To see this we remember that, generally, the normalization of the probability density is related only to the stationary eigenmode and it ca be proved that $U_{0n} = \int_{v_{min}}^{\theta} \phi_n(v) dv = \delta_{0n}$. Then applying the same step as above to:

$$\tau \lambda_n \phi_n = \partial_v [(v - \mu) \phi_n] + \frac{\sigma^2}{2} \partial_v^2 \phi_n \quad (6.3)$$

we obtain the interesting relation:

$$U_{1,k} = \langle v \rangle_{\phi_n} = \frac{H - \theta}{\lambda_n \tau + 1}$$

Or in the general case $U_{k,n} = \langle v_n^k \rangle = \int_{\alpha}^{\theta} v^k \phi_n(v) dv$:

$$U_{k,n} = \langle v^k \rangle_{\phi_n} = \frac{\beta_k + k \mu U_{k-1,n} + \frac{\sigma^2}{2} k(k-1) U_{k-2,n}}{\lambda_n \tau + k}$$

which is closed by recursion.

As a bonus note that this allows to find some interesting results that re-sum series of ERE terms similar to what I've shown in Chapter 3. Just to give an example lets consider

the case where $p(v) = \delta(v - \tilde{v})$ which implies $a_n = \psi_n(\tilde{v})$. Now if we compute the k-th moment we get:

$$\tilde{v}^k = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \psi_n(\tilde{v}) \langle v_n^k \rangle$$

and if we set k to 1 and $\tilde{v} = u_0$ we find:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\psi_n(u_0)}{\lambda_n \tau + 1} = u_0$$

In a recent work [SZT20] the same moment closure problem was tackled following the maximization of entropy approach, another power-full tool of statistical physics. However as mentioned by the author themselves [ZR15] the transient dynamics, low and high frequency firing rate activity are poorly captured. The approximation made is that the solution $p(v, t)$ is essentially a slight modification of a implicitly time dependent stationary solution $p(v, \mu(t), \sigma^2(t))$ or in the spectral expansion notation $\phi_0(v, \nu(t))$. The success of our approach in a way suggests that when facing out-of-equilibrium non-linear problem the spectral expansion theory is one the most robust tool as it can relies on a state dependent decomposition that I already discussed in Chapter 5.

6.3 Linear regime

A first understanding of the limits of the approximations behind Equations 6.1 comes with studying the stability of the stationary state. As it is evident using spectral expansions techniques, see Chapter 3, this question can be answered by studying the poles the dynamic response $H_\nu = \partial_\nu \mu H_\mu + \partial_\nu \sigma H_\sigma$ [MD02; MD04].

Another possibility, that we follow here, is to look directly at the nature of the dominant eigenvalues of the stability matrix i.e. the linearized jacobian, of the ERE and moment systems. The analytic expression for both the jacobians for truncated expansions are reported in the Appendix. Figure 6.1 A – C demonstrates that the newly introduced system capture accurately the nature of the fixed point as we increase the coupling strength KJ .

In both systems we can distinguish three cases: when the real part of the eigenvalue is negative the fixed point is stable, when positive if the imaginary part is not null a stable limit cycle emerge or finally, in the case of a pure positive eigenvalue the limit cycle looses disappear. The last case was found to happen whenever $\partial_\nu \Phi(\nu) > 1$ (for excitatory population) [MD02]. The relative distance between the ERE and the moments system droops increasing the number of moements used. This is excepted since the approximation

$$\vec{a} \approx \mathbf{U}^{-1}(\vec{m} - \vec{m}_0)$$

becomes exact in the limit of infinite number of eigenmodes (i.e. moments) used.

6.4 Analytic expression for λ

From a practical point of view the system 6.1 is a significant step-forward with respect to the spectral expansion 5.2. In fact even though we now have closed expression for the coupling coefficients c_{n0} thanks to the results in Chapter 5, the same cannot be said for the non-linear terms coupling terms. In fact the integrals $c_{nm}(\nu)$ must be computed numerically for all possible values of $\nu(t)$ making the the original formulation unfeasible.

Figure 6.1: Linear Response. The dominant eigenvalues of the Jacobian of the ERE system [MD02] and moment system are reported in figure A and B. Different number of modes (moments) are considered: the color indicates the number of complex eigenpair used from 1 (red) to 4 (blue). The relative difference of the dominant eigenvalues between ERE and moment rapidly converges to zero as the dimensionality of the system is increased (C). The convergence of the low dimensional system and the Fokker-Planck is visible also in figure D where we compare the dynamics response to a modulation of μ using an increasing number of moment. The analytic results of [BH99] is reported in black. The stationary $\mu\tau$ is 21 [mV] while $\sigma\sqrt{\tau} = 2.66$ and $\theta = 20$ [mV] the unit of time i.e the membrane decay time τ is set to unity. For these parameters the stationary firing rate is at $\nu_0 = 0.4$.

On the contrary the only quantities needed for the moment system are $\lambda_n(\mu, \sigma)$ that have been studied thoughtfully in literature and in this thesis.

As we discussed in Chapter 5 a two dimensional system should be enough to capture most of the interesting features. In this case, to close analytically the of equations we need an expression for the dominant eigenvalues λ .

Several numerical tools have been proposed such as [Aug+17] that relies in standard non-linear root finding. Another more robust possibility is to use the Cauchy theorem that allows to find the eigenvalues calculating residues on a complex function, see Chapter 3, without the need of ansatz. From the analytical point of view a standard technique is to find perturbative correction to the deterministic case (that has exact solution) assuming $\sigma^2 \ll 1$. This is a WKB approach that lead to closed formulas [Kni00].

In [SOA13] the authors found that an approximate solution for the eigenvalue is

$$\lambda = \Phi(\mu, \sigma) [-(c_v/0.22)^2 + 2\pi i]$$

c_v being the coefficient of variation of the Inter-Spike-Interval (ISI) distribution defined in Chapter 3. When fluctuation can be neglected and the synaptic mean $\mu \gg F(V)$ all spiking model converge to the Perfect IF for which this result hold exactly [PGS20].

Albeit it gives physical intuition, this Ansatz is good only for small c_v and high stationary firing rate $\Phi(\mu, \sigma) \gg 1$ or, in other terms, sub-threshold regime regime ($\mu > \theta$). The strength of our approach compared to others is that we can fully capture noise-dominaneted dynamical state. For this reasons we followed a different path that relies on a number of exact result that we previously derived in Chapter 5. A good Ansatz must take into account a key feature of the spectrum of these systems: the existence of two different kind of family of eigenvalues witch eventually leads to a non smooth $\lambda(\mu, \sigma)$. Combining all the analytical results that we found it possible to derived an approximate formula for λ valid in both regimes, see Appendix D. Figure 6.2 shows the match between the numerical solution to the eigenvalue problem and our approximation in the plane (μ, σ) and the comparison between the analytic model and the Fokker-Planck integration stimulated by a sinusoidal current.

When I_{ext} is positive (negative) we are in drift-(noise-)dominated regime. The striking match with the continuity equation at all time demonstrates also that the new approach works well in all regimes and in the transition between the two which is a major improvement with respect to previous attempts.

Beyond the Leaky IF

In this chapter we used the LIF neuron model since, despite its biological accuracy, it allowed us to derive all the moment projection \mathbf{U} and stationary moments \vec{m}_0 analytically. Nevertheless the theory here presented is far more general then previous ones.

Consider the case an arbitrary current base IF neuron model. The Fokker-Planck reads:

$$\partial_t P = -\partial_v [(F(v) + \mu)P] + \frac{\sigma^2}{2} \partial_v^2 P$$

a good example is the exponential IF for which $F(v) = av + be^{cv} + d$ or the QIF neuron [Ger+14]. A convenient feature of our approach, that we have not use so far, is that

Figure 6.2: Analytic guess for λ . Figure **A** compares the numerical solution of the characteristic equation for the dominant eigenvalue in the plane (μ, σ) and the analytic guess approximation that we describe in the text. Figure **B** is the same but for the imaginary part. Figure **C** shows that using the analytic guess (red) we get striking match with in the integration of the Fokker-Planck (black). The parameters in this case are: $\mu_0 = 1.1, \sigma_0 = 0.3, KJ = 0.48$ (in unit of θ). We also add an external sinusoidal modulation of μ (magenta) with frequency $0.123\nu_0$. When I_{ext} is positive (negative) we are in drift-(noise-)dominated regime. This demonstrates also how our approach works well in the transition between the two main regime.

the definition of the moment m is arbitrary and could be any observable i.e. $\langle g(v) \rangle$ for arbitrary function $g(v)$.

A good choice for observables is the mean $u = \langle v \rangle$ and mean drift $f = \langle F(v) \rangle$ since this allows to greatly simplify the \mathbf{U} matrix in the 2D moment system. In fact with this choice, independently on the neuron model, we only need to estimate, together with the first two dominant eigenvalues, only the projection of the mean : $u_n(\mu, \sigma) = \int_{\alpha}^{\theta} v \phi_n(v) dv$. In fact we have that the projection of the drift on n -th eigenfunction is simply:

$$f_n = \int_{\alpha}^{\theta} F(v) \phi_n(v) dv = \theta - H - \lambda_n u_n$$

based on this observation we can expect that the method here presented can be applied with success to derive low dimensional dynamical laws of even more realistic neural populations. Note also that the eigenvalues spectrum of this kind of models is more dependent on the universal set of boundary condition than on the detail of single neuron, as I will address in Chapter 7, so there are reasons to believe that the functional form of $\lambda(\mu, \sigma)$ we derived here will be approximately the same.

6.5 The physics of neural populations

Before we proceed further in the analysis of non-linear regimes, it might be useful for the discussion to elucidate the main features of the physical behaviour of a general neural population. Using the spectral expansion we proved in Chapter 5 that the firing rate dynamics is equivalent to a state dependent oscillator meaning that both the decay time τ_ν and the natural frequency ω_ν depend on the moments of the synaptic current (μ, σ) .

More precisely, in the simple scenario of uncoupled network, the decay time is $\tau_\nu = -Re(\lambda)$ while the natural frequency $\omega_\nu = Im(\lambda)$.

When a coupled network is considered, either with itself or with external sources, these macroscopic quantities will also change with the coupling strength in a state-dependent manner. If that was not enough, an additional layer of complexity comes from the extended mean-field itself. To see this consider for example a network of uncoupled neurons that all receive the same time dependent current $I(t)$. The population $\omega_\nu(t)$ and $\tau_\nu(t)$ will depend on $I(t)$ through both $\mu(t)$ or $\sigma(t)$ and through the correction induced by the coupling with the external sources.

In other words, it is impossible to periodically drive a population of neurons without changing, at the same time, its natural frequency and decay time. Physical system with these properties may be subjected to the phenomena of parametric resonance.

In literature parametric resonance is studied under fairly simple scenario (i.e. linear oscillator with a time dependent $\omega(t)$) [LL76], this is however a simplification that we cannot afford since the firing rate dynamics we uncovered is intrinsically non-linear.

To summarize we can say that neural population are non-linear driven oscillator with state and time dependent frequency and decay time. The joint contribution of all this feature is responsible for the complex resonances and response patterns that are observed. Finally consider the fact that, albeit the mean-field dynamics is clearly deterministic, σ^2 is nonetheless the diffusion parameter of the stochastic dynamics of the single neurons in the pool. So conceptually speaking, the resonances that we discuss can be accounted as stochastic coherence phenomena [Lin+04; BSV81].

6.6 Non-linear regime

A great advantage of the theory we have just developed is that it is valid even in strongly non-linear regime and in open systems i.e, with external sources. While this is strictly true also for the standard spectral expansion approach, in that case to implement a non linear system we need all the coefficients $c_{nm} = \langle \partial_\nu \psi_n | \phi_m \rangle$ which pose a serious challenge for numerical implementation. On the contrary the moment system is formally identical to the uncoupled case i.e. no extra terms are added, and the coupling is completely taken into account through the definition of $\mu(\nu)$ and $\sigma(\nu)$. We demonstrate this investigating the case of a strongly coupled network of excitatory neurons. Using the prediction of linear theory we chose the value of the synaptic strength J such that the stationary solution is unstable and the firing rate dynamics follows a limit cycle. Moreover we add an external sinusoidal modulation of the mean synaptic current $\mu_0(t)$. As shown in figure 6.4 two moments alone can already reproduce, on a quantitative level, most of the features of the dynamics obtained by direct integration of the Fokker-Planck. This is even more evident when we look at the striking similarity of the phase space portrait. The quality of the match increase

Figure 6.3: Stability of limit cycle. Figure A is a contour map of the amplitude of the limit cycle as a function of extra mean or variance of the synaptic current. The parameters of the network are fixed such that the stationary moments are $\mu_0 = 1.36$, $\sigma_0 = 0.205$, $K = 1000$ and $J = 0.52/K$. In figure B we report firing rate dynamics in four reference point in the plane for $\beta = 0$. Black traces correspond to the case $\mu_x = \sigma_x = 0$. Figure C shows the case $\beta = 0.3$ with a modulation on μ of amplitude $0.3\mu_{ext}$ (i) and on σ^2 of amplitude $0.3\sigma_{ext}^2$ (ii).

Figure 6.4: Non-linear regime. To test the limit of our model we set the network in a strongly non-linear regime. We set $K = 1000$ $J = 0.38\theta/K$ and μ_{ext}, σ_{ext} such that the stationary state is at firing rate $\nu_0 = 0.4$ ($\mu_0 = 1.05\theta, \sigma = 0.133\theta$ and $\tau=1$). For this value of KJ the stationary state is unstable and the rate dynamics presents a limit cycle. We had also a periodic drive to μ_{ext} equal to $I_1 \sin(\omega t)$ ($I_1 = 0.12\mu_{ext}, \omega = 0.122\pi\nu_0$). The match between the trajectories of the firing rate and the first two moments is reported in figure **A** and the phase portrait in figure **B**. As in previous figure red indicate 2 moments system, purple 6 moments systems and black the Fokker-Planck equation.

when we consider 6 moments system as already expected from the linear theory prediction.

In this condition the neural population has an intrinsic frequency, that of the limit cycle, so we decided to study the effect of external periodic stimulation. To do so we plotted the Poincare section of the the local maxima of the firing rate as a function of the external frequency. In figure 6.5 we report the results of this analysis both for the modulation of μ and σ as a function of β i.e. the ratio between the frequency of the limit cycle oscillation and that of the external drive using a two-moment model and the Fokker-Planck result.

Crowded regions indicate complex structure of the firing rate dynamics with multiple local peaks possibly a-periodic or chaotic-like dynamics. The quantitative differences with respect to the Fokker-Planck integration were expected especially at high frequency stimulation as they were already present in the linear regime. Moreover a fair comparison would require a different value of KJ for the moment system since, as we have shown previously the bifurcation to limit cycle is slightly shifted with respect to the real value.

Despite these differences, that as we demonstrated vanish upon increasing the dimensionality of the model, we can observe striking qualitative similarities already with the 2 dimensional approximation. In particular it is interesting that the low frequency stimulation is qualitatively different in the two different kind of modulation.

A modulation of only the variance of the synaptic current seems at first a rather academic effort since it appears as a condition difficult to obtain in experiments. However when we consider coupled populations of excitatory and inhibitory neurons a balanced condition become accessible. When the excitatory and inhibitory contribution are balanced the mean of the synaptic current can not change considerably while the variance has no such constraints [Bru00]. In fact growing number of evidence have been reported that advocate for variance-based exchange of information in neural processing systems. It is then important to understand the reasons behind such different non-linear response in the two scenarios [LS01]. Due to multiple and interacting mechanism at play, some of which we discussed above, it is difficult to pin-point a unique cause behind the absence of these regular structures in the low frequency regime of the σ -modulation. However one property that may have a role is the robustness of limit-cycle under small perturbation. As we shown in figure 6.3 a positive constant increase on μ_{ext} will result in a limit cycle with higher amplitude, while a negative one can even make the cycle vanish. The exact opposite happens when we add constant external variance. In a way this is reminiscent of what occurs in uncoupled population: the population decay τ_v increase with σ^2 ($-Re(\lambda)$) while the angular frequency ω_v increase with μ ($Im(\lambda)$). Under slow stimulation ($\beta \ll 1$) the system will adapt adiabatically to the change in synaptic current leading to an entertainment for the modulation of μ . On the contrary when we modulate σ it will result in a "wax and wane" motion that leads to a far richer Poincare section.

Non-linear response is far less studied in neuroscience with respect to linearizable regime, maybe due to the analytical approaches that exist for the latter. Leveraging on the effectiveness our theory we can try to answer new questions and uncover new phenomena. For example we can ask what is the effect of the intensity of the periodical modulation? As we show in figure 6.6 that the effects of large amplitude are dependent also on the frequency of stimulation and the Poincare section of the maxima change considerably when we increase the intensity of the modulation.

Particularly interesting is the case of $\beta \sim 1$. We can see a peculiar effect both on the

Figure 6.5: Non linear response. On the y axis we show the Poincaré map of the local maxima in the firig rate dynamics of both the Fokker-Planck and 2D moments system. On figure **A** we use the same parameters of Fig. 6.4 but we modulate $\mu(t) = KJ\nu(t) + 0.05\mu_{ext}\sin(2\pi\beta\nu_0t)$. **B** Here the modulation is on $\sigma^2(t) = KJ^2\nu(t) + \sigma_{ext}^2 + 0.03\sigma_{ext}^2\sin(2\pi\beta\nu_0t)$ moreover the stationary moments are $\mu_0 = 1.36\theta$ and $\sigma_0 = 0.205\theta$ with $J = 0.52\theta/K$.

Figure 6.6: Effects of amplitude of stimulation. Figure A shows how the Poincaré map of Figure 6.6 B changing the amplitude of stimulation of σ^2 from $(0.1\sigma_{ext})^2$ (left) to $(0.5\sigma_{ext})^2$ (right). For the same span of parameters we also report the firing rate dynamics at $\beta = 1.1$ in figure B for the model (upper panel) and the F.P. (lower). Finally in C following the protocol in the first row we change in time the intensity of the modulation, as discussed in the text the initial state (red for the model and black for the F.P) is radically different to the final state even though the parameters in this two cases are the same.

model and on the Fokker-Planck. An envelope appears when we modulate σ in a specific range of amplitude and subsequently disappears. This is a case of multi stability of limit cycles, a known property of driven non linear oscillator [LL76; Bog+61].

As in standard non-linear oscillator we found also in our model, an intensity-dependent bi-stability of cycles highlighted by the hysteresis phenomena shown in figure 6.6 C.

6.7 Conclusions

In this work have shown how it is possible to derive closed dynamical laws for the moments of the membrane potential distribution of a population of LIF spiking neurons and, most importantly, their relation with the population firing rate. Of particular interest in this regards are the eigenvalues of the Fokker-Planck operator that governs the mean-field population dynamics.

The dynamical system we derived has the great advantage to be valid both in noise

and drift-dominated regimes in contrast with most moment closure approaches that can be found in the literature so far that only applies in restricted regimes. Those restrictions arise from approximations necessary to close the moment systems, such as assuming deterministic synaptic current [MPR15], weak coupling [SOA13] or adiabatic approximation [ZR15]. We could avoid these typical issues applying spectral expansion tools. As expected the quality of reproduction of the macroscopic quantities increase with number of moments used which in our context is equivalent to the number of eigenmodes, or time scales, considered. We demonstrated this by studying first linear regime for which analytical form of the dynamic response could be found and matched to exact analytical results.

Our theory works equally well in strongly non-linear regime both due to huge coupling of the network or strong external modulation so we decided to study the non-linear response of the system. We found that a 2 moments closure can already reproduce the firing rate dynamics of the F.P integration with striking similarity even in strongly out-of-equilibrium regimes.

Applying a sinusoidal modulation of μ or σ to a strongly coupled population that already is autonomously oscillating we investigated the response as a function of both the frequency and amplitude of the forcing. Keeping the amplitude of modulation fixed we analyzed the pattern of local maxima in $\nu(t)$ varying the frequency of the forcing uncovering a rich and not yet reported scenario. As expected we observed high response peaks when the external frequency is an integer multiple of the proper oscillation frequency. More interestingly we found analogous results in the low frequency regime and windows of chaotic-like or a-periodic dynamics clear signs of non-linear nature of neural populations.

Surprisingly the low frequency peaks were not present when considering the modulation of σ . We believe that such profound differences are related to equally different structural stability of the limit cycle to a perturbation of either the mean or the variance of the synaptic current.

We also investigated the effects of the amplitude of the modulation in σ and found a non monotonic response. In the sense that a sort of envelope of the firing rate is gradually more manifest until a critical value of intensity is reached. This behaviour has been long known to be typical of driven non-linear oscillators [Bog+61], and is related to the existence of multiple accessible cycles whose stability depends non-monotonically on the amplitude of the external forcing. This hysteresis of cycles was never reported before for neural populations.

We proved with comparison of direct integration of the population density the effectiveness and limits of our theory. Contrary to standard moment closure approaches where an ansatz of $p(v, t)$ is assumed and consequently the macroscopic equations are consistently derived, we relied on the separation of time scales that is manifested in the spectral gap typical of spiking neural networks population dynamics and appears to be a model independent feature [Aug+17] i.e. related more to the common boundary conditions than on the single neuron details.

As a result our approach is far more general than previous attempts. For example we can investigate both drift-dominated and strongly noise dominated regimes and consider both strongly and weakly coupled populations. We have also found an analytical expression for the dominant eigenvalues of the LIF Fokker-Planck operator that allows us to close analytically a 2-dimensional dynamical system. The main result of this chapter however,

is the complex relation between population activity, i.e. firing rate, and mean membrane potential. We anticipate that this results will be of value to analyze experimental data that have access to both kinds of information such as voltage-sensitive dye recordings. Finally the simplicity and efficiency of our theory makes it ideal for studies involving large scale dynamics and whole brain simulation [San+13]. For all the reason above we anticipate that the dynamical laws we derived here will be powerful lens to study the complex multi-scale and out-of-equilibrium dynamics of the brain.

Chapter 7

Universal population dynamics with simplified spiking neurons

It is not because Nature is really similar; it's because the physicists have only been able to think the same damn thing over and over again

Richard Feynman

Despite the large plethora of different theoretical models of cortical circuits, the emerging neural dynamics is often similar. In this chapter we investigate to what extent the mean-field description of a neural population can be considered universal, i.e. partially independent on the specific single neuron model. I show this in the context of population density approach of network of Integrate-and-Fire neurons. We found that the source of this universality is in the strong analogies of the spectrum of the Fokker-Planck operator that governs the dynamics of the membrane potential density for different models. We show how it is possible to map on a quantitative level the firing rate dynamics of a population of uncoupled LIF neurons to that of VIF neurons, a simplified and analytically tractable model. Once the match is done also the Inter-Spike-Interval distribution of the two model are indistinguishable.

Since its foundation the field of computational neuroscience is characterized by two different tensions regarding the models of biological neural networks. On one hand the emphasis is on biological details such as specific ionic channels effects [HH52a]. On the other simplified model of population of neurons have been also been used where the focus is on general dynamical properties [WC72]. The idea behind the latter approach is that the computations that are behind all cognitive function are mainly due to emergent effects arising from the interaction of a large number of neurons. In this context many authors have consistently use concept from theoretical physics, as mean-field theories, to derive population model from first principles. This allows to bridge the mesoscopic scale to the microscopic one and thus understand what are the key ingredients that must be considered and what is less important.

A good example of the balance between simplicity and complexity is the population density approach in network of Integrate-and-Fire neurons. However during the years a plethora of different models has been proposed leaving open a question: to what extent the mean-field dynamics, i.e. the population dynamics, is universal and independent on the specific model used? The Exponential Integrate and Fire has been shown to be the

best choice to fit the exact timing of spike emission in single neuron in-vitro [Bad+08], its non-linearity make the analysis essentially computational and very few analytic results can be obtained. If one is interested however on the population firing rate it might be possible to obtain identical dynamics but using much simpler models as it has been observed both theoretically [SML13] and experimentally [Rau+03].

In this chapter we will study the simplified Virtual Integrate-and-Fire neuron and show how it is possible to use it to reproduce, on a population level, the firing rate of the "gold-standard" leaky IF. We demonstrate that the source of this universality is related to the model-independent structure of the spectrum of the Fokker-Planck operators which depends more on the boundary condition than on the single neuron details. We will also show how the same reasoning applies to the Inter-Spike-Interval distributions of the two models.

The results are presented as follow: we first present the general framework of population density approach of Integrate-and-Fire neurons. In particular we briefly review the spectral expansion of the Fokker-Planck equation for the population membrane potential and the equivalent formulation in terms of emission rate equations. Then we specialize the result to the Virtual Integrate Fire neuron a simplified model first introduce in [FM99]. We show the eigenvalues spectrum of the Fokker-Planck operator of the VIF and highlight its model-independent features by comparing it with the standard Leaky Integrate-and-Fire. We then comment on the complex relation between the first passage time distribution and the spectrum and show that the universality of the spectrum is reflected also in the universality of the the fist two moment of the Inter-Spike-Interval distribution of the two models. We also mention that despite its analytical tractability the VIF neuron is capable of reproducing true neural response function observed in vitro [Rau+03].

The mesoscopic parameter of the firing rate dynamics, i.e. the decay time and angular frequency, are studied as a function of the value of the reflecting boundary α and compared with the LIF model. Finally we discuss how a state dependent α allows to match quantitatively the rate dynamics of this two microscopically different models. We also show that once the identification of the parameter is done also the Inter-Spike-Interval distribution, I.S.I, are essentially indistinguishable.

7.1 A simplified spiking neuron

In this chapter we will consider two choices for $f(v)$ in Eq.2.2 corresponding to the *leaky* and *virtual* IF neuron:

$$f(v) = \begin{cases} -\frac{v}{\tau} & \text{leaky IF} \\ -\beta & \text{virtual IF} \end{cases} \quad (7.1)$$

The first is considered as the "gold-standard" of integrate-and-fire modeling, while the second is a version of the model used in [GM64], in which a key ingredient is introduced: a lower bound, α , on the V values, acting as a reflecting barrier for the corresponding stochastic process. The VIF model was initially proposed for electronic VLSI implementations [FM99] where α was taken equal to the reset potential H while here we leave α as a free choice.

Independently on the specif IF model the boundary conditions of the continuity equation are the same and we have already discussed them in Chapter 2.

7.2 Infinite population of uncoupled VIF neurons

Because of its amenability to analytical treatment, we specialise the above analysis to the linear IF neuron (VIF) taking as decay term $f(v) = -\beta$ a constant. For simplicity here we set $\mu(t) - \beta \rightarrow \mu(t)$, considering β as a constant inhibitory afferent current, and the corresponding Fokker-Planck operator L_{VIF} becomes

$$L_{\text{VIF}}(v, t) = -\mu(t)\partial_v + \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2(t)\partial_v^2. \quad (7.2)$$

while the adjoint operator in this specific model is

$$L_{\text{VIF}}^+ = \mu(t)\partial_v + \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2(t)\partial_v^2, \quad (7.3)$$

Note that we will focus in this chapter on an uncoupled population for which the spectral expansion can be formally solved, see equation 3.6. The stationary solution, corresponding to $\lambda = 0$, turns out to be

$$\phi_0(v, t) = \begin{cases} -\frac{\nu}{\mu} \left(e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}(v-\theta)} - 1 \right) & H \leq v \leq \theta \\ -\frac{\nu}{\mu} \left(e^{-\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}\theta} - e^{-\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}H} \right) e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}v} & \alpha \leq v < H, \end{cases} \quad (7.4)$$

where ν is the mean fraction of neurons crossing the threshold per unit time. By the Eq.(7.4), the explicit form of the gain function can be derived

$$\Phi(\mu, \sigma) = -\frac{\sigma^2}{2} \partial_v \phi_0(v)|_{v=\theta} = \frac{2\mu^2}{\sigma^2 e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}\alpha} \left(e^{-\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}H} - e^{-\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}\theta} \right) - 2\mu(\theta - H)}, \quad (7.5)$$

An analytic expression of the eigenfunctions ϕ, ψ that satisfies all the boundary condition is derived in the Appendix E (using methods similar to [DR17]): in both cases, the eigenfunctions are combination of exponential functions, but with an explicit dependence on the L_{VIF} eigenvalues λ s. The latter are the solutions of the *characteristic equation*

$$\frac{e^\xi (\zeta \cosh(\zeta\alpha) - \xi \sinh(\zeta\alpha))}{\xi \sinh(\zeta - \zeta\alpha) + \zeta \cosh(\zeta - \zeta\alpha)} = 1 \quad (7.6)$$

where we introduce the variables $\xi = \frac{\mu}{\sigma^2}$ and ζ such that $\lambda = \frac{\sigma^2}{2}(\zeta^2 - \xi^2)$ and set for simplicity $\theta = 1$ and $H = 0$. This shows a convenient property of the VIF eigenvalues i.e. while λ is a function of both μ and σ^2 we can find a ζ , and so solve the spectrum, that depends only on one variable. This can be proven formally since we can derive a differential equation for the eigenvalue. To do so we can start from $\lambda\psi = L^\dagger\psi$ and take the derivative of the equation with respect of ∂_μ and ∂_σ^2 . Multiplying the results with respect to ϕ and integrating in the domain one can use the orthonormality of the basis to prove that $\partial_\mu\lambda = \langle \phi \partial_v \psi \rangle$ and $\partial_\sigma^2\lambda = \langle \phi \partial_v^2 \psi \rangle / 2$. Finally using this results in the equation $\lambda \langle \phi \psi \rangle = \langle \psi L \phi \rangle$ one arrive at:

$$\mu \partial_\mu \lambda + \sigma^2 \partial_{\sigma^2} \lambda = \lambda$$

that admits a general solutions of the form :

$$\lambda = \mu k(\xi)$$

where $k(\xi)$ is an arbitrary function.

For the critical value $\mu = 0$ (already been identified in [MD02], where the VIF model was implemented with $\alpha = H$), the equation (7.6) can be solved and two family of eigenvalues are found:

$$\lambda_{DD} = -2\pi^2 \left(\frac{\sigma}{H - \theta} \right)^2 n^2, \quad n \in \mathbb{N}, \quad (7.7)$$

$$\lambda_{ND} = -2\pi^2 \left(\frac{\sigma}{H + \theta - 2\alpha} \right)^2 n^2, \quad n \in \mathbb{N}. \quad (7.8)$$

In general [MD02; Aug+17], we can distinguish between two different kind of eigenvalues : (i) the *noise-dominated* eigenvalues λ_{ND} , those are present both in supra-threshold regime ($\mu > 0$ for the VIF) and in sub-threshold regime ($\mu < 0$ for the VIF), they are always real (ii) the other type of eigenvalues, are called *drift-dominated* λ_{DD} , their real part also goes as $\sim n^2$ but for a critical value for μ they bifurcate to complex conjugate pairs.

7.2.1 Role of α : match with LIF neurons

In previous studies [MD02; FM99], the reflecting barrier of the membrane potential was set equal to the reset potential $\alpha = H$. This choice simplifies the analytical study and was also natural for a VLSI implementation.

The Leaky I.F. loses memory of the incoming stimuli at a rate of $1/\tau_m$ where τ_m is the membrane decay time. From a physical point of view the reflecting barrier of the VIF has the exact same role.

In this case the memory of the neuron is related to the time to drive the depolarization to α which is θ/μ in absence of afferent current.

On a population level the relevant time scales of the system are captured by the dominant eigenvalues of the F.P. operator i.e. $\tau_n = -1/Re(\lambda_n)$, so the effects of α of the spectrum induce different population dynamical regimes, see Chapter 5.

In figure (7.1) we show the spectrum of VIF operator for tree different values of α . As was pointed out in Chapter 5, when $\alpha = H$ all the eigenvalues will bifurcate from real to complex conjugates when the mean synaptic current is greater then a model-specific threshold $\mu > \mu^*$. This qualitative behaviour is universal, i.e. model independent, as it occurs in VIF, LIF and EIF ([Aug+17]).

When $\alpha \neq H$ two important features appear. First a newborn family of eigenvalues, called Noise-Dominated, emerge. These λ will always be real independently on the value of μ .

The second important feature is that the Drift-Dominate family of eigenvalues still bifurcates to complex conjugate but we found that the value of μ^* where this occur depends non monotonically on both of α and the index of the mode n . Also this two characteristics appear to be universal as have been noted for the other I.F. models mentioned above.

To summarize, it is reasonable to assume that the eigenvalue problem of the Fokker-Planck operator of I.F. neuron depend more strictly on the general structure of boundary conditions then on the specific drift component. For this reason the main features and hierarchy of the spectrum are universal.

Figure 7.1: Spectrum of the VIF neuron Fokker-Planck operator with varying $\alpha = H$. The dominant eigenvalues λ_n , found solving the characteristic equation (), are reported. The Drift-Dominated λ are in red tonality while the Noise-Dominated are in blue and the intensity of the tone differentiate the mode n . **A** $\alpha = H$ as in [MD02] only the DD eigenvalues are present and the all bifurcate simultaneously at $\xi^* = 0$. **B** $\alpha = H - 0.2\theta$ the ND family is now present even though the dominant modes are still DD. Moreover the complex conjugate λ_n will bifurcate at $\xi^* = \xi^*(\alpha, n)$. **C** $\alpha = H - 0.3\theta$ same feature of **B** but the dominant eigenmode is now ND up to a second bifurcation at high ξ .

7.2.2 Single-neuron features: ISI statistics, input-output gain function Φ and coefficient of variation c_v

The most important single-neuron feature that rules part of the mean field population dynamics is the current-to-rate gain function Φ , or, more generally, the Inter-Spike-Interval, ISI, distribution [Tuc89]. For this reason we compare now the distributions of first-passage time and its relation with the adjoint eigenfunctions $\psi_n(v)$ for the VIF and LIF neuron.

The distribution of the first passage time, $\rho(t)$, is related to the backward Fokker-Planck equation [Kam07] or in our notation $\partial_t \rho(x', t) = L^\dagger \rho(x', t)$. This can be solved in Laplace domain [FM99] :

$$\rho(x', s) = \int_0^\infty e^{-st} g(x', t) dt$$

were the problem becomes:

$$\frac{\sigma^2}{2} \rho''(x, s) + b(x) \rho'(x, s) - s \rho(x, s) = 0 \quad (7.9)$$

with boundary condition

$$\rho(\theta, s) = 1 \quad \partial_{x'} \rho(x', s)|_{x'=\alpha} = 0$$

this has the same solution to the adjoint eigenfunction problem so for any I.F neuron it holds that the Laplace transform of the ISI density is:

$$\rho(s) = \frac{\psi(H, s)}{\psi(\theta, s)} = \frac{e^{\xi} (\zeta \cosh(\zeta \alpha) - \xi \sinh(\zeta \alpha))}{\xi \sinh(\zeta - \zeta \alpha) + \zeta \cosh(\zeta - \zeta \alpha)} \quad (7.10)$$

with the usual definition of $\zeta(s)$ and ξ .

As a consequence of this results it follows from (7.6), that the characteristic equation that determines the eigenvalues λ_n , of the F.P. operator, can be rewritten using the ISI Laplace transform:

$$\rho_{\theta, H}(\lambda_n) = 1 \quad (7.11)$$

this observation was made recently, with a different proof, also in [PGS20].

Equation (7.11) proves that a complex relation between the eigenvalues and moments of the ISI exists suggesting that a similarity on the structure of the spectrum might induce a similarity in the ISI distribution of two different I.F. models.

The mean of the variance of the ISI distribution can be computed from the Laplace transform:

$$M_T = \tau_{arp} - \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial s} \Big|_{s=0} \quad V_T = \left(\frac{\partial^2 \rho}{\partial s^2} - \left(\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial s} \right)^2 \right) \Big|_{s=0}$$

where τ_{arp} is the absolute refractory period.

From that the gain function $\Phi(\mu, \sigma) = \frac{1}{M_T}$ and the ISI coefficient of variation $c_v(\mu, \sigma) = \frac{\sqrt{V_T}}{M_T}$ are obtained.

In figure (7.2) we compare this two quantities in the plane (μ, σ) between a LIF neuron with $\alpha = -\infty$ and a VIF with $\alpha = H - 0.2\theta$. The effects of increasing further α in the VIF are mostly notable at relatively high σ but the general picture remain untouched.

The strong resemblance of this two key ingredients of the mean-field description of two microscopically different models suggests, once again, a possible mapping of (μ, σ, α) that can fit on a quantitative level the population dynamics of LIF neurons as we will show in the last section of the results.

Figure 7.2: Comparison of gain function and ISI c_v . **A** The gain functions $\Phi(\mu, \sigma)$ of a LIF neuron $\alpha = -\infty$ and a VIF with $\alpha = H - 0.2\theta$ are compared. The only substantial difference between the two is a shift on the μ axis. **B** Shows the match of the c_v of the same two model

Having a quantitative match of the firing rate dynamics of two different uncoupled populations is actually equivalent to say that the ISI distributions of the two are very similar and viceversa. This statement can be proven rigorously for any I.F. model by considering the probability of emitting one spike in an interval $[t, t + dt]$ is given by $Pr(t_{spike} \in [t, t + dt]) = \rho(t)dt$.

Under renewal regime, which applies in the context of uncoupled population, the probability of emitting the m -th spike in the same interval, $Pr(t_{m-th\ spike} \in [t, t + dt]) = \rho_m(t)dt$ can be written as a convolution:

$$\rho_m(t) = \int_0^t \rho(t)\rho_{m-1}(t - \tau)d\tau$$

with $\rho_0(t) = \delta(t)$ and $\rho_1(t) = \rho(t)$. Then using the definition of the firing we can found a closed relation, in Laplace domain, between the ISI distribution and the the firing rate dynamics of a population of neurons that start all at $v = H$:

$$v_H(s) = \frac{\rho(s)}{1 - \rho(s)} \quad (7.12)$$

See equation 3.3 for the proof. One could note that up to know we have showed an equivalence of only the first two moments of the ISI. However equation (7.12) implies that if a match of the firing rate dynamics $v_H(t)$ is possible, in particular of the transient, then the same holds for ρ . At the same time $v(t)$ is fully determined by the Fokker-Planck spectrum $\{\lambda_n\}$ which we have already showed to be in some sense "universal". In the next section we will show to what extent the relaxation dynamics of the two model, in different regimes, are qualitatively similar, before that we show yet another general relation between the c_v and the λ_n . By taking the limit $s \rightarrow 0$ it can be proved that:

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\psi_k(H)}{\tau_m \lambda_k} = \frac{1 - c_v^2}{2} \quad (7.13)$$

Equation (7.13) is useful in different context. For example it clearly show that the first two moment of the the ISI constrain greatly the Fokker-Planck spectrum. In figure (7.3) we report the rate of convergence of (7.13) as a function of the number of eigenvalues included in noise and drift-dominated regime for the VIF, highlighting the fact that in the former case far fewer mode are necessary to reach convergence and so to capture the full dynamics of $v(t)$. The exact same behaviour was found in LIF neural population. Stated in more physical terms the firing rate dynamics is intrinsically higher dimensional in drift-dominated regime with respect to noise-dominated one.

7.3 Population relaxation dynamics

The different eigenvalues of the F.P spectrum accounts for different time scales. Including all the eigenmodes up to $m - th$ one allows us to describe accurately the firing rate dynamics $v(t)$ neglecting all the effects that live on a time scale $\tau \ll -1/Re(\lambda_m)$.

The universal hierarchy of eigenvalues that we have shown above implies then a separation of time scales in the mean field description and the possibility of reducing the dynamics to a limited number of dimension. If one consider only the dominant eigen mode two possible scenario arise:

- $Im(\lambda_1) = 0$ which implies a one dimensional dynamics:

$$\dot{v} = \frac{\Phi(v) - v}{\tau_v}$$

- $Im(\lambda_1) \neq 0$ which implies a two dimensional dynamics:

$$\tau_v^2 \ddot{v} + 2\tau_v \dot{v} = (1 + \tau_v^2 \omega_v^2)(\Phi(v) - v)$$

Figure 7.3: Relation between the c_v and Fokker-Planck spectrum. The convergence of (7.13) is shown for Noise-Dominated **A** and Drift-Dominated **B** regime, as a function of the number of λ included. The former case need just few λ while for the second at least $n\lambda \sim 10^2$ is required.

where we defined the population decay time and angular frequency:

$$\tau_v(\mu, \sigma) = -1/\text{Re}(\lambda_1(\mu, \sigma)) \quad \omega(\mu, \sigma) = \text{Im}(\lambda_1(\mu, \sigma)) \quad (7.14)$$

so the firing rate dynamics of an uncoupled population is always a relaxation oscillator with state dependent coefficients.

As already discussed in Chapter 5, the decay time and angular frequency are non monotonic function of the synaptic current. Figure (7.4) shows the match between theory and non linear fit of direct integration of Fokker-Planck equation of a VIF population.

In the literature a distinction is often made between sub-threshold regime ($\mu < \theta$) and supra-threshold regime ($\mu > \theta$). However the often related overdamped and oscillatory response regime can be found at various points of the plane (μ, σ) . Stated differently, just like in the LIF population, it is the nature of the dominant eigenvalue (being complex or real) that decide the type of response to a step stimulus. For example one can find overdamped response with a mean current well above threshold, and also a counter intuitive behavior of τ_v as a function of the variance of the synaptic current.

We know proceed to compare the decay time and angular frequency of VIF and LIF population. As reported in figure (7.5) the major difference, just like $\Phi(\mu, \sigma)$ and c_v is a shift on the mean current (μ). This was expected also by analytical results on the spectrum obtained in both models. More specifically for the LIF we know that the bifurcation from real to complex conjugate will occur around $\mu = \frac{\theta-H}{2}$ while for the VIF this happens at $\mu = 0$. This is strictly true on the limit of $\alpha \rightarrow H$ where there are no Noise dominated eigenvalue for both models.

When $\alpha < H$, on one hand the bifurcation point mentioned above is state dependent and on the other the noise-dominant family starts to play a role. In the LIF non matter the value of α , as long as it is different of H there will be a σ such that for any μ $\omega_v = 0$, i.e. the dominant eigenvalue is real. These two effects combined are responsible for the curvature of the $\omega_v = 0$ boundary as a function of α .

For the VIF instead there exist two threshold values of α : one below which the noise dominated eigenvalue is never dominant, yet the bifurcation of the drifted-dominated is

Figure 7.4: Match between theory and Fokker-Planck integration. **A** the population decay τ_v and angular frequency ω_v as a function of the mean μ and standard deviation σ of the synaptic current measured in unit of threshold θ (τ_m is the membrane decay time). The contour levels and color function are the same used in figure (). **B** shows the match between theory (solid line) and non-linear fit of F.P. integration (dots) of τ_v and ω_v along the cyan cut reported in **A**. The same is shown in **C** for the magenta path. In this case an iso-firing rate curve was followed.

state dependent and one above which the dominant λ is always real, i.e. $\omega_v(\mu, \sigma) = 0$ for all (μ, σ) . Moreover for relatively low level of σ the τ_v of the VIF seems to be much faster than for the LIF.

Even when these differences are taken into account the overall picture still suggests remarkable similarities between two models that at a microscopic level are completely different.

Figure 7.5: Comparison of τ_v and ω_v . For three different values of α the comparison of decay time and population angular frequency is reported between the VIF (**A**) and the LIF (**B**). The best quantitative match between the two models is reached at not too low σ . However the qualitative change as a function of α is consistent.

7.4 Mapping the VIF to LIF

The spectral expansion formalism highlights a general structure of the dynamical laws of a mean field neural population which is independent on the specific IF neuron used. In the previous section we have shown that the parameters that govern the mean field dynamics are qualitatively similar for the VIF and LIF neuron. At the same time we also saw that this similarity is even stronger when we look at the first two moment of the ISI distribution as a function of the synaptic current.

In particular we note that some features of the LIF model not captured by the standard VIF can be taken into account by considering a non static $\alpha(\mu, \sigma)$. The idea of of state dependent threshold to model the emission of a spike is an old one and can also be justified with biophysical arguments [Ger+14].

We will not discuss here what are the characteristic of $\alpha(\mu, \sigma)$, and eventually $\theta(\mu, \sigma)$, that optimally implements the missing features of a static VIF but we will directly try to map the firing rate dynamics of a LIF population to that of a VIF.

To do so we first fix the stationary firing rate of the LIF ν_{LIF} and mean current μ_{LIF} then we found σ_{LIF} imposing:

$$\Phi^{LIF}(\mu_{LIF}, \sigma_{LIF}) = \nu_{LIF}$$

The ISI Laplace transform of the LIF is known to be:

$$\rho(s)_{LIF} = \frac{\sqrt{e^{X_r^2}} \mathcal{D}_{-s}(-\sqrt{2}X_r)}{\sqrt{e^{X_t^2}} \mathcal{D}_{-s}(-\sqrt{2}X_t)}$$

where $X_t = \frac{\theta - \mu}{\sigma}$, $X_r = \frac{H - \mu}{\sigma}$ and $\mathcal{D}_\nu(z)$ is the parabolic cylinder function solution of the Weber differential equation.

From the above equation we then calculate the corresponding c_v^{LIF} . Finally, using standard find root algorithm, we search for the triplet (μ, σ, α) that satisfies:

$$\begin{cases} \Phi^{VIF}(\mu, \sigma, \alpha) = \nu_{LIF} \\ c_v^{VIF}(\mu, \sigma, \alpha) = c_v^{LIF} \end{cases} \quad (7.15)$$

the system is under-determined so in principle infinite solution might exist.

In figure 7.6 we show the results of this mapping in both Noise- and Drift-Dominated regime. Once the mapping is done we integrate the Fokker-Planck equation of the two systems with the same initial condition i.e. $P(v, t = 0) = \delta(v - H)$. The firing rate dynamics, $\nu(t)$, are indistinguishable despite the great difference of the whole stationary distribution especially in the ND regime, see figure.

What is truly remarkable is the striking match during the whole transient. This feature strongly advocate for the fact the ISI distribution of the two model must be very similar, a similarity that one cannot really understand by inspecting their analytical form.

Another possibility, equally remarkable, is that to achieve this match one needs an equivalence of only the first two modes of the ISI distribution since the higher ones are not essential.

Figure 7.6: Quantitative match of firing rate dynamics. The firing rate dynamics $\nu(t)$ and stationary solution of the Fokker-Planck integration of the VIF and LIF neural population are showed for Drift (**A**) and Noise (**B**) dominated regime. The parameter of the VIF are chosen to match the stationary firing rate and c_v of the LIF as described in the text.

7.4.1 The PIF limit

When we go in the limit of $\alpha \rightarrow -\infty$ in (7.10) we recover the ISI distribution and hence the spectrum of the PIF neuron. This model was historically the first Integrate and fire

model used to fit and explain the empirical data. In this case we have that

$$\rho(s) = e^{(\theta-H)\frac{\mu-\sqrt{\mu^2+2s\sigma^2}}{\sigma^2}}$$

that implies only complex eigenvalues. This raises an apparent inconsistency with what we discussed so far since we have shown that the higher is α the more real ND eigenvalues go close to $\lambda = 0$. This behaviour is also explicit in the analytical result (7.8) however we want to remark that having a dominant real part is a necessary but not a sufficient condition to govern the relaxation dynamics. The second requirement is that the non stationary flux f_n of the mode considered has to be non-vanishing. As we show in figure (7.7), this is precisely what happen as a function of α . So in conclusion, for $\alpha \ll -1$ but finite, the dominant eigenmode will be real but due to the small flux it's effect can be neglected.

Figure 7.7: The dominant real eigenvalue **A** and associated flux **B** as a function of the reflecting barrier α here we set $\mu = \sigma^2 = 1$

7.5 Closing remarks on universality

Mean-Field models of neural population, also refereed to as neural mass models, are at the core of modern computational neuroscience. Since the seminal work of Wilson and Cowan [WC72] a great deal of work has been done in deriving these mean field description from first principles. In this context the framework of Integrate-and-Fire neurons and the related population density approach has established to be the preferred choice since in can be matched very well with experimental data despite it's relative simplicity.

If one is interested mainly in capturing the exact timing of spike emission and single neuron details the Exponential I.F. was shown to be the best choice [Bad+08]. However the non linearity of the model force the description of the mean-field dynamics to be computational [Aug+17].

In this chapter we showed that the firing rate dynamics $\nu(t)$ of two uncoupled population that are microscopically different, the VIF and the LIF neurons, can be mapped onto each other. In other words the mean field dynamics is for the greater part "universal".

We showed that the source of such universality is to be found on the general structure of the eigenvalues spectrum of the Fokker-Planck operator of the two models. a structure that is mainly dependent on the set of boundary conditions shared by both models.

We also investigated how, for any I.F. model, the ISI distribution is related to the Fokker-Planck spectrum. The universal feature of the eigenvalues is followed by a strong

similarity of the first two moment of the ISI which determine the two key element of the mean-field description, the gain function Φ and the ISI coefficient of variation c_v .

We gave particular attention to the role of the reflecting boundary condition located at α that was not well documented in the literature.

Using the ERE formalism we compared the population decay time and angular frequency to a step stimulus for both models and finally concluded that a state dependent $\alpha(\mu, \sigma)$ could be used to construct a map that relates the parameters of the LIF neuron to that of the VIF.

The optimal α can be found by imposing equivalence on the c_v and stationary rate of the two model. This can be done both in Drift and in Noise-dominated regime. In particular the stationary solutions to the Fokker-Planck equation are obviously different but the firing rate dynamics, even in the very fast transient is equivalent.

Despite the fact that eigenfunctions of the LIF are known analytically they are expressed as combination of confluent hypergeometric functions. This makes the analytical analysis difficult or even impossible except for limit cases. On a practical note instead, the derivation of the spectrum is for the same reasons challenging and requires high precision computation. This often leads to the impossibility of deriving a large number of eigenvalues often required in the context of power spectrum analysis. On the other hand, the VIF neuron is fully analytical, all the integrals involved in the analysis have closed form in term of exponentials. This not only opens the door to a better and deeper understanding of mean-field dynamics but also offer the possibility of fast and realistic simulations of large scale networks.

Thanks to mean-field universality that we studied here, we now know that this simplified model can reproduce on a quantitative level the firing rate dynamics of more complex models. For this reason we anticipate that the VIF neuron will be a powerful tool to tackle the current open problems in computational neuroscience.

7.5.1 Limitation and future work

Guided by the strong similarity of the spectrum we investigated here the universality of the mean field dynamics of uncoupled neural population. Real cortical columns are neither uncoupled nor infinite.

So a natural question arise: can we extend this results to overcome this limitation? In the framework of the ERE this amounts to ask whether or not the coupling coefficients:

$$C_{nm} = \langle \partial_\nu \psi_n | \phi_m \rangle$$

are qualitatively similar for different IF models. In a preliminary study we saw that this seems to be the case. The coupling coefficient have a major role in composing the transfer function that appear in the power spectrum analysis, see Chapter 3. A quick comparison transfer functions of the two model studied here seems to hint in the same direction.

Moreover including more details in the models such as a synaptic delay distribution [MG03] and spike frequency adaptation [GMD07] might even reduce the importance of single neuron details in the firing rate for power spectrum in favor of a more general structure.

All this observation and question will be analyzed in future work to test the true limit of the universal behavior that we reported here.

Regarding the finite-size limitation we can already say something. The Fokker-Planck equation can be extend to include finite size fluctuation, we already discuss in Chapter 4,

that even in strongly non linear (and coupled) regime the power spectrum of the population rate obtained in detailed simulation can be very well captured using a self consistent noise whose power spectrum can be derived analytically for any IF model in Chapter 4. In particular it is fully determined by $\rho(s)$ i.e. the Laplace transform of the ISI. Since we have showed that the ISI distribution of the two models overlap then same can be said for the finite size fluctuations.

Chapter 8

Degeneracy of mean-field neural dynamics

I remember my old friend Johnny von Neumann used to say, with four parameters I can fit an elephant, and with five I can make him wiggle his trunk

Enrico Fermi

Experimental data in neuroscience is often related to a limited number of degrees of freedom. This common lack of information severely limits the identification of generative models due to degeneracy in parameter space. In this work we study this degeneracy for two mean-field model of cortical activity dynamics, when only partial information is used in the optimization process. We found a degenerate manifold where the set of parameters are highly heterogeneous but the dynamics of the excitatory firing rate is the same. Surprisingly the degeneracy is non-local in the parameters space. All the solutions found generate identical bifurcation diagrams in the fatigue-excitability plane. The source of this degeneracy is identified both in the inhibitory activity and the adaption current, essential characteristics of standard neural mass models. Finally we demonstrate how it is possible to break the degeneracy using internal fluctuations or strong external stimulation

8.1 Introducing the problem

Cortical columns are thought to be computational building block of the neural cortex [Mou97]. The collective activity of cortical circuits, i.e. network of cortical columns, is responsible for most high level computation in the brain [Wan10]. For this reason much effort has been made to capture and understand the dynamics of population of interacting neurons with the hope of bridging neural computation with neural activity. Moreover, detailed knowledge of such dynamics could also suggest innovative approaches to probe the intact brain at work.

A first step in understanding the physical properties of cortical columns is to model them as homogeneous network of spiking neurons [Ger+14] as we have done throughout the thesis. These systems can be studied using neural density approaches [Kni72], a particular declination of mean-field theories [AB97]. Neural mass models have established as an essential tools of computational neuroscience especially to address multi-scale dynamical phenomena [Dec+08]. The reason behind the popularity of similar approaches is mainly the enormous dimensional reduction, characteristic of any mean-field theory.

However, despite the low number of degrees of freedom, see Chapter 5, even the simplest neural population model depends on a relatively large number of parameters Θ .

The stationary solutions [Bru00] and the dynamic response [Fou+03] of neural populations as a function of the parameters has been thoughtfully studied in the years leading to many important results. One worth mentioning is the principle of the balanced state in excitatory-inhibitory network [VS96] which has found experimental validation [Hai+06] and been proposed multiple times as a general operational principle of the neural cortex [Hai+06]. Much less has been said about the dual problem of finding the parameters Θ that give rise to a specific solution, or pattern of activity, even though, parameters inference is important as much as model building in order to bridge theory and experimental data.

In this chapter we address one specific and central issue that arises in this context which is commonly referred to as degeneracy. With degeneracy of the solutions we mean that multiple, profoundly different, set of parameters can be found that have all comparable fit quality. This phenomena is quite common for general dynamical system, especially when one has only access to limited information. In presence of degeneracy the dynamical system is said to be unidentifiable [Led+22]. In the context of neuroscience this issue has been recognized at different scale both in experimental and theoretical settings. Variability in the parameters space is often found to be compensated dynamically, [MG06] in a non-linear fashion by complex mechanism of homeostasis. For example in [PBM04] the authors show, for a 3 neuron network, how disparate circuit parameters can generate analogous activity. These mechanisms of dynamics compensation [ROG16] are strongly related to the resilience typical of biological systems. In fact degeneracy in parameters space is a convenient solution to unrealistic fine-tuning and for this reason alone it is crucial to understand its origin. Another important question is to investigate which kind of data or experimental protocol is more prone to highlights this degeneracy. In the models studied here all the parameters are related to structural properties of either single neuron dynamics, such as membrane decay time, or network features, as the average number of synaptic contacts per neuron. A degenerate manifold of parameters that explain a given emergent property then, can make interpretation and explanation much harder. This problem is particularly relevant also at the highest scale of whole-brain modeling [Wis+22]. Surprisingly, while some effort has been made regarding model identification at the level of neural population [LSM11] much less can be found about the degenerate manifold of mean-field theories of neural population dynamics. Due to the great importance of neural density approaches in neuroscience, we decided here to analyze this concept. I found that neural population dynamics is highly degenerate when the inhibition sources are not known and I will identify its origin. Moreover I discovered that it is possible to solve the degeneracy using either internal fluctuation beyond mean-field theories such as finite-size effects or by strong and specific external simulations.

The outline of the chapter is as follow. We first briefly introduce the mean-field model of a cortical module explaining the set of parameters we want to infer and what information we will use as target defining a loss function. In the second section we apply a genetic algorithm to find solutions in the parameters space using an identical model as the target one and analyzing the degenerate manifold of solutions. In the third section we do the same but trying to fit the target dynamics using a lower dimensional model. The origin of degeneracy in this model is then identified and explained. Finally in the last section we compare the non-linear response of the system for some of the solution found to address the generative power of mean-field models, proposing a possible way to reduce the degeneracy using strong external stimulation.

Figure 8.1: Figure A is a schematic representation of the cortical circuit model used in this chapter where each population is a node and each synaptic connection is an edge. Figure B is the bifurcation diagram in the strength of adaptation g and external firing rate ν_{ext} . On the right the traces of excitatory firing rate in three different dynamical phases.

So far we have discussed neural mass models for single population. If we now consider a network of populations each one will evolve according to its own Fokker-Planck (2.15) and the interactions are transmitted only through the activities ν_α where the suffix indicates the population. More precisely the synaptic current mean and variance are given by:

$$\begin{aligned}\mu_\alpha(\vec{\nu}, \vec{c}) &= \sum_{\beta} K_{\alpha\beta} J_{\alpha\beta} \nu_\beta + \mu_{x\alpha} - g_\alpha c_\alpha \\ \sigma_\alpha^2(\vec{\nu}) &= \sum_{\beta} K_{\alpha\beta} J_{\alpha\beta}^2 \nu_\beta + \sigma_{x\alpha}^2\end{aligned}\quad (8.1)$$

here we introduce also a constant component of current that comes from external environment μ_x, σ_x^2 and the adaptation variables c_α . A fatigue mechanism [GMD07] is implemented through Spike-frequency adaptation (SFA) and we can think to c as the average concentration of Ca ions inside the neurons membrane. SFA implies that the adaptation variables dynamics is:

$$\dot{c}_\alpha = -\frac{c_\alpha}{\tau_C} + \nu_\alpha$$

The simplest canonical cortical circuit is typically made of two interacting population, an excitatory and an inhibitory one. The inter- and intra- connections are controlled by the average synaptic weights $J_{\alpha\beta}$ in eq. (8.1) which gives the strength of the coupling from population β to population α , see Figure 8.1 A for a schematic representation. These systems are capable to express a rich dynamical repertoire [MS12] analogous to what has been observed both in-vivo and in-vitro, in particular we can distinguish both oscillatory behaviour and multistability at the population level. The bifurcation diagram varying the

Figure 8.2: Solution to the optimization problem. The figure shows the distributions of parameters related to mean **A** and variance **B** of the excitatory synaptic current in the EI model. As discussed in the text all solutions have a loss $L(\Theta) < 0.1$. The adaptation strength is fixed to the target value $g = 50$ [mV/s] and $\tau_c = 0.15$ [s].

strength of the adaptation and external firing rate is reported in Figure 8.1 **B**. Once again the question we pose here is: given the population firing rates in time $v_\alpha(t)$, can we recover the set of parameters Θ that collects all the parameters in equation (8.1)?

A feature typical of any experimental setting is the access to only a limited number of degree of freedom. In particular, electrophysiological measurements like MUA gives us a proxy for the firing rate of the neurons under the electrodes. In a way then we can interpret MUA as a population firing rate. However this average will be composed mostly by excitatory neurons activity due to their relative higher number with respect to inhibitory ones. For this reason we decide in this study to use only excitatory firing rate information to obtain the parameters in Eq. 8.1. The ideal result would be to find the parameters such that the firing rate not only reproduce the target for a given dynamical regime but that the whole bifurcation diagram is reproduced. For this reason we will define the loss function as follows:

$$L(\Theta) = \sum_k \int (v_{E,\Theta}^k(t) - v_E^{k,T}(t))^2 dt \quad (8.2)$$

Where $v_E^{k,T}(t)$ are the target excitatory firing rates for $k = 1, 2, 3$ which indicates the 3 different points in the bifurcation diagram that I chose, see Figure 8.1 **B**. So given a set of parameters Θ the network is simulated to get the $v_E^1(t)$. Then for $k = 2, 3$ the network is simulated but with a relative change in the two relevant parameters g and v_{ext} analogous to what generated the target.

8.2 Degeneracy on the Excitatory-Inhibitory model

We start by only optimizing the parameters that enters the synaptic moments 8.1 except for the strength of adaptation and its relaxation time scale that we kept equal to the the target values. In total 12 parameters are to be estimated.

If we define a success threshold to $L(\Theta < 0.1)$, about 40% of realizations reach a minimum after at least 10^3 iterations. In Figure 8.2 we report the distribution of some of the parameters in this degenerate manifold. The parameters found appears to be highly heterogeneous, see Table 8.1 for details, but despite these disparate solutions have comparable excellent fit quality. A PCA analysis reveals that 98% of the variance is explained by the first component. In other terms then, a strong correlation between the parameters exist which we believe to be related to a compensation mechanism that guarantees the same excitatory firing rate.

To investigate the origin of this degeneracy we look at top 2 solutions, Figure 8.3A (red and blue). Despite their striking difference in parameters value they bot match very well the target excitatory firing rate $v_E(t)$ (black). On the contrary, the inhibitory rate is completely different as it can also be seen inspecting the synaptic current moments dynamics (D right). Surprisingly enough this degeneracy is non-local in the Θ space. In fact both solutions are capable to reproduce the bifurcation diagram (8.3C) in the adaption-excitability plane of the target.

A general property that we found to be verified for all the solutions is that the inhibitory firing rate is almost linearly related to the excitatory rate:

$$v_I(t) \approx \alpha v_E(t) + \beta$$

The coefficient of this linear relation however depend on the particular solution, see Fig. 8.3D right. The plane (α, β) is then a good candidate to find a low dimensional representation for the degenerate manifold. If, in this plane, we color code the solutions with respect to their loss, Fig.8.3B upper, we see that the quality of the fit does not depend on the specific value of α, β . On the contrary if we use the euclidean distance between the solutions and the target Θ a clear ordering emerge, Fig.8.3B lower. More precisely, the closest solution to the target int the Θ space, coincide with the closest to the true value of (α, β) . This give us a strong indication on the origin of the degeneracy: since we have only access to excitatory activity, the inhibitory firing rate (i.e. α and β) are not completely bounded. As we show in the next section this situation can only get worse when we try to estimate also adaptation parameters.

8.3 Degeneracy and adaptation

The adaptation variable c enters the excitatory population as an inhibitory current. It is then reasonable to assume that, if we search solutions optimizing also the parameters that regulate adaptation, the degeneracy can only be worse compared to previous section. To see this consider for a moment the case of a stationary solution such that: $v_I(t) = v_I$ and $c(t) = c$. The excitatory firing rate is then a non linear function of the synaptic moments μ_E and σ_E . In particular the inhibitory component of μ_E is given by two terms: $KJ_{EI}v_I$ and $-gc$, then the specific value of total inhibitory current can be achieved in an infinite number of way by an opportune balance of this two terms. Note that this simple idea applies even for different inhibitory sources different to SFA . To confirm this intuition in a non-stationary regime we performed, as before, the optimization with multiple different initial guesses. Once again we found a large number of different solutions θ whit excellent fit to the excitatory firing rate. However in this case the we need at least five principal components to explain the variability on the degenerate manifold, see figure 8.4 A, clearly showing that the complexity of the degeneracy has increased as expected. Already in the previous session we have seen that different solutions will follow different trajectory in the plane μ, σ and we believe this to be the key to better understand and maybe solve the degeneracy.

Figure 8.3: Degeneracy EI model. **A** Two different solution (red and blue) found minimizing the Loss function defined in the text. The upper row shows the agreement with the target excitatory firing rate (black) and in the lower panel we report the inhibitory firing rate. The remarkable differences in inhibitory activity and overall parameters Θ is also visible in the dynamics of moments μ, σ in the oscillatory phase (**D** right). Despite this the bifurcation diagrams in the plane g, ν_{ext} **C** of the two solutions is identical to the target. We also found for all the solution a strong linear relation $\nu_I \approx \alpha\nu_E + \beta$ (**D** left). This values can be used to effectively visualize **B** the solution in a low dimensional plane. On the top the colorbar refer to the logarithm of the loss showing that very different solutions have similar fit performance. On the bottom map the color code indicates the log of the euclidean distance with respect to the true Θ .

Table 8.1: Summary statics for the degenerate solution of different models. EI 1 indicates the Excitatory-Inhibitory population but with adaption parameters fixed to the target value while in EI 2 they are included in the optimization process.

Parameters	EI 1			EI 2			E		
	Mean	Std.	CV	Mean	Std.	CV	Mean	Std.	CV
KJ_{EE} [mV]	88.62	40.21	0.45	71.82	30.99	0.43	0.31	0.08	0.25
KJ_{EI} [mV]	-85.09	49.79	-0.59	-99.39	59.4	-0.6	-	-	-
KJ_{IE} [mV]	97.72	57.19	0.59	60.79	33.12	0.54	-	-	-
KJ_{II} [mV]	-71.41	21.35	-0.3	-62.86	21.1	-0.34	-	-	-
KJ_{EE}^2 [mV ²]	91.04	57.92	0.64	162.48	108.51	0.67	188.53	1.84	0.01
KJ_{EI}^2 [mV ²]	137.77	94.7	0.69	179.9	124.14	0.69	-	-	-
KJ_{IE}^2 [mV ²]	165.93	110.3	0.66	94.31	81.63	0.87	-	-	-
KJ_{II}^2 [mV ²]	59.09	55.17	0.93	88.0	75.63	0.86	-	-	-
μ_{xE} [mV/s]	1033.64	300.33	0.29	978.97	208.98	0.21	660.12	1.12	0.001
σ_{xE}^2 [mV ² /s]	409.16	311.65	0.76	425.94	419.57	0.99	446.60	2.23	0.005
μ_{xI} [mV/s]	1053.55	483.53	0.46	1031.98	292.44	0.28	-	-	-
σ_{xI}^2 [mV ² /s]	7871.38	3319.86	0.42	6059.7	2359.48	0.39	-	-	-
g [mV/s]	50.0	-	-	56.57	7.51	0.13	61.82	0.40	0.006
τ_C [s]	0.15	-	-	0.15	0.003	0.02	0.132	0.001	0.006

A major role in the discussion is given to the moments of the single neurons Inter-Spike-Interval distribution or ISI. For example, the stationary solution to the coupled Fokker-Planck equations, see F.1, are given by the gain function:

$$\nu = \Phi(\mu, \sigma)$$

where $\Phi = \frac{1}{\langle T \rangle}$ whit $\langle T \rangle$ the mean ISI. Even though the time dependent firing rate $\nu(t)$ is only partially related to $\Phi(\mu(t), \sigma(t))$, the Gain function explain how it is possible to obtain the same activity whit highly different trajectories in the (μ, σ) plain. On a side note we mention that also the transient population dynamics is actually strongly dependent on the ISI distribution as we have showed in previous chapters. On Figure 8.4C the trajectories, in the (μ, σ) plane, of different solutions during the oscillatory phase are reported. We also plotted the contour lines of $\Phi(\mu, \sigma)$ and of the ISI coefficient of variation, $c_v(\mu, \sigma)$. As it can be seen despite the different shape all the trajectory are in a bounded region of the plane that are delimited by the contour levels of Φ corresponding to the minimum and maximum firing rate observed in the oscillatory phase, this clearly proves that the compensation mechanisms for different parameters are to be searched in the gain function transformation of the synaptic current. However quite surprisingly we cannot really say the same for the range of c_v explored by the different solutions which varies widely. A question that easily arise is then if it is possible to use this heterogeneity to disambiguate the otherwise analogous solutions. The main problem in doing so is that currently there is no dynamic mean-field theory that makes prediction about the population c_v and how it relates to the single-neuron one.

A possible way is to use this information is offered by finite-size fluctuation. In Chapter 4, we extend the mean-field theory used here to include finite-size effects that make the mean field firing rate stochastic. Specifically the firing rate of finite population of N neurons is given by:

$$\nu_N(t) = \nu(t) + \eta(t)$$

where ν is the mean-field rate and η is the finite size noise. It is possible to derive the general formula, valid for any IF neural network, for the power spectrum of the noise η

which turns out to depend on the Fourier transform of single neuron ISI. For example we have seen that the limit of zero frequency of the η spectrum is:

$$|\eta(\omega = 0)|^2 = \frac{\Phi}{N} \frac{4c_v^2}{(1 + c_v^2)^2}$$

The finite-size power spectrum for the different solutions in the High state, cyan square in Fig. 8.1 B, is shown in Figure 8.4 D where we can see the impact of the heterogeneity of the c_v . Power spectra like $|\eta(\omega)|^2$ can be well approximated through markovian embedding with one-dimensional colored noise like an Ornstein–Uhlenbeck process [VL19]. The correlation time of this noise will clearly depend on μ and σ through the single neuron Φ and on the c_v . In principle then if we take the ensemble of degenerate solutions to their bi-stable state, red region in the bifurcation diagram, and include the finite size fluctuation, the systems will naturally jump between the two states with a time statistics which will not be degenerate. It is in fact well known that noise correlation has a strong impact in stochastic induced transition [HTB90]. Whether or not this strategy is practically feasible, it is interesting to note that, thanks to their state-dependent nature, finite-size fluctuations of the firing rate can help disambiguate what is degenerate for the standard-mean field theory ($N \rightarrow \infty$), without adding extra information about inhibitory neurons. Anticipating what we will discuss in the last section, it is important to highlight that fluctuations, which in this case are endogenous, seem capable to accentuate differences in the degenerate manifold.

8.4 Degeneracy in the Excitatory model

To better understand the origin of the degeneracy of previous section here we will use 1 population model of only excitatory neurons (E model hereafter). The intuition behind this are mainly two. First the bifurcation diagram in Fig. 8.3 was originally derived for the 1 population case [GMD07] and does not show significant differences with respect to the one in Figure 8.3. Secondly, in the previous section we found that despite the degeneracy of the solutions, the inhibitory firing rate was linearly related to the excitatory one in a linear fashion even in the global oscillation phase ($\nu_I(t) \approx \alpha \nu_E(t) + \beta$). This clearly suggests that a dimensional reduction should be feasible. Most importantly to the scope of this work, we are interested to see if the degeneracy found in the EI model, which we believe to be related to the absence of information about inhibitory neurons, persists even when there is only one kind of population.

Applying the same optimization procedure discussed above to the E model, we found that, despite the number of parameters is halved, degeneracy is still present. However, the coefficient of variation of all the parameters except for KJ is lower than 0.01 indicating an overall low variability in the degenerate manifold. To be more precise large relative variation of KJ , can be compensated by small relative variation of the other parameters. In Figure 8.5 D the trajectories in the (μ, σ) of three different solutions are reported. Despite being much smaller than in the EI model, there are once again differences. On the contrary the trajectories in the phase plane (c, ν) are identical. To achieve this the null-clines, which are the back-bone of the force-field, of the different dynamical system must be the same. We demonstrated that the dimension of the dynamic mean-field theory can be greatly reduced as shown in Chapter 5. In a sub-threshold regime (i.e. $\mu\tau < \theta$) the firing rate dynamics if given, approximately, by the dynamical system:

Figure 8.4: Degeneracy and adaptation. Including in the optimization also the parameters of the adaptation τ_C , g leads to an increase of variance in the set of solution found **A-B**. Figure **C** shows the contour line of $\Phi(\mu, \sigma)$, red, and $c_v(\mu, \sigma)$ in blue. In grey we reported the trajectory of different solutions during the oscillatory phase. Using the same color code, figure **D** shows the finite-size noise power spectrum in the up state of the bi-stable of different solutions.

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{v} &= \frac{\Phi(v, c) - v}{\tau(v)} \\ \dot{c} &= -\frac{c}{\tau_c} + v\end{aligned}\tag{8.3}$$

We can use 8.3 to test our hypothesis on the null-clines. Since the variability of τ_c is very low the c null-cline, $c = \tau_c v$, is clearly the same for all the solutions. On the other hand, $\tau(v)$ is a monotonic function so the v null-cline is defined as the solution to the non-linear equation:

$$v(c) = \Phi(\mu(v(c)), \sigma(v(c))), \Theta\tag{8.4}$$

For the LIF the gain function has an integral form [RS79] given in Chapter 3.

In Figure 8.5D, we report the numerical solution of $v(c)$ showing that also the second null cline is indeed the same for different solutions Θ . It is actually possible to formally derive the set of equations that define the degenerate manifold from the equivalence of null cline. First derive the formal Taylor expansion of the gain function:

$$\Phi(\mu, \sigma) \sum_{i,j} \alpha_{ij} \mu^i \sigma^j$$

and perform a non-linear fit to estimate:

$$v_c \approx \sum_k \beta_k c^k$$

Using the definition of the moments we can use the polynomial expression of Φ to write down a polynomial expression in v, c which is equivalent to the null-cline definition:

$$v_c = P(v_c, c)$$

Finally plugging in v_c we arrive at polynomial equation:

$$Q(c) = P(v_c = \sum_k \beta_k c^k, c) - \sum_k \beta_k c^k = \sum_k \gamma_k(\Theta, \alpha, \beta) c^k = 0$$

Thanks to the theorem of equivalent polynomials, we know that this expression is satisfied for any value of c only if all the coefficients are null. This simple derivation demonstrates that a universal trajectory of the phase space $v(c)$ can be achieved by any set of parameters Θ that satisfies the set of non-linear equations:

$$\gamma_k(\Theta, \alpha, \beta) = 0\tag{8.5}$$

for $k = 1, \dots, Deg(Q(c))$. We note that generally $Deg(Q) > Dim(\Theta)$ hence the system is in principle over determined. If we call M the number of equation that are left once the redundant one are removed, the dimension of the degeneracy manifold is simply $M - Dim(\Theta)$. Equations 8.5 defines the level sets of parameters that reproduce the features imposed by the loss function. As discussed above, a change in a given subset of parameters can be compensated, potentially in a non-linear way, by changing accordingly the rest of them, following the level set equations. We also mention that similar derivation could be applied to the EI model as well. In this case we have also a third nulclines for the inhibitory rate but as a first approximation the concept of effective gain function, introduced in [MA99], where the inhibitory activity is effectively taken into account with a proper $\Phi_{eff}(v_E)$ and the same calculation of above can be repeated.

Figure 8.5: Degeneracy of excitatory model. Figure A shows the histograms of 24 solutions found via optimization using the excitatory model. In B we report the firing rate activity of two such solution in red and blue, matched with the target in black. The dynamic response at low frequency is highly correlated with the parameter KJ as we report in C. For three solutions in different colors (red, blue and green) we plot the mean and standard deviation of the synaptic current (D left) in the global oscillation phase showing significant differences. These differences are not visible if we look instead at the trajectory in the phase plane of the firing rate ν and adaptation c (D mid) which is the same for all the solution. The same universality holds also in the stationary condition as showed in D right by comparing the solutions of $\nu(c) = \Phi(\nu(c), c, \Theta)$.

Differently from what we found for the EI model the dispersion of parameters in the E model is rather small except for the excitability of the population i.e. KJ . that varies as much as 50%. From a prospective of model inference then, the E model is "practically" identifiable if we could found a good estimation of KJ . From linear response theory, see Chapter 3, we know that the response function at low frequency to an external sinusoidal stimulation depends on the derivative of the gain function and hence on the excitability of the system:

$$H_\mu(\omega \sim 0) = \partial_\mu \Phi = \partial_\nu \mu \partial_\nu \Phi \sim KJ$$

which we could use to discern the value of KJ . We tested this hypothesis estimating numerically, from the E model Fokker-Planck, the transfer function for a modulation of μ . In Figure 8.5C we show the strong correlation between KJ and $H_\mu(\omega \sim 0)$. This simple consideration demonstrates that to overcome parameter degeneracy without adding information of other degree of freedom external perturbation could be used, as we will investigate in the last section. We also note that from the prospective of model identification the simplified E model is not only capable to overcome the degeneracy of the EI model but it is quite accurate in the fit of excitatory firing rate. Moreover the model is generative: the bifurcation diagram in the plane adaptation-excitability of the solutions found is practically the same of the original target system, see Figure 8.5 B,C.

8.5 Non-linear response to solve degeneracy

In the previous section we have seen that the degeneracy of the solution is tightly related to the degeneracy of null-clines with respect to parameters Θ . However two dynamical systems with identical null-clines might still differ if we look at the flux far from them. In other words it is reasonable to expect that a strong external drive, which will force the system to visit region of the phase space distant from the null-clines, might be able to accentuate differences in the degenerate manifold. We start by selecting the best M solution of both kind of model studied so far. Then we implement to the system a sinusoidal external current that is added to mean synaptic current of the excitatory population: $I(t) = \alpha \mu_{x,E} \sin(\omega t)$. We then measured the vector of loss function \vec{L} , composed of the loss of the M different degenerate solution, varying both the strength, α , and the frequency, ω , of the stimulation. To measure the degree to which the degeneracy of the solutions persists even with external stimulation, we introduce the dissimilarity index:

$$\gamma(\alpha, \omega) = \frac{std(\vec{L})}{\sqrt{M}} \quad (8.6)$$

Degeneracy then implies very low dissimilarity, and we already know that $\gamma(\alpha = 0, \omega) \sim 0$.

The contour plots of Figure 8.6 A show the value of $\gamma(\alpha, \omega)$ for both models studied here. Surprisingly we found that for a large portion of the plane (α, ω) , degeneracy persists. In fact the degenerate dynamical systems will respond equally to external stimulation that are either fast or weak. That been said, great differences appear for very slow stimuli even if the strength α is small. Figure 8.6 B shows, for the EI model, the loss as a function of α and ω , for the solutions with minimal and maximal average loss, \bar{L} , in the plane. The plots clearly show that, among the degenerate solution found without external stimuli, there are some that are much closer to the target in terms of non-linear response, hence external stimulation seems capable to disambiguate degeneracy. To prove this we repeated the optimization process including an external current with amplitude 0.007 frequency of 7 Hz. As initial condition we used the top 20 solutions obtained in the $\alpha = 0$ case. Due to the stochastic nature of the algorithm of these 20 solution only 12 reached lower level of loss

function with respect to the initial condition. The results are shown in Figure 8.6 C, where the euclidean distance between the vectors of parameter and the target Θ is plotted as a function of the stimulus dependent loss $L(\alpha, f)$. The colors of the scatter plots indicate the ranking of the solutions with respect of the loss before the optimization. The difference in ordering reflects the fact that a stimulus dependent minimization is actively changing the ranking. The most important result however is that the stimulus is responsible of a profound reshaping of the energy landscape explored during optimization. In fact before the optimization degeneracy implied that solutions highly distant from the target in the parameter space can have very low level of loss. In fact the Pearson correlation between loss and parameter distance is very low (0.1). On the other hand after the stimulus-dependant optimization a strong correlation between loss and parameter distance emerges. In other terms it seems that external stimulation simplifies greatly the energy landscape reducing it to a mostly unique paraboloid since low loss correspond to solutions close to the target. The Pearson correlation in this case (if we exclude the 3 solutions with $L > 0.027$) is very high (0.95).

As it was the case with endogenous fluctuations, these results clearly show that external stimulation can be used effectively to reduce, and maybe even remove, the degeneracy found for closed, i.e. without external current, mean-field models of cortical columns dynamics.

8.6 Conclusions

In this chapter we studied the degeneracy of mean-field models of a canonical microcircuit of spiking neural network. Degeneracy implies that a given set of features of the observed data can be reproduced by models with highly different parameters, [Tra+15]. As it has been argued in [EG01] it often comes alongside with complexity. Moreover, studying the origin and the characteristics of the degenerate manifold is equivalent to search for an effective low-dimensional theory of the phenomena of interest [Mac+13]. In particular degeneracy is an hallmark of biological systems and it is believed to be related to their robustness and resilience to variations of different kinds and, at the same time, their capabilities to express context dependent behaviour [EG01].

In neuroscience degeneracy has been studied mainly at the scale of single neurons or entire brain areas, here we focus on the populations level. We chose as target of the fitting process the time series of the population excitatory firing rate in three different dynamical regime and treat the inhibitory firing rate as an hidden variable in order to be closer to typical experimental data. We found that this incomplete knowledge results in highly degenerate manifold of parameters. The models in the degenerate manifold all reproduce exactly the excitatory rate dynamics but strongly differ in the inhibitory rate.

Another surprising feature of the degenerate models is their non-locality in some parameters: a proportional change in the parameters of the models and the target will still result in a good fit. In fact degenerate models present essentially the same bifurcation diagrams. As for the effective dimension of the degenerate manifold it turned out to be approximately 2. This fact is in accordance with further observation that for all solutions the inhibitory firing rate is approximately a liner function of the excitatory rate i.e. $v_I(t) = \alpha v_E(t) + \beta$ and the two parameters α and β can be used as a low dimensional parameterization of the manifold. This clearly shows that the dynamics is mostly determined by the a specific balance of inhibition and excitation which is in turn a

Figure 8.6: Non-Linear response and degeneracy. **A** In the color-map we report the log of the dissimilarity index we introduced in the main text for the Exc (left) and Exc.-Inh model (Inh). The Loss functions needed for γ are computed introducing in the integration an extra external synaptic current $I(t) = \alpha \mu_x \sin(2\pi ft)$ to the excitatory population. In both cases we can see that a stimulation either too weak (low α) or too fast (high f) is not capable to disambiguate substantially the degenerate solutions. We can rank the degenerate solution with respect to mean loss \bar{L} in the plane (α, f) . Figure **B** clearly shows that despite the degeneracy found for no-stimulus case ($\alpha = 0$) some solutions are much better than others in the stimulated case. In figure **C** we repeated the optimization using as initial condition the top 20 degenerate solution ($\alpha = 0$) choosing $\alpha = 0.007$ and $f = 7$. On the left we plotted the normalized euclidean distance of the parameter vectors with respect to the target Θ as a function of the loss $L(\alpha, f)$ before the optimization. Degeneracy implies that no correlation between the two can be found. On the other hand after the stimulus dependent optimization (right panel) a strong correlation emerges. Moreover the color of the points indicate the ranking with respect of the Loss before of the optimization. Optimizing using external stimulus does change the ranking of the previous optimization.

function of all the parameters. When we include in the parameters to fit also the strength and time scale of spike-frequency adaptation the dimensionality of degenerate manifold further increases. This has however a similar explanation since adaptation is effectively just another source of inhibition. Guided by this intuition we repeat the optimization process using an effective model of a single population with both self inhibition and excitation. As expected this strongly decreases the dimension of the degenerate manifold and the dispersion of each parameter in general. There is however yet another possibility to solve degeneracy. Using results of Chapter 4 on the extensions of the mean-field theory we use here, we discovered surprisingly that, while the mean-field solutions are degenerate, the endogenous fluctuation, due to finite-size effects, around it are not. In other words finite-size fluctuations potentially carry a lot of information. A similar reasoning can then be applied to the case of controlled external stimulation. To prove this we set-up the same optimization process but we include a known external sinusoidal input. We found however that the response of the degenerate models is as well highly degenerate. It is however possible to choose specific amplitude and frequency of stimulation that majorly amplify subtle differences in the ensemble of models. Generally the stimulation has to be neither too weak or too fast meaning that linear-response is not enough but, a proper choice of external protocol can indeed break degeneracy leading to unique solutions. Fitting the parameters of a model to experimental data is an essential step in Science but with complex systems degeneracy can complicate a lot the process. We believe that our results consist in a significant step in two different directions. On one hand we discovered and explained degeneracy in mean-field models that are commonly used in computational neuroscience. Degeneracy can be seen as a feature and our results can be potentially used for further theoretical understanding of cortical column dynamics. On the other hand however model identification is a practical and unavoidable problem and in this regard any insight on how to solve it is useful.

Chapter 9

Conclusions

There is a theory which states that if ever anyone discovers exactly what the Universe is for and why it is here, it will instantly disappear and be replaced by something even more bizarre and inexplicable.

There is another theory which states that this has already happened.

Douglas Adams

In this thesis, I laid out the foundations and expanded on some crucial details of a general theory of neural population dynamics. We started at the scale of the single neuron and with a bottom-up first-principle approach derived the emergent dynamics of an interacting population.

The general idea of a population density approach [[Kni72](#)], or in the Physics jargon the mean-field theory, is one of the main pillars of computational and theoretical neuroscience [[Ger+14](#)]. It is now clear that neurons perform computation at a network level, hence a detailed understanding of the physics expressed by these complex systems is essential to fully capture the information processing of neuronal systems.

All neurons are different and, intrinsically, out of equilibrium non-linear units. For these reasons a hydrodynamic approach to describe mesoscopically averaged degrees of freedom is substantially more difficult with respect to main-stream statistical physics. Numerous shots at synthesis have been made in the years but the general theory of neural population dynamics is still in its infancy. This thesis and the original results in it are an attempt to address three major open questions, the solution of which would greatly contribute to the maturation of said theory: low dimensionality, universality and finite-size effects.

By finite-size effects, I mean the unavoidable fact that real neural populations are not composed of infinitely many neurons, quite on the contrary cortical columns are made of $10^2 - 10^3$ neurons [[Mou97](#)]. This is clearly at odds with the main assumption of a typical mean-field theory which requires infinite size or volume. As it is well known a finite system will generate mesoscopic quantities that fluctuate around the mean-field value. Those fluctuations can be easily understood in linear regimes applying fluctuation-dissipation approaches, and in those regimes, they do not really add neither modify much the mean-field predictions. When dealing with the non-linear system, however, one must be careful. The combination of non-linearities and fluctuations can give rise to

noise-induced phenomena, such as stochastic resonance [BSV81], that can be an essential component in the behavior of the system and might even be used to process information. Here lies the first serious obstacle in our path since a general prescription, that is valid in all possible regimes, to include finite-size fluctuations and extend the mean-field description of spiking neural network is still lacking. I presented in Chapter 4 an approach that can be applied, in principle, to a very broad set of mean-field theories for spiking neurons. Most importantly we derived analytically the correlation function of the noise term η that added to the mean-field firing rate fully captures the finite-size activity of the network $v_N(t) = v(t) + \eta(t)$. Since the derivation is from the first principle we uncovered how single neuron details shape the finite-size fluctuations.

We found that the correlation structure of finite-size fluctuations is state-dependent, hence it changes dynamically. Our theory is self-consistent and can be applied even in non-linear regimes. For example, we applied it to study noise induce synchronization that happens close to a bifurcation and found a quantitative match with detailed simulations. I expect those results to be essential in the study of meta-stable dynamics, commonly observed in experiments [Bri+22], where the transition between states is the direct consequence of the finite size of the networks.

By low dimensionality, I refer to the common approach of statistical physics to recover, hopefully from first principles, the dynamical laws that govern mesoscopic quantities that are usually moments of the population density. The laws for the evolution of order parameters, think for example to thermodynamics, live usually in a much lower dimension than the number of microscopic degrees of freedom. Surprisingly a similar view applies also to neuronal dynamics as I show in Chapter 5. We found that a dynamical system for the population firing rate can be worked out by applying a separation of time scales argument. Doing so we found not only an effective low-dimensional representation that captures on a quantitative level the full mean-field dynamics but also several new interesting phenomena such as state-dependent population decay time and angular frequency. While several works have tried and succeeded to reduce the dimensionality by imposing certain ansatz for the population density, these same ansatzs limit the general applicability of the effective theory. On the contrary, our approach is one of the few that remains valid in all possible regimes even in non-equilibrium non-linear ones.

By universality I mean, to what extent does the emergent population dynamics depends on single neuron feature? What are the truly essential characteristics of an abstract neuron one must consider in order to obtain a consistent mesoscopic theory?

In Physics universality has a deep meaning. The revolution of the renormalization group [Set21] has unveiled that systems in critical regimes belong to universality classes, i.e. despite strong differences at the microscopic level they behave identically at the macroscopic level close to a the critical state. In Biology, where everything is heterogeneous and structured, a universal theory seems at first a chimera. However, when fitting high-dimensional models to complex systems, ranging from ecology to protein interaction networks, one consistently finds degeneracy in the parameter space. A system is degenerate, with respect to some features, if it can reproduce the expected behavior with a wide variability of parameters. It can be demonstrated [Qui+22] that effective theories, which are simplified and somewhat universal, are tightly related to degeneracy in the parameter space thus explaining why effective models can be applied over and over in very different contexts.

Going back to neuroscience, in the literature one can find a jungle of single neuron models that span different levels of detail and consequently the number of parameters. This is true also at the network and brain areas levels, in fact a lot of fundamental circuits

related to most of the cognitive functions have been identified and studied in the years. Nonetheless, the emergent population dynamics seem rather universal on a qualitative level. For this reason, in Chapter 7 we study the origin of this universal behavior by comparing the population dynamics of two very different Integrate-and-Fire neurons. More precisely the two models share the same boundary conditions, which implement for example the spike-reset mechanism, but have very different membrane potential dynamics. Despite the profound differences it is possible to map the firing rate of one population to the other on a quantitative level. The source of this universality is found to be on the general mathematical formulation of the continuity equations that govern the evolution in time of the population density and, more specifically, on the equivalence of the eigenvalues of the operators governing the continuity equations.

As for the parameter space, mean-field models of neural activity appear highly degenerate. In Chapter 8 we investigate this interesting issue by trying to find the parameters that reproduce optimally the dynamical traces of excitatory firing rate in three different dynamical phases. To be closer to typical experimental data, however, we did not give to the optimization process any information about the inhibitory activity. We found a highly degenerate manifold of models that reproduce equally well the target activities despite having large dispersion on the parameters. Surprisingly we found that while the mean-field dynamics are degenerate the fluctuations around it are not. In other terms, finite-size noise might be used to extract information and help reduce degeneracy. In the same spirit, external stimulation could in principle disambiguate different models in degenerate manifolds since they allow to explore a larger portion of the phase space. While we found this to be true, in general, the stimulation should be neither too weak nor too fast. In other words, the degeneracy persists even in the linear dynamic response regime.

Many questions remain open. From a theoretical point of view, it is known for example, that when neurons in the network interact substantially in a pairwise fashion mean-field theory must be revised. This does not necessarily imply that we have to start over, in fact the way we treated finite-sized fluctuation should be general enough to take into account, at least partially, correlations.

While we have made numerous predictions about the behaviour of neuronal populations, all these new effects need to be proved experimentally. Thankfully, neuroscience is now embracing a golden era for what is experimentally accessible. Experiments where thousands of neurons are recorded simultaneously in-vivo are more and more frequent. But it is precisely when we have access to massive data that a working theory is needed the most. Another obvious step ahead is to explore the largest scale and investigate brain wide networks. If a parcellization in terms of cortical columns, i.e. the neuronal population studied here, is possible we could use what we have found as a starting point to build a field theory of extended cortical tissues which opens the doors to a plethora of new phenomena [Bre11; SSS13] like propagation of waves of neural activity. In this regard the role of heterogeneity, commonly observed between different brain areas, cannot be neglected and could be central. Another question that we never addressed here, but it is of huge importance also in other domain of Science, is how to distinguish the environment contribution from the system behaviour. A clear distinction between inside and outside, like is done in thermodynamics, is never simple with complex system but nevertheless is essential to fully understand neural information processing. Finally a key aspect of neural systems which we never address here are their fascinating capabilities to learn and memorize. Learning in particular naturally pushes outside equilibrium neural networks complicating greatly the theoretical description of such process.

While much work is still needed to fully consolidate the view that a universal theory of neural population dynamics is now in our hands, the results here presented are a significant step in the direction of simplicity and elegance. Traditionally, Biology has been the opposite of Physics regarding reductionism. The overwhelming number of detailed mechanisms found at the single cell level confuse the general picture and discourage theoretical efforts. However one must not forget that the first job of neurons is not to think but to survive. In order to do so massive and intricate metabolic network are used by all the neurons in the brain. In this context redundancy, heterogeneity and complexity strongly hinder any simplification effort. On the other hand if we are interested only in neural information processing, the general program I presented in this thesis becomes much more credible even if we started from the simplest possible model of neurons. The generality of the results here presented should not be taken for granted and it is, in my opinion, another strong hint toward a universal theory of neuronal dynamics.

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Appendix A

A Rosetta stone

Derivation of Eq. (3.36)

To derive the formula for the perturbation of the density $p_1(x_t)$ we need first to find the following coefficients a , b and d :

$$p_1(x) = \begin{cases} a f_1(x) + b f_2(x) + Q(x) & x_r < x < x_t \\ d f_2(x) + Q(x) & x < x_r \end{cases}.$$

They can be evaluated by taking into account the boundary conditions of the Fokker-Planck equation:

$$\begin{aligned} a f_1(x_t) + b f_2(x_t) &= -Q(x_t) \\ a [f_1'(x_t) - f_1'(x_r)] + \\ b [f_2'(x_t) - f_2'(x_r)] + d f_2'(x_r) &= \Delta Q'(x_r) - Q'(x_t) \\ a f_1(x_r) + b f_2(x_r) - d f_2(x_r) &= -\Delta Q(x_r) \end{aligned}$$

We note that the homogeneous system is equivalent to the eigenfunction problem. Indeed, the setting of the associated determinant to zero gives back the spectral equation, i.e. the boundary condition $\psi_n(x_r) = \psi_n(x_t)$, for the eigenvalues λ_n [DR17]. Solving the above system we have

$$a = \frac{Q(x_t) f_2(x_r) f_2'(x_t) - f_2(x_t) [\Delta Q(x_r) f_2'(x_r) + f_2(x_r) (Q'(x_t) - \Delta Q'(x_t))]}{W(x_t) f_2(x_r) - W(x_r) f_2(x_t)}$$

and

$$b = -\frac{f_2(x_r) [Q(x_r) (f_1'(x_r) - f_1'(x_t)) + f_1(x_t) (Q'(x_t) - \Delta Q'(x_r))]}{W(x_t) f_2(x_r) - W(x_r) f_2(x_t)} + \frac{f_2'(x_t) [\Delta Q(x_r) f_1(x_t) - Q(x_t) f_1(x_r)]}{W(x_t) f_2(x_r) - W(x_r) f_2(x_t)}$$

These coefficients determine $p_1(x)$ in the domain of interest ($x > x_r$), this is why we do not report the expression for d . Evaluating the derivative $p_1'(x_t)$ of the above density perturbation at the threshold potential eventually leads to Eq. (3.36). Regarding Eq.(3.37) we first need to prove the general form of the particular solution $Q(x)$. We are interested to second order linear O.D.E problem of the form:

$$c_2(x)Q'' + c_1(x)Q' + c_0(x)Q = F_0(x)$$

To solve this we make use of the solution of the homogeneous problem (i.e. with $F_0 = 0$) that we defined as $f_{1,2}$ and proposing the Ansatz:

$$Q(x) = A_1(x)f_1(x) + A_2(x)f_2(x)$$

further imposing the condition:

$$A'_1 f_1 + A'_2 f_2 = 0$$

Substitution in differential equation gives a second constraint:

$$A'_1 f'_1 + A'_2 f'_2 = F_0/c_2$$

The system for $A_{1,2}$ can be solved and leads to the results in the main text. Substituting $Q(x)$ in Eq. (3.36) further simplifies the expression leading to:

$$p'_1(x_t) = \frac{-A_1(x_t) + \Delta A_1(x_r)}{Z(\psi(x_t) - \psi(x_r))}$$

How in this case the $\Delta A_1(x_r)$ vanish since it is the integral:

$$\Delta A_1(x_r) = 2 \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \int_{x_r - \epsilon}^{x_r + \epsilon} f_2(y) F_0(y) dy$$

Derivation of the transfer function $H_\epsilon^{(P)}$

From Eq. (3.34) we know that the generic transfer function $H_\epsilon^{(P)}$ is proportional to $p'_1(x_t)$ given by Eq. (3.36), whose derivation has been detailed in the previous Appendix. Starting from this, here we provide the key steps needed to obtain the explicit expressions for $H_\epsilon^{(P)}$ reported in Eqs. (3.38) and (3.39) for the specific case of the standard LIF neuron model. If the input modulation involves only the mean μ , $Q_\mu(x) \propto \phi'_0(x)$. As in the main text, here we assume an implicit dependence on s . Remembering that $L_{x0}\phi_0 = \partial_x(x\phi_0) + \frac{1}{2}\partial_x^2\phi_0 = 0$ we can write

$$Q'_\mu(x) = -2x Q_\mu(x) - 2\phi_0(x) = \frac{W'(x)}{W(x)} Q_\mu(x) - 2\phi_0(x),$$

where we taken into account that from Eq. (3.32) the Wronskian for the LIF neuron reduces to the differential equation $W'(x) = -2x W(x)$. The first term of the numerator in Eq. (3.36) then reduces to

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{W_{Q,f_2}(x_t)}{W(x_t)Z} &= \frac{Q'_\mu f_2 - Q_\mu f'_2}{WZ} \Big|_{x=x_t} \\ &= -\frac{Q_\mu}{Z} \left(-\frac{W' f_2}{W^2} + \frac{f'_2}{W} \right) - 2\phi_0 \frac{f_2}{WZ} \Big|_{x=x_t} \\ &= -(Q_\mu + 2\phi_0) \psi' \Big|_{x=x_t} \\ &= -Q_\mu(x_t) \psi'(x_t) \end{aligned}$$

where we used Eq. (3.33) replacing λ_n with s and defining $Z(s) = Z_n|_{\lambda_n=s}$, and we took into account the boundary condition $\phi_0(x_t) = 0$. The same can be done with the other

term $W_{\Delta Q, f_2}(x_r)/W(x_r)Z$ by taking into account the other boundary condition about the flux conservation, $Q(x_l) = \Delta Q(x_r)$, eventually leading to rewrite Eq. (3.36) as

$$p'_1(x_l) = -Q_\mu(x_l) \frac{\psi'(x_l) - \psi'(x_r)}{\psi(x_l) - \psi(x_r)}.$$

Analogous results hold whenever the particular solution is proportional to the derivative of the stationary eigenfunction.

In the case of a changing variance σ^2 of the input current, the forcing term is $F_0(t) = \frac{\nu_1(t)}{\sigma_0^2} \phi_0''$. The particular solution is then

$$Q^\sigma(x) = K(s) \phi_0''(x) = \frac{\gamma(s)}{2(s+2)} \phi_0''(x).$$

Using the stationary equation $L_{x0} \phi_0 = 0$, we have that

$$\partial_x^3 \phi_0 = (-2x \partial_x^2 - 4 \partial_x) \phi_0 = (4x^2 - 4) \phi_0'.$$

By making use of these expressions in Eq. (3.36), we eventually obtain for the first term of the numerator

$$\frac{W_{Q, f_2}(x)}{W(x)Z} = \frac{K \phi_0'}{WZ} (-4f_2 + 2x(2xf_2 + f_2')) .$$

As above, the differential definition of W and Eq. (3.33) lead us to derive the results presented in the main text. Note that, in order to obtain the transfer function $H_\epsilon^{(P)}$ the complete definition of the variation of the firing rate is $\nu_1 = -\frac{1}{2} p'_1(x)$.

Alternative derivation of Eq. (3.44)

Consider the differential equation for $\psi_n(v)$:

$$\lambda_n \psi_n(v) = \mathcal{L}^\dagger \psi_n = (f(v) + \mu) \partial_v \psi_n + \frac{\sigma^2}{2} \partial_v^2 \psi_n$$

which can be derived with respect of μ leading to:

$$\partial_\mu \lambda \psi_n + \lambda_n \partial_\mu \psi_n = \mathcal{L}^\dagger \partial_\mu \psi_n + \partial_x \psi_n$$

by multiplying by the stationary solution $\phi_0(v)$ and integrating we can further simplify. In fact using orthogonality of the eigen-basis we get:

$$\lambda_n c_{n0}^{(\mu)} = \langle \phi_0 | \mathcal{L}^\dagger \partial_\mu \psi_n \rangle + \langle \phi_0 | \partial_v \psi_n \rangle$$

however using the fact that $\langle \phi_0 | \mathcal{L}^\dagger \partial_\mu \psi_n \rangle = \langle \mathcal{L} \phi_0 | \partial_\mu \psi_n \rangle = 0$. we finally arrive at $\lambda_n c_{n0}^{(\mu)} = \langle \phi_0 | \partial_x \psi_n \rangle$.

Appendix B

Finite-Size effects

Spectral expansion and power spectrum of v . — Following [MD02], the SFP Eq. (4.3) can be rewritten as an infinite set of differential equations for the projection coefficients $a_n(t) = \int_{-\infty}^{\theta} \psi_n(v) p(v, t) dv$ of p onto the eigenfunctions $\psi_n(v)$. Briefly, this can be done by applying $\int_{-\infty}^{\theta} dv \psi_n(v)$ to both hand sides of Eq. (4.3), eventually obtaining the stochastic firing rate equation

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\vec{a}} &= (\mathbf{\Lambda} + \mathbf{C}\dot{v}_N) \vec{a} + \vec{c} \dot{v}_N + \vec{\psi}_H \eta \\ v_N &= \Phi + \vec{f} \cdot \vec{a} + \eta \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.1})$$

For the sake of simplicity, we resorted to a matrix formalism where $\{\vec{a}\}_n = a_n(t)$, and the ‘coupling’ coefficients $c_{nm} = \int_{-\infty}^{\theta} \phi_m(v) \partial_v \psi_n(v) dv$ compose the infinite vector $\{\vec{c}\}_n = c_{n0}$ and matrix $\{\mathbf{C}\}_{nm} = c_{nm}$, given $n, m \neq 0$. The ‘coupling’ label comes from the fact that these coefficients directly depend on the synaptic efficacy J as, from Eq. (2.11), $\partial_v \cdot = \partial_v \mu \partial_\mu \cdot + \partial_v \sigma^2 \partial_{\sigma^2} \cdot \sim J$. Here, the ‘stationary mode’ ($n = 0$) with $\lambda_0 = 0$ and probability density $\phi_0(v)$ has been isolated, and it gives the current-to-rate gain function $\Phi(\mu, \sigma^2) \equiv f_0$, i.e., the stationary firing rate v_0 of the network (see for instance [Ger+14]). Other definitions are as in the main text.

Under stationary conditions ($\dot{\mu}_{\text{ext}} = 0$ and $\dot{\sigma}_{\text{ext}} = 0$), the above firing rate equation for a set of uncoupled neurons ($\vec{c} = 0$ and $\mathbf{C} = 0$ being $J = 0$) reduces to

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\vec{a}} &= \mathbf{\Lambda} \vec{a} + \vec{\psi}_H \eta \\ v_N &= \Phi + \vec{f} \cdot \vec{a} + \eta \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.2})$$

where all the coefficients are now constant. The Fourier transform of the firing rate is then $\hat{v}_N(\omega) = \vec{f} \cdot \hat{\vec{a}}(\omega) + \hat{\eta}(\omega)$, where $\hat{\vec{a}}(\omega) = (i\omega \mathbf{I} - \mathbf{\Lambda})^{-1} \vec{\psi}_H \hat{\eta}(\omega)$. Given that, an explicit expression $P_v^{(\text{SE})}(\omega) = |\hat{v}_N(\omega)|^2$ can be worked out leading to Eq. (4.5).

Numerical analysis. — The continuity equation (2.15) is a nonlinear PDE with the following boundary conditions: i) neurons emitting a spike cross an absorbing barrier in $v = \theta$, $p(\theta) = 0$; ii) after a refractory period τ_0 from spike emission, neurons reenter in $v = H$ requiring the conservation of the probability current, $S_p(\theta, t - \tau_0) = S_p(H^+, t) - S_p(H^-, t)$; iii) membrane potential is limited to $v \geq v_{\text{min}}$ by setting a reflecting barrier, $S_p(v_{\text{min}}) = 0$. For the sake of simplicity, here $\tau_0 = 0$ and $v_{\text{min}} \rightarrow \infty$. To numerically integrate Eq. (4.1), we resorted to the open-source software described in [Aug+17]. It implements a voltage and time discretization scheme based on the Scharfetter-Gummel flux [SG69] and taking into account the above boundary conditions. We adapted this software by incorporating finite-size fluctuations to integrate the SFP Eq. (4.3) Briefly, at each time step dt the

firing rate $\nu_N(t)$ of a network composed of N neurons is computed by adding the finite-size noise $\eta(t)$ to the flux $\nu(t) = S_p(\theta)$. The noise $\eta(t)$ is worked out resorting to the Euler–Maruyama method to integrate the Itô defined Eq. (4.8) [Ris96].

In the SFP Eq. (4.3), we consider the moments of the synaptic current Eq. (2.11) being dependent on the rate of incoming spikes $K\tilde{\nu}(t)$ instead of $K\nu_N(t)$. This because the example networks in Figs. 4.3 and 4.4 incorporate a distribution $g(\delta)$ of axonal delays δ such that

$$\tilde{\nu}(t) = \int_0^\infty g(\delta)\nu_N(t - \delta)d\delta, \quad (\text{B.3})$$

where $g(\delta) = e^{-(\delta - \delta_{\min})/\tau_\delta}/\tau_\delta$ vanishing for any $\delta < \delta_{\min}$, and with mean delay $\langle\delta\rangle = \tau_\delta + \delta_{\min}$. For the numerical integration we resorted to the equivalent expression $\tau_\delta\dot{\tilde{\nu}}(t) = \nu_N(t - \delta_{\min}) - \tilde{\nu}(t)$ [MD02; Mat+19]. The reentering flux in H of realizations/neurons just having emitted a spike, is taken into account by setting at each time step $S_p(H^+, t) - S_p(H^-, t) = \nu_N(t)$.

Spiking neuron networks were simulated resorting to the open source NEST simulator [Far+20]. Network and neuron parameters are those detailed in Fig. 4.2.

Appendix C

Low dimensional dynamics

The eigenfunctions of the Fokker-Planck operator The definition of all the special functions used here can be found in [DLM17] What follows holds for any IF, i.e. the general form of the eigenfunctions is relate to the boundary conditions of the FP equation, however for consistency with the rest of the paper we will consider the LIF neuron. For details on the derivation we suggest the appendixes of the papers [BH99; DR17] while here we only give the main results.

It is useful to introduce the rescaled membrane potential variable i.e.:

$$x = \frac{v - \mu\tau_m}{\sigma\sqrt{\tau_m}}$$

Then the differential equation to solve for the eigenfunctions of the LIF F.P. operator L is:

$$\frac{\partial(xf)}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial x^2} = \lambda f(x, \lambda) \quad (\text{C.1})$$

For further simplification, without loss of generality, we assume the minimum potential to be at $-\infty$. To complete the Sturm-Liouville problem we need boundary conditions for $f(x, \lambda)$ that can be derived with a substitution of f in the boundary conditions of the FP operator given in the main text. However eigenfuncions are unique up to a normalization constant that, following [DR17], we fix by constraining the non stationary components of the firing rate to be unitary:

$$-\frac{\partial\phi_\lambda(x)}{\partial x} = 1$$

we will refer to the two independent solution of (C.1) as $f_1(\lambda, x)$ and $f_2(\lambda, x)$ with $\lim_{x \rightarrow -\infty} f_2(\lambda, x) = 0$, and to their Wroskian evaluated at x as $Wr(x)$. Then the the eigenfunction can be finally written as:

$$\phi(x, \lambda) = \begin{cases} a(\lambda)f_1(x, \lambda) + b(\lambda)f_2(x, \lambda) & x_r < x \leq x_t \\ c(\lambda)f_2(x, \lambda) & -\infty < x \leq x_r \end{cases}$$

where the coefficients are defined as:

$$a(\lambda) = f_2(x_r, \lambda)e^{x_r^2} \quad b(\lambda) = -f_1(x_t, \lambda)e^{x_t^2}$$

$$c(\lambda) = f_1(x_r, \lambda)e^{x_r^2} - f_1(x_t, \lambda)e^{x_t^2}$$

Since the FP operator is not Hermitian, to complete the eigen basis set we need to find the eigenfunctions of the adjoint operator [Ris96] L^\dagger defined as:

$$\langle \psi_\lambda | L\phi_\lambda \rangle = \langle L^\dagger \psi_\lambda | \phi_\lambda \rangle$$

Were we used the braket notation for the inner product and introduce the adjoint eigenfunction $\psi_\lambda(x)$. In this case the boundary condition are obtained imposing vanish boundary terms in the inner product. One of this condition is actually the characteristic equation that we used in the text however any of the boundary condition can be used to derive the spectrum $\{\lambda_n\}$ such as:

$$\phi_\lambda(x_t) = 0$$

Turns out that the general solution of the adjoint problem can be always found in the form:

$$\psi_\lambda(x) = C f_2(x, \lambda) / Wr(x)$$

Where the constant prefactor is constrained requesting normality of the set: $\langle \psi_{\lambda_n} | \phi_{\lambda_m} \rangle = \delta_{nm}$. In the specific case of the LIF the Wroskian is $Wr(x) = 2e^{-x^2}$ and the function f_1, f_2 can be written in terms of the confluent hypergeometric function $M(a, b, z)$ [DLM17]:

$$f_1(x, \lambda) = M\left(\frac{1-\lambda}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, -x^2\right)$$

$$f_2(x, \lambda) = \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{\lambda}{2}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{\lambda+1}{2}\right)} M\left(\frac{1-\lambda}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, -x^2\right) + 2x M\left(1 - \frac{\lambda}{2}, \frac{3}{2}, -x^2\right)$$

We found however that the equivalent form in term of parabolic cylinder function $D_\nu(z)$ is computationally more robust and convenient.

Analytical result on the LIF spectrum The characteristic equation to solve for the λ is:

$$e^{x_t^2} f_2(x_t, \lambda) = e^{x_r^2} f_2(x_r, \lambda) \quad (\text{C.2})$$

We start with highly negative drift case, $\mu \rightarrow -\infty$, where all the probability density is located below reset potential H . The formally speaking we can remap the problem to an equivalent Shrodinger equation and show that the eigenfunctions become Hermite polynomial of odd order $H_{2n+1}(x)$. Here we use the inverse approach and ask ourselves if there is any x for witch $\lambda = -(2n+1)$ with n positive integers. Substitution in (C.2) leads to:

$$H_{2n+1}(x_t) = H_{2n+1}(x_r)$$

The only solution valid for any n is simply $x_t = x_r$, witch is only possible in the limit $\mu \rightarrow -\infty$, then in this case the eigenvalue are odd negative integers.

Now let's consider the case $\mu = 0$ for our choice of $H = 0$ this implies $x_r = 0$. Now for the range of typically observed firing rate, σ must be of the same order of θ , see Fig C.1, this suggest that we can Taylor expand around x_t (C.2):

$$1 + x_t W\left(\frac{\lambda}{2}\right) + o(x_t^2) = 0$$

where we write the Wallis ration $W(z) = \frac{\Gamma(z+1)}{\Gamma(z+\frac{1}{2})}$. We will now use an asymptotic result derived by [Mor11] that relates W to the digamma function for large values of z i.e. $W(z) \sim e^{\frac{\Psi(z+\frac{3}{4})}{2}}$. Then the C.E. reduces to:

$$\Psi\left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{3}{4}\right) = -2\ln(x_t)$$

Figure C.1: Gain Function of the LIF neuron. In the contour plot we show the Gain function as a function of the mean $\mu\tau$ and variance $\sigma\tau$ of the synaptic current. In white we report the iso-frequency curves at 5,20,60,100 Hz from left to right.

from which we learn that the eigenvalues are related to the poles of Ψ :

$$\lambda_n = -2n - 3/2$$

for $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$. Proceeding with increasing μ , some of the real eigenvalues, Drift-Dominated, will bifurcate to complex conjugates while others will remain real and decrease to $-\infty$. We found that this bifurcation occurs roughly close to $\mu^* = \frac{\theta-H}{2}$ or equivalently at $x_t = -x_r$. In this point the C.E. is simplified and becomes:

$$M \left(1 - \frac{\lambda}{2}, \frac{3}{2}, -x^2 \right)$$

that has known perturbative solutions:

$$\lambda_{nDD}^* \sim \frac{-3\pi^2 n^2 - x_t^4 + 3x_t^2}{6x_t^2} \quad (\text{C.3})$$

those are the eigenvalues that will become complex upon further increasing of μ . Regarding the Noise-Dominated eigenvalues we can use the same strategy as before and ask where the eigenvalues will even negative integer:

$$\lambda_{nND} \sim -2n$$

and using the relation with Hermite polynomials we find the C.E. to be $H_{2n}(x_t) = H_{2n}(x_r)$ which is true for any n when $x_t = -x_r$.

Finally using previous result on the VIF neuron [FM99; MD02] we were able to derive a good approximation for the complex conjugate eigenvalues at $\mu > \mu^*$.

The simplified IF model studied by Fusi and Mattia has constant drift term, $f(v) = -\beta$ and a reflecting barrier at $v = H$, and is closely related to the LIF especially at high drift μ . In fact the path followed by the membrane potential of the LIF in the fully deterministic case, $\sigma = 0$, is :

$$V(t) = e^{-t/\tau} (H - \mu\tau + e^{t/\tau} \mu\tau)$$

Noting that if $\mu\tau \gg \theta$ then we must have $\tau \gg \theta/\mu \gg 1$ that justifies a Taylor expansion:

$$V_{LIF}(t) \approx H - \mu_{LIF} t$$

Now provided that $\mu_{VIF} = H/\tau - \mu_{LIF}$ and $\theta_{VIF} = \theta - H$, the two models are equivalent in the limit of very high drift. This means that the spectrum of the LIF coincides in that limit $\mu \gg \theta/\tau$ to the one of the VIF found in [MD02]. Using this duality we can prove that the real part follows:

$$Re(\lambda_n^{DD}) \approx -\frac{2n^2\pi^2\sigma^2}{\theta^2}$$

and also that in the limit $\sigma \rightarrow 0$ the DD eigenvalues become pure imaginary:

$$\lambda_n^{DD} = i2\pi n\nu = \frac{i2\pi n}{\log\left(\frac{x_t}{x_r}\right)}$$

. Surprisingly we found that this result holds quite well even at know zero σ and that the imaginary part of the eigenvalues increase linearly with μ just like can be analytically proved for the VIF i.e.:

$$\lambda_n^{DD} \approx -2\left(\frac{n\pi\sigma}{\theta}\right)^2 + i2n\pi\frac{\mu - \mu^*}{\theta}$$

Delay distribution In presence of distribution of synaptic delay the ERE equations can be generalized [MG03]:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\vec{a}} &= (\mathbf{\Lambda} + \mathbf{C}\dot{\nu})\vec{a} + \vec{c}\dot{\nu} \\ \dot{\nu} &= \frac{\nu - \tilde{\nu}}{\tau_D} \\ \nu &= \Phi + \vec{f} \cdot \vec{a} \end{aligned} \tag{C.4}$$

The instantaneous firing rate of the population ν must be substituted with the averaged version:

$$\tilde{\nu} = \int_0^\infty \nu(t - \delta)\rho(\delta)$$

In the text we assumed an exponential distribution of delays following [Mat+19]:

$$\rho(\delta) = \frac{1}{\tau_D} e^{-\frac{\delta}{\tau_D}} \Theta(\delta)$$

where we add an Heaviside function Θ to avoid negative delay. The ERE equation now complicates greatly since the become integro-differential, however there is an important result noted by Fargue [Far73] also known as the linear chain trick. In can be proved that a dynamical system of the kind:

$$\dot{x}(t) = H(x, t) + \int_{-\infty}^t f(t - \theta)G(\theta)d\theta$$

can be recast to a chain of ordinary differential equation as long as $f(t - \theta)$ is a combination of linear function like $t^n e^{at}$ with a that can also assume complex values.

This is exactly the case of the ERE with delay, in fact we need just to derive to respect of time $\tilde{\nu}$ to obtain:

$$\dot{\tilde{\nu}} = \frac{\nu - \tilde{\nu}}{\tau_D}$$

This leads $\tilde{\nu}$ to be a version of the collective firing rate ν smoothed in time by a first order low pass filter with decay time τ_D . Equation (5.9) follows from (C.4) in the same way the coupled case is obtained in [Mat16], how ever one has to separate the derivative of ν with that of $\tilde{\nu}$.

Derivation of low dimensional model To derive the low dimensional model from the truncated ERE equations we can proceed in multiple ways. We consider the case of two eigenmodes and for simplicity will neglect the coupling between modes, $c_{nm} \sim 0$ since we verified to be irrelevant with respect of the autocoupling terms that we have included instead. All these assumption have been made only for the sake of clarity but the same calculation can be carried out for any number of modes and coefficients to include.

The main idea is to found n equations that relates a_n with mesoscopic quantities. An obvious choice is the mean firing rate that by definition is:

$$\nu = \Phi(\tilde{\nu}) + \frac{a_1 + a_2}{\tau_m} \quad (\text{C.5})$$

where we already considered the filtered version of the firing rate due to synaptic delays, $\tilde{\nu}$ of (C.4). The second equation to close the system can be derived by time derivation of (C.5). The terms \dot{a}_1, \dot{a}_2 can be removed using:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{a}_1 = \Lambda_1(\tilde{\nu}, \nu_{Ext})a_1 + c_{01}\dot{\tilde{\nu}} + c_{01}^{Ext}\dot{\nu}_{Ext} \\ \dot{a}_2 = \Lambda_2(\tilde{\nu}, \nu_{Ext})a_2 + c_{02}\dot{\tilde{\nu}} + c_{02}^{Ext}\dot{\nu}_{Ext} \end{cases}$$

Were introduced also the external population ν_{Ext} and defined the rinormalized eigenvalues: $\Lambda_n = \lambda_1 + c_{nn}\dot{\tilde{\nu}} + c_{nn}^{Ext}\dot{\nu}_{Ext}$. In the end the equation for $\dot{\nu}$ is:

$$\dot{\nu} = \frac{\partial\Phi}{\partial\tilde{\nu}}\dot{\tilde{\nu}} + \frac{\partial\Phi}{\partial\nu_{Ext}}\dot{\nu}_{Ext} + \frac{1}{\tau_m}(\Lambda_1a_1 + \Lambda_2a_2 + c_{02}\dot{\tilde{\nu}} + c_{02}^{Ext}\dot{\nu}_{Ext}) \quad (\text{C.6})$$

Inverting Equations C.5,C.6 we can derive $a_1(\nu, \dot{\nu})$ and $a_2(\nu, \dot{\nu})$. The last step consist in deriving once again eq.(C.6) and use the found relations to remove a_1 and a_2 . After some algebra we arrive at the model used in the text, where the only variables are the firing rate and it's time derivatives:

$$\begin{cases} \alpha_2(\tilde{\nu}, \nu_{Ext})\ddot{\tilde{\nu}} + \alpha_1(\tilde{\nu}, \nu_{Ext})\dot{\tilde{\nu}} = \Phi(\tilde{\nu}, \nu_{Ext}) - \nu + F(\tilde{\nu}, \nu_{Ext}) \\ \dot{\tilde{\nu}} = \frac{\nu - \tilde{\nu}}{\tau_D} \end{cases}$$

Whit the following definitions for the coefficients:

$$\begin{cases} \gamma = -\Lambda_1\Lambda_2 \left(\Lambda_1 - \Lambda_2 + \frac{d\log(\frac{\Lambda_1}{\Lambda_2})}{dt} \right) \\ \alpha_2 = -\frac{\Lambda_1 - \Lambda_2}{\gamma} \\ \alpha_1 = \frac{\Lambda_1^2 - \Lambda_2^2 + \frac{d\Lambda_1}{dt} - \frac{d\Lambda_2}{dt}}{\gamma} \end{cases} \quad (\text{C.7})$$

and driving:

$$\begin{cases} f = \dot{\Phi} + \frac{c_{01} + c_{02}}{\tau_m}\dot{\tilde{\nu}} + \frac{c_{01}^{Ext} + c_{02}^{Ext}}{\tau_m}\dot{\nu}_{Ext} \\ g = \frac{c_{01}\Lambda_1 + c_{02}\Lambda_2}{\tau_m}\dot{\tilde{\nu}} + \frac{c_{01}^{Ext}\Lambda_1 + c_{02}^{Ext}\Lambda_2}{\tau_m}\dot{\nu}_{Ext} \\ \quad + \frac{c_{01} + c_{02}}{\tau_m}\ddot{\tilde{\nu}} + \frac{c_{01}^{Ext} + c_{02}^{Ext}}{\tau_m}\ddot{\nu}_{Ext} \\ F = \alpha_2(f + g) + \alpha_1f \end{cases} \quad (\text{C.8})$$

τ_ν and ω_ν in coupled network To derive the decay time and angular frequency of a network of coupled neurons we need to Taylor expand with respect to J the coefficients α_1 and α_2 . From the mean field theory we have that

$$c_{n0} = KJc_{n0}^\mu + \frac{KJ^2}{\sigma^2}c_{n0}^{\sigma^2}$$

from this follows that

$$\tau_v \sim \tau_0 \left(1 - KJ \frac{(\lambda_1 c_{10}^\mu + \lambda_2 c_{20}^\mu)}{(\lambda_1 + \lambda_2) \tau_m} \right) + o(J^2)$$

and the angular frequency

$$\omega_v^2 \sim \omega_0^2 + J \left(-\frac{\alpha_{10}^2 (\lambda_1 c_{10}^\mu + \lambda_2 c_{20}^\mu)}{2\alpha_{20}^2 (\lambda_1 + \lambda_2) \tau_m} - \frac{\partial_\mu \Phi}{\alpha_{20}} \right) + o(J^2)$$

Appendix D

Moments dynamics

Equations for the mean membrane potential For the most general IF model such as the Exponential IF, the stationary mean membrane potential and the projection on the various eigenmodes, u_n must be calculated numerically as it is the case for the coefficients of the ERE expansion c_{nm} . This is due to the fact that in general $\langle f(x) \rangle \neq f(\langle x \rangle)$ except when $f(x)$ is linear which is the case for Leaky Integrate and Fire model used here. In fact in this case a closed form can be obtained directly from the Fokker-Planck equation:

$$\tau \partial_t P = \partial_v [(v - \mu)P] + \frac{\sigma^2}{2} \partial_v^2 P$$

that comes with three boundary conditions:

- Absorbing boundary at the spike emission threshold θ : $P(\theta, t) = 0$
- Conservation of flux after the reset at potential H . $\partial_v P(H_+) - \partial_v P(H_-) = \partial_v P(\theta)$
- Reflective boundary at v_{min} : $S_P(v_{min}) = 0$ where S_P is the probability flux.

By multiplying for v and integrating on all the domain we get for $m = \int_{v_{min}}^{\theta} v P dv$:

$$\tau \dot{m} = -m + \mu + \left[v(v - \mu)P + \frac{\sigma^2}{2} (-P + v \partial_v P) \right]_{b.c.}$$

where we integrated by parts. For simplicity we will assume $v_{min} = -\infty$. Now for the integrability ,i.e. $\lim_{v \rightarrow -\infty} v^n P = 0$ and continuity condition on $P(v, t)$ only the last term of the boundary condition part survives. we finally get:

$$\tau \dot{m} = -m + \mu + (H - \theta) \nu \tau \quad (D.1)$$

using:

$$\partial_v P(H_+) - \partial_v P(H_-) = \partial_v P(\theta) = -\frac{2\nu\tau}{\sigma^2}$$

From this we also get the stationary mean potential:

$$m_0 = \mu + (H - \theta) \Phi(\mu, \sigma) \tau$$

where Φ is the gain function. An analogous result holds for any moment $m_k = \int_{-\infty}^{\theta} v^k P(v, t) dv$ and its stationary value:

$$\begin{aligned} \tau \dot{m}_k &= -k m_k + k \mu m_{k-1} + \beta_k \nu \tau + \frac{k(k-1)}{2} \sigma^2 m_{k-2} \\ m_{k,0} &= \mu m_{k-1} + \frac{\beta_k \nu \tau}{k} + \frac{k-1}{2} \sigma^2 m_{k-2,0} \end{aligned} \quad (D.2)$$

with $\beta_k = (H^k - \theta^k)$

The Jacobian matrix of the model The Jacobian matrix can be obtained by differentiation with of the flux that in scalar notation reads:

$$F_i = \sum_j G_{ij}^\lambda(v)(m_j - m_j^0(v))$$

From equation () follows the derivative of the firing rate respect the moments:

$$\frac{dv}{dm_k} = \frac{\sum_j \mathbf{U}^{-1}_{kj}}{1 + \partial_v \Phi(v) - \frac{1}{\tau} \sum_{ij} \mathbf{U}^{-1}_{ij} \partial_v m_j^0}$$

and finally the Jacobian calculated at the fixed point $\vec{m} = \vec{m}_0$ and $v = v_0$:

$$\frac{dF_i}{dm_k} = \sum_j G_{ij}^\lambda(v) \left(\delta_{ik} - \partial_v m_j^0 \frac{dv}{dm_k} \right).$$

The standard spectral expansion system or ERE in the linearized regime for the dynamics of the eigenmodes $a_n(t)$ reads:

$$\dot{\vec{a}} = \mathbf{\Lambda} \vec{a} + \vec{c} \dot{v}$$

where the coupling coefficient are defined as $c_n = \langle \partial_v \psi_n | \phi_0 \rangle$. In this case the time derivative of the firing rate can be expressed as:

$$\dot{v} = -\frac{1}{\tau} \frac{\sum_j \lambda_j a_j}{1 - \partial_v \Phi - \frac{\sum_j c_j}{\tau}}$$

from which the Jacobian directly follows:

$$\frac{dF_i}{da_k} = \lambda_i \delta_{ik} - \frac{c_i \frac{\lambda_k}{\tau}}{1 - \partial_v \Phi - \frac{\sum_j c_j}{\tau}}$$

Analytical expression for the dominant λ In the main text we report the following approximation for the real part of the dominant eigenvalue:

$$\begin{aligned} Re(\lambda_{ND}) &= -1 + (\lambda_*(\sigma) + 1) \left(\frac{\mu - v_m}{\mu_* - v_m} \right)^{c(\sigma)} \\ Re(\lambda_{DD}) &= -2 \left(\frac{\pi\sigma}{\theta} \right)^2 \\ &\quad + \left(\lambda_\gamma(\sigma) + 2 \left(\frac{\pi\sigma}{\theta} \right)^2 \right) \left(\frac{\mu - v_M}{\mu_* - v_M} \right)^{c(\sigma)} \end{aligned}$$

The distinction between noise (ND) and drift dominated (DD) comes from [..]. We found that curve that separates this two regimes $\gamma(\sigma)$ can be fitted by a piece-wise polynomial function of order 3. The same goes for the value of the eigenvalue there $\lambda_\gamma(\sigma)$. This are the only expression that we need to fit in fact the rest of the information needed can be derived by analytical results directly. The asymptotic value of λ as we get close to the reflecting boundary v_m (here $v_m = -3\theta$) is -1 (in unit of τ). Moreover thanks to the fact the for sufficiently high drift $\mu \gg \theta$ all the neuron model coincides with PIF neuron [..] the real part must converge to $-2 \left(\frac{\sigma\pi}{\theta} \right)^2$. A good approximation is then forcing the eigenvalue to have such value for $\mu \geq v_M$ (here we chose 3θ). Finally the characteristic equation can be solved exactly when $\mu = \mu_* = \frac{\theta-H}{2}$. Here the dominant eigenvalue λ_* is the maximum

value between -2 and the dominant zero of a Bessel function of the first kind for which asymptotic expression exist or a cubic fit in σ can be used. A power law ansatz:

$$\lambda(\mu, \sigma) = a(\mu, \sigma) + b(\mu, \sigma)\mu^{c(\sigma)}$$

allows to consider all this information and leads to the expressions in the main text with the following definition for $c(\sigma)$:

$$c_{DD}(\sigma) = \frac{\log(\max(3/2, \frac{\lambda_s - \lambda_M}{\lambda_\gamma - \lambda_M}))}{\log\left(\frac{\mu_* - v_M}{\gamma(\sigma) - v_M}\right)}$$

where $\lambda_M = -2\left(\frac{\pi\sigma}{\theta}\right)^2$. In the DD regime we force the maximum value of the exponent to be 3/2 that we found to improve greatly the approximation in the low σ region. In the ND regime we have instead

$$c_{ND}(\sigma) = \frac{\log\left(\frac{1+\lambda_\gamma}{1+\lambda_*}\right)}{\log\left(\frac{\gamma(\sigma) - v_M}{\mu_* - v_M}\right)}$$

For the imaginary part we can once again use the *PIF* neuron that has $I(\lambda) = 2\pi n \frac{\mu - \mu_0}{\theta}$ where in that case $\mu_0 = 0$. For the LIF we found analogous behaviour however the correct μ_0 is a function of σ . A good approximation is assuming however $\mu_0 = \mu_*$.

Appendix E

Spectral quantities of the VIF neuron

The boundary condition of the Fokker-Planck equation are reflected on the eigenfunctions $\phi_n(v)$ while for ψ_n we have to assume: (i) ϕ_n, ψ_n to be continuous in the interval (α, θ) , including the possibility that $\alpha \rightarrow -\infty$; (ii) $\{\phi_n\}$ to be a complete set of eigenfunctions ; (iii) boundary conditions (2.19),(2.18),(2.17) must be satisfied by each $\phi_n(v, t)$. Then, the conditions on the eigenfunctions ψ_n of \mathbf{L}^+ result:

$$\begin{aligned}\psi_n(\theta, t)S_{\phi_n}(\theta, t) &= \psi_n(H, t)s_{\phi_n}(\theta, t), \\ \partial_v \psi_n(\alpha, t) &= 0, \\ \partial_v \psi_n(H^+, t) &= \partial_v \psi_n(H^-, t).\end{aligned}\tag{E.1}$$

The VIF stationary mode

Replacing the value $\lambda = 0$ in the equation for the eigenfunction:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{1}{2}\sigma^2\partial_v^2\phi_0(v, t) - \mu\partial_v\phi_0(v, t) &= 0 \\ \Rightarrow \phi_0(v, t) &= k\frac{\sigma^2}{2\mu}e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}v} + k'.\end{aligned}$$

To determine the constants k and k' , we have to take into account boundary conditions. For the spectral expansion, ϕ_0 is supposed to be continuous in all the interval (α, θ) , but, because of the flux conservation, we expect a *jump discontinuity* in the first derivative of ϕ_0 calculated in H .

We thus suggest the solution in the form:

$$\phi_0(v, t) = \begin{cases} k_1\frac{\sigma^2}{2\mu}e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}v} + k_2, & H \leq v \leq \theta \\ k_3\frac{\sigma^2}{2\mu}e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}v} + k_4 & \alpha \leq v < H. \end{cases}$$

Making use of the boundary conditions:

$$k_2 = -k_1\frac{\sigma^2}{2\mu}e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}\theta} \text{ from 2.17,}$$

$$k_4 = 0 \text{ from 2.19,}$$

As ϕ_0 is supposed to be continuous, $\phi_0(H^+, t) = \phi_0(H^-, t)$, and then

$$k_3 = k_1\left(1 - e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}(\theta-H)}\right).$$

For now, our function is defined as

$$\phi_0(v, t) = \begin{cases} k_1 \frac{\sigma^2}{2\mu} (e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}v} - e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}\theta}) & H \leq v \leq \theta \\ k_1 \frac{\sigma^2}{2\mu} (1 - e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}(\theta-H)}) e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}v} & \alpha \leq v < H. \end{cases}$$

Since the eigenfunction associated to the eigenvalue $\lambda = 0$ is the stationary mode, it is a probability density function and the integral over (α, θ) has to be equal to 1. Imposing that condition, we obtain an expression for k_1 :

$$k_1 = \frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2} \left[\frac{\sigma^2}{2\mu} e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}\alpha} (e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}(\theta-H)} - 1) - e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}\theta} (\theta - H) \right]^{-1},$$

leading to an explicit form for $\phi_0(v, t)$:

$$\phi_0(v, t) = \begin{cases} \mathbf{c} (e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}v} - e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}\theta}) & H \leq v \leq \theta, \\ \mathbf{c} (1 - e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}(\theta-H)}) e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}v} & \alpha \leq v < H \end{cases} \quad (\text{E.2})$$

where

$$\mathbf{c} = \left[\frac{\sigma^2}{2\mu} e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}\alpha} (e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}(\theta-H)} - 1) - e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}\theta} (\theta - H) \right]^{-1}, \quad (\text{E.3})$$

is the normalisation constant.

In the general case, the probability per unit time of crossing the threshold and re-entering into the reset potential H , is given by the flux of the realisations (i.e., the probability flux) at $v = \theta$:

$$\nu(t) = S_p(\theta, t) = -\frac{\sigma^2}{2} \partial_v p(v, t)|_{v=\theta},$$

where $p(v, t)$ is the probability density function of the depolarization process $V(t)$, and we used the fact that θ acts as an absorbing barrier.

The mean fraction of neurons crossing the threshold per unit time at time t is $\nu(t)$, and if the network state is stationary, is also the average emission frequency for any generic neuron.

If we consider a steady statistics of the input current and in a stationary regime, we have that $\nu(t) \equiv \nu$ is constant, and we can explicit it through direct calculation:

$$\nu \equiv \Phi(\mu, \theta) = -\frac{\sigma^2}{2} \partial_v \phi(v)|_{v=\theta} = \frac{2\mu^2}{\sigma^2 e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}\alpha} (e^{\frac{-2\mu}{\sigma^2}H} - e^{\frac{-2\mu}{\sigma^2}\theta}) - 2\mu(\theta - H)}$$

where $\Phi(\mu, \sigma)$ is the gain function. In fact, in stationary conditions $\phi(\mu, \sigma^2)$ gives the output emission rate ν of the population and ϕ_0 is the constant p.d.f. $p(v)$ of the membrane potential at any time.

So we can re-write the stationary solution of the Fokker-Planck equation (??) using ν :

$$\phi_0(v, t) = \begin{cases} -\frac{\nu}{\mu} (e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}(v-\theta)} - 1) & H \leq v \leq \theta \\ -\frac{\nu}{\mu} (e^{-\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}\theta} - e^{-\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}H}) e^{\frac{2\mu}{\sigma^2}v} & \alpha \leq v < H. \end{cases} \quad (\text{E.4})$$

We now focus on a particular limit for the mean value of the input current, $\mu \rightarrow 0$, because, for the critical value $\mu = 0$, the uncoupled VIF network shows analytical properties useful to study the network behaviour [MD02].

Apparently the solution has a discontinuity, but it is a removable one: in fact, for $\mu \rightarrow 0$, the structure of the equation changes

$$\frac{\sigma^2}{2} \partial_v^2 \phi_0(v, t) = 0 \Rightarrow \phi_0(v, t) = kv + k'.$$

With the same arguments of the previous case and imposing the above boundary conditions, the conservation of the probability flux and the normalisation, we get:

$$\lim_{\mu \rightarrow 0} \phi_0(v, t) = \begin{cases} \frac{2}{(H-\theta)(H-2\alpha+2\theta)}(v-\theta) & H \leq v \leq \theta \\ \frac{2}{H-2\alpha+2\theta} & \alpha \leq v < H \end{cases}. \quad (\text{E.5})$$

Remarking that $v = -\frac{\sigma^2}{2} \partial_v \phi_0|_{v=\theta} = \frac{\sigma^2}{(H-\theta)(H-2\alpha+2\theta)}$, we can re-write the solution in the limit $\mu \rightarrow 0$ as:

$$\lim_{\mu \rightarrow 0} = \begin{cases} -\frac{2v}{\sigma^2}(v-\theta) & H \leq v \leq \theta \\ -\frac{2v}{\sigma^2}(H-\theta) & \alpha \leq v < H \end{cases}. \quad (\text{E.6})$$

We remind that the eigenfunction ψ_0 of the adjoint operator L_{VIF}^+ is

$$\psi_0 = 1.$$

Eigenfunctions of L_{VIF} Taking $\lambda \neq 0$, the equation ?? becomes a homogeneous second order differential equation with time dependent coefficients:

$$\frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 \partial_v^2 \phi(\lambda, v) - \mu \partial_v \phi(\lambda, v) - \lambda \phi(\lambda, v) = 0, \quad (\text{E.7})$$

whose general solution is a linear combination of the two fundamentals functions

$$f_1(\lambda, v) = e^{(\xi+\zeta)\frac{v}{\theta}}, \bar{f}_1(\lambda, v) = e^{(\xi-\zeta)\frac{v}{\theta}}$$

where

$$\xi = \frac{\mu\theta}{\sigma^2}, \zeta(\lambda) = \frac{\theta}{\sigma^2} \sqrt{\mu^2 + 2\lambda\sigma^2}, \quad (\text{E.8})$$

and thus

$$\phi(\lambda, v) = c_1 f_1(\lambda, v) + c_2 \bar{f}_1(\lambda, v).$$

We put the dependence of λ in ϕ because of the presence of the function $\zeta(\lambda)$, which we will just call $\zeta = \zeta(\lambda)$ to ease the notation, in the definition of the fundamental functions, and we are not putting the explicit dependence on t because it is implicitly due to the presence of μ and σ^2 .

As in the stationary mode case, using the same arguments, we are looking for a solution in the form:

$$\phi(\lambda, v) = \begin{cases} c_1 f_1(\lambda, v) + c_2 \bar{f}_1(\lambda, v) & H < v \leq \theta \\ c_3 f_1(\lambda, v) + c_4 \bar{f}_1(\lambda, v) & \alpha \leq v < H \end{cases} \quad (\text{E.9})$$

In order to simplify as much as possible the following derivations, we want to re-write the general solution as a linear combination of two *new* fundamental functions f_1, f_2 , where

$$f_2(\lambda, v) = k_1 f_1(\lambda, v) + k_2 \bar{f}_1(\lambda, v), \quad (\text{E.10})$$

such that f_2 embodies the reflecting barrier, i.e:

$$S_{f_2}(\lambda, \alpha) = 0.$$

$$S_{f_2}(\lambda, \alpha) = k_1 \frac{\sigma^2}{2\theta} e^{(\xi+\zeta)\frac{\alpha}{\theta}} (\xi - \zeta) + k_2 \frac{\sigma^2}{2\theta} e^{(\xi-\zeta)\frac{\alpha}{\theta}} (\xi + \zeta) = 0$$

$$\implies k_2 = -k_1 \frac{\xi - \zeta}{\xi + \zeta} e^{2\frac{\alpha}{\theta}\zeta}.$$

Using the arbitrariness of k_1 , we can fix it equal to 1, so that our *new* fundamentals solutions are:

$$f_1(\lambda, v) = e^{(\xi+\zeta)\frac{v}{\theta}}, \quad (\text{E.11})$$

$$f_2(\lambda, v) = e^{(\xi+\zeta)\frac{v}{\theta}} + \frac{\xi - \zeta}{\zeta + \xi} e^{2\frac{\alpha}{\theta}\zeta} e^{(\xi-\zeta)\frac{v}{\theta}}. \quad (\text{E.12})$$

In that way, by construction of f_2 , we suppose the solution of the equation (E.7) is of the form:

$$\phi(\lambda, v) = \begin{cases} a(\lambda)f_1(\lambda, v) + b(\lambda)f_2(\lambda, v) & H < v \leq \theta \\ d(\lambda)f_2(\lambda, v) & \alpha \leq v < H, \end{cases} \quad (\text{E.13})$$

where we put the coefficients $a(\lambda), b(\lambda), d(\lambda)$ depending on λ since the presence of the $\zeta(\lambda)$ function.

Next we make use of the boundary conditions:

- *Absorbing barrier* $\phi(\lambda, \theta) = 0$

$$a(\lambda)f_1(\lambda, \theta) + b(\lambda)f_2(\lambda, \theta) = 0;$$

- *Continuity condition* $\phi(\lambda, H^+) = \phi(\lambda, H^-)$

$$a(\lambda)f_1(\lambda, H) + b(\lambda)f_2(\lambda, H) - d(\lambda)f_2(\lambda, H) = 0;$$

- *Flux Conservation*: Using the definition of the probability flow (??), then $S_\phi(\lambda, \theta) = S_\phi(\lambda, H^+) - S_\phi(\lambda, H^-)$ leads to:

$$a(\lambda)(f'_1(\lambda, H) - f'_1(\lambda, \theta)) + b(\lambda)(f'_2(\lambda, H) - f'_2(\lambda, \theta)) - d(\lambda)f'_2(\lambda, H) = 0.$$

We are denoting $\partial_v f_{1,2}(\lambda, v)$ as $f'_{1,2}(\lambda, v)$.

We have obtained the linear system:

$$\begin{cases} f_1(\lambda, \theta)a(\lambda) + f_2(\lambda, \theta)b(\lambda) = 0 \\ f_1(\lambda, H)a(\lambda) + f_2(\lambda, H)b(\lambda) - f_2(\lambda, H)d(\lambda) = 0 \\ (f'_1(\lambda, H) - f'_1(\lambda, \theta))a(\lambda) + (f'_2(\lambda, H) - f'_2(\lambda, \theta))b(\lambda) - f'_2(\lambda, H)d(\lambda) = 0, \end{cases} \quad (\text{E.14})$$

and in order to have nonzero solutions, the determinant of the coefficients matrix must satisfy

$$\det \begin{pmatrix} f_1(\lambda, \theta) & f_2(\lambda, \theta) & 0 \\ f_1(\lambda, H) & f_2(\lambda, H) & -f_2(\lambda, H) \\ f'_1(\lambda, H) - f'_1(\lambda, \theta) & f'_2(\lambda, H) - f'_2(\lambda, \theta) & -f'_2(\lambda, H) \end{pmatrix} = 0$$

$$\implies f_2(\lambda, \theta) [f_1(\lambda, H)f'_2(\lambda, H) - f'_1(\lambda, H)f_2(\lambda, H)] +$$

$$-f_2(\lambda, H) [f_1(\lambda, \theta)f'_2(\lambda, \theta) - f'_1(\lambda, \theta)f_2(\lambda, \theta)] = 0.$$

Recalling that the Wronskian of two functions $f_1(\lambda, v), f_2(\lambda, v)$ is defined as

$$\text{Wr}(f_1, f_2)(v) \equiv \text{Wr}(v) := \det \begin{pmatrix} f_1(\lambda, v) & f_2(\lambda, v) \\ f'_1(\lambda, v) & f'_2(\lambda, v) \end{pmatrix} = f_1(\lambda, v)f'_2(\lambda, v) - f'_1(\lambda, v)f_2(\lambda, v), \quad (\text{E.15})$$

we finally obtain a *characteristic equation*

$$\frac{f_2(\lambda, \theta)}{\text{Wr}(\theta)} - \frac{f_2(\lambda, H)}{\text{Wr}(H)} = 0, \quad (\text{E.16})$$

whose solutions are the eigenvalues of the Fokker-Planck operator L_{VIF} .

In order to find $a(\lambda)$, $b(\lambda)$, fixing $d(\lambda)$, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} a(\lambda) &= \frac{f_2(\lambda, H)\text{Wr}(\theta)}{f_1(\lambda, H)\text{Wr}(\theta) - f_1(\lambda, \theta)\text{Wr}(H)}d(\lambda), \\ b(\lambda) &= -\frac{f_1(\lambda, \theta)\text{Wr}(H)}{f_1(\lambda, H)\text{Wr}(\theta) - f_1(\lambda, \theta)\text{Wr}(H)}d(\lambda). \end{aligned}$$

Since eigenfunctions are unique up to some normalisation condition, we arbitrarily set $S_\phi(\lambda, \theta) = 1$.

Using the definition of the probability flow and the presence of the absorbing barrier in θ :

$$\begin{aligned} S_\phi(\lambda, \theta) &= \left[\mu\phi(\lambda, v) - \frac{\sigma^2}{2}\partial_v\phi(\lambda, v) \right]_{v=\theta} = -\frac{\sigma^2}{2}\phi'(\lambda, \theta) = 1 \\ &\Rightarrow a(\lambda)f_1'(\lambda, \theta) + b(\lambda)f_2'(\lambda, \theta) = -\frac{2}{\sigma^2} \\ d(\lambda)(f_1'(\lambda, \theta)f_2(\lambda, H)\text{Wr}(\theta) - f_1(\lambda, \theta)f_2'(\lambda, \theta)\text{Wr}(H)) &= \\ = -\frac{2}{\sigma^2}(f_1(\lambda, H)\text{Wr}(\theta) - f_1(\lambda, \theta)\text{Wr}(H)) & \end{aligned}$$

Using the characteristic equation (E.16) :

$$\begin{aligned} d(\lambda)\text{Wr}(H)(-f_1(\lambda, \theta)f_2'(\lambda, \theta) + f_1'(\lambda, \theta)f_2(\lambda, \theta)) &= \\ = -\frac{2}{\sigma^2}(f_1(\lambda, H)\text{Wr}(\theta) - f_1(\lambda, \theta)\text{Wr}(H)) & \\ \Rightarrow d(\lambda) = \frac{2}{\sigma^2} \frac{f_1(\lambda, H)\text{Wr}(\theta) - f_1(\lambda, \theta)\text{Wr}(H)}{\text{Wr}(H)\text{Wr}(\theta)} & \end{aligned}$$

For this choice of $d(\lambda)$, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} a(\lambda) &= \frac{2}{\sigma^2} \frac{f_2(\lambda, H)}{\text{Wr}(H)}, \\ b(\lambda) &= -\frac{2}{\sigma^2} \frac{f_1(\lambda, \theta)}{\text{Wr}(\theta)}, \end{aligned}$$

and we can finally write an expression for the eigenfunctions of the non-stationary modes ($n \neq 0$) (E.13)

$$\phi(\lambda, v) = \begin{cases} \frac{2}{\sigma^2} \left[\frac{f_2(\lambda, H)}{\text{Wr}(H)} f_1(\lambda, v) - \frac{f_1(\lambda, \theta)}{\text{Wr}(\theta)} f_2(\lambda, v) \right] & H < v \leq \theta \\ \frac{2}{\sigma^2} \left[\frac{f_1(\lambda, H)}{\text{Wr}(H)} - \frac{f_1(\lambda, \theta)}{\text{Wr}(\theta)} \right] f_2(\lambda, v) & \alpha \leq v \leq H. \end{cases} \quad (\text{E.17})$$

The dual eigenspace: eigenfunctions of L_{VIF}^+ operator. Here we want to characterise the eigenfunctions $\psi(\lambda, v)$ of the adjoint operator (7.3). Knowing the fundamental solution of the FP eigenfunction problem, $f_i(v, \lambda)$ with $i = 1, 2$:

$$\frac{\sigma^2}{2} f_i'' - b(v)f_i' - (b'(v) + \lambda)f_i = 0$$

where ' denote the derivative respect of v and $b(v)$ is the total drift term, we can derive the equation for the Wroskian of the two fundamental solutions: $W(v) = f_1' f_2 - f_1 f_2'$:

$$\frac{\sigma^2}{2} W(v)' + b(v)W(v) = 0$$

that has solution : $W(v) = e^{-\frac{2}{\sigma^2} \int^v b(u) du}$. It can be shown by substitution that the fundamental solution of the adjoint eigenfunction problem:

$$\frac{\sigma^2}{2} g_i'' + b(v)g_i' - \lambda g_i = 0$$

are given by $g_i(v) = f_i(v, \lambda)/W(v)$, moreover if define f_2 to satisfy the reflecting boundary condition at α the adjoint eigenfunction is:

$$\psi(v, \lambda_n) = f_2(v, \lambda_n)/W(v)$$

The boundary condition for $\psi_n(v)$ are two:(i) $\psi_n(\theta) = \psi_n(H)$ that is precisely the characteristic equation found above and (ii) $\partial_v \psi_n(\alpha) = 0$ that it can be shown to be true if the characteristic equation is verified. If we set $\theta = 1$ and $H = 0$ we have the following expression for the normalized eigenfunctions:

$$\psi_n(v) = \frac{(\zeta + \xi)e^{v(\zeta - \xi) - 2\alpha\zeta}}{\zeta - \xi} + e^{-v(\zeta + \xi)}$$

$$\phi_n(v) = \frac{1}{Z_n} \begin{cases} e^{v(\xi - \zeta)} - e^{\zeta(v-2) + \xi v} & 0 < v < 1 \\ e^{\zeta(-v-2) + \xi v} (e^{2\zeta} + e^{\zeta + \xi} (e^{2\zeta v} - 1) - e^{2\zeta v}) & \alpha < v < 0 \end{cases} \quad (\text{E.18})$$

For sake of brevity we omit the expression of the normalization coefficient $Z_n = \langle \psi_n | \phi_n \rangle$.

Appendix F

Degeneracy

Model details Since the single neurons are integrate-and-fire point neurons Equation 4.1 must be solved considering appropriate boundary conditions:

- An a reflecting barrier at $v = -\infty$: $\lim_{v \rightarrow -\infty} S_p(v, t)$
- Neurons cannot cross θ so we have an absorbing barrier: $p(\theta, t) = 0$
- When a neuron hit θ it will emit a spike and after a silent refractory period τ_0 it will restart its dynamics from the reset potential H . This induces a probability current that we implement by imposing: $S_p(H^+, t) - S_p(H^-, t) = S_p(\theta, t - \tau_0)$

One last element in the model is axonal delays. From a mean field prospective however considering an exponential distribution of time delays with average τ_D is equivalent to have low-pass filtered firing rates \tilde{v}_α in the synaptic current with:

$$\dot{\tilde{v}}_\alpha = \frac{\nu_\alpha - \tilde{v}_\alpha}{\tau_D}$$

In the following we will consider two specif models of cortical column. The Excitatory-Inhibitory model (EI) with only excitatory adaptation:

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t p_E &= -\partial_v S_{p_E}(\mu_E, \sigma_E^2) \\ \partial_t p_I &= -\partial_v S_{p_I}(\mu_I, \sigma_I^2) \\ \dot{c} &= -\frac{c}{\tau_C} + \nu_E \\ \dot{\tilde{v}}_E &= \frac{\nu_E - \tilde{v}_E}{\tau_{D,E}} \\ \dot{\tilde{v}}_I &= \frac{\nu_I - \tilde{v}_I}{\tau_{D,I}} \end{aligned} \tag{F.1}$$

Where the moments are given by equation 8.1 with $\nu_\alpha \rightarrow \tilde{v}_\alpha$ and $c_I \rightarrow 0$. In the second model we consider instead a single excitatory population with adaptation (E model):

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t p &= -\partial_v S_p(\mu, \sigma^2) \\ \dot{c} &= -\frac{c}{\tau_C} + \nu \\ \dot{\tilde{v}} &= \frac{\nu - \tilde{v}}{\tau_D} \end{aligned} \tag{F.2}$$

As discussed elsewhere this simple model is capable to express a rich variety of dynamical behaviour (see Fig 8.3A) thanks also to the Spike-Frequency adaptation. In particular

we are interested obtaining through optimization the target parameters that reproduce the bifurcation diagram of the figure where we can distinguish a bi-stable state (BS-red) a Low asynchronous state (LAS-black) an high asynchronous state (HAS-yellow) and global oscillation state (GO-white).

For the numerical integration we used the open-source software released with [Aug+17] which implement a Scharfetter-Gummel flux discretization scheme [SG69] with the above defined boundary conditions.

Optimization With this aim, we select 3 point in the plane with different phases ($\beta = \text{HAS, LAS, GO}$) and we simulate the model for 4 seconds to obtain the target excitatory firing rates $v_E^{\beta, T}(t)$. The loss function is then mean square distance:

$$L(\Theta) = \sum_{\beta} \frac{\sum_{n=1}^M (v_{E, \Theta}^{\beta}(ndt) - v_E^{\beta, T}(ndt))^2}{M} \quad (\text{F.3})$$

where M is the number of samples in the traces.

Since we do not have an analytical expression for the gradient of the loss function we decided to adopt an optimization procedure, of the family of genetic algorithm, called Covariance matrix adaptation evolution strategy (CMA-ES) for its proved efficacy for non-linear non convex problem. To explore the possible degeneracy in the Θ space we used 500 different initial conditions extracted by random uniform distribution. We also defined a good fit whenever after 10^3 iterations $L(\Theta) < 0.1$.

Bibliography

- [Lap07] Louis Lapicque. “Recherches quantitatives sur l’excitation électrique des nerfs traitée comme une polarisation”. In: *Journal de Physiologie et de Pathologie Generale* 9 (1907), pp. 620–635.
- [Tur+36] Alan Mathison Turing et al. “On computable numbers, with an application to the Entscheidungsproblem”. In: *J. of Math* 58.345-363 (1936), p. 5.
- [Sie51] Arnold JF Siegert. “On the first passage time probability problem”. In: *Physical Review* 81.4 (1951), p. 617.
- [HH52a] A L Hodgkin and A F Huxley. “A quantitative description of membrane current and its application to conduction and excitation in nerve.” In: *Journal of Physiology* 117.4 (1952), pp. 500–44.
- [HH52b] Alan L Hodgkin and Andrew F Huxley. “A quantitative description of membrane current and its application to conduction and excitation in nerve”. In: *The Journal of physiology* 117.4 (1952), p. 500.
- [DS53] D A Darling and Arnold Siegert. “The first passage problem for a continuous Markov process”. In: *Ann. Math. Stat.* 24.4 (1953), pp. 624–639.
- [Fit55] Richard FitzHugh. “Mathematical models of threshold phenomena in the nerve membrane”. In: *The bulletin of mathematical biophysics* 17.4 (1955), pp. 257–278.
- [Bog+61] Nikolai Nikolaevich Bogoliubov et al. *Asymptotic methods in the theory of non-linear oscillations*. Vol. 10. CRC Press, 1961.
- [Gri63] B. Grigelionis. “On the convergence of sums of random step processes to a Poisson process”. In: *Theory Probab.* 8.2 (1963), pp. 177–182. DOI: [10 . 1137/1108017](https://doi.org/10.1137/1108017).
- [GM64] George L Gerstein and Benoit Mandelbrot. “Random walk models for the spike activity of a single neuron”. In: *Biophysical journal* 4.1 (1964), pp. 41–68.
- [Joh68] P I M Johannesma. “Diffusion models for the stochastic activity of neurons”. In: *Neural Networks*. Ed. by E R Caianiello. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 1968, pp. 116–144. DOI: [10 . 1007/978-3-642-87596-0_11](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-87596-0_11).
- [RS69] Bhakta K Roy and David R Smith. “Analysis of the exponential decay model of the neuron showing frequency threshold effects”. In: *Bull. Math. Biophysics* 31.2 (1969), pp. 341–357. DOI: [10 . 1007/BF02477011](https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02477011).
- [SG69] Donald L Scharfetter and Hermann K Gummel. “Large-signal analysis of a silicon read diode oscillator”. In: *IEEE Transactions on electron devices* 16.1 (1969), pp. 64–77.

- [CR71] R M Capocelli and Luigi M Ricciardi. “Diffusion approximation and first passage time problem for a model neuron”. In: *Kybernetik* 8.6 (1971), pp. 214–23. DOI: [10.1016/0025-5564\(83\)90026-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-5564(83)90026-3).
- [Ama72] Shun-ichi Amari. “Learning patterns and pattern sequences by self-organizing nets of threshold elements”. In: *IEEE Transactions on Computers* C-21.11 (1972), pp. 1197–1206. DOI: [10.1109/T-C.1972.223477](https://doi.org/10.1109/T-C.1972.223477).
- [Kni72] B. W. Knight. “Dynamics of encoding in a population of neurons.” In: *J. Gen. Physiol.* 59.6 (1972), pp. 734–66.
- [WC72] Hugh R Wilson and Jack D Cowan. “Excitatory and inhibitory interactions in localized populations of model neurons.” In: *Biophysical Journal* 12.1 (1972), pp. 1–24. DOI: [10.1016/S0006-3495\(72\)86068-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0006-3495(72)86068-5).
- [Far73] Daniel Fargue. “Réducibilité des systèmes héréditaires à des systèmes dynamiques”. In: *CR Acad. Sci. Paris B* 277 (1973), pp. 471–473.
- [LL76] L. D. Landau and E. M. Lifshitz. *Mechanics, Third Edition: Volume 1 (Course of Theoretical Physics)*. Butterworth-Heinemann, 1976.
- [Ric76] Luigi M Ricciardi. “Diffusion approximation for a multi-input model neuron”. In: *Biol. Cybern.* 24.4 (1976), pp. 237–240. DOI: [10.1007/BF00335984](https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00335984).
- [CM77] D. R. Cox and H. D. Miller. *The theory of stochastic processes*. Vol. 134. CRC press, 1977.
- [RS79] Luigi M Ricciardi and Laura Sacerdote. “The Ornstein-Uhlenbeck process as a model for neuronal activity”. In: *Biological cybernetics* 35.1 (1979), pp. 1–9.
- [BSV81] Roberto Benzi, Alfonso Sutera, and Angelo Vulpiani. “The mechanism of stochastic resonance”. In: *Journal of Physics A: mathematical and general* 14.11 (1981), p. L453.
- [Hop82] John J Hopfield. “Neural networks and physical systems with emergent collective computational abilities.” In: *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the USA* 79 (1982), pp. 2554–2558. DOI: [10.1073/pnas.79.8.2554](https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.79.8.2554).
- [Gar+85] Crispin W Gardiner et al. *Handbook of stochastic methods*. Vol. 3. Springer Berlin, 1985.
- [SCS88] Haim Sompolinsky, Andrea Crisanti, and Hans-Jurgen Sommers. “Chaos in random neural networks”. In: *Physical review letters* 61.3 (1988), p. 259.
- [Mea89] Carver Mead. *Analog VLSI and neural system*. Reading, MA: Addison-Wesley, 1989.
- [Tuc89] Henry C Tuckwell. *Stochastic processes in the neurosciences*. Philadelphia: Society for Industrial and Applied Mathematics (SIAM), 1989, p. 129. ISBN: 0898712327.
- [HTB90] Peter Hänggi, Peter Talkner, and Michal Borkovec. “Reaction-rate theory: fifty years after Kramers”. In: *Reviews of modern physics* 62.2 (1990), p. 251.
- [Wig90] Eugene P Wigner. “The unreasonable effectiveness of mathematics in the natural sciences”. In: *Mathematics and Science*. World Scientific, 1990, pp. 291–306.

- [AT92] Daniel J Amit and MV Tsodyks. “Effective neurons and attractor neural networks in cortical environment”. In: *Network: Computation in Neural Systems* 3.2 (1992), pp. 121–137.
- [AV93] Larry F Abbott and Carl van Vreeswijk. “Asynchronous states in networks of pulse-coupled oscillators.” In: *Physical Review E* 48.2 (1993), pp. 1483–1490.
- [Kaw94] K. Kawasaki. “Stochastic model of slow dynamics in supercooled liquids and dense colloidal suspensions”. In: *Physica A* 208.1 (1994), pp. 35–64. doi: [10.1016/0378-4371\(94\)90533-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-4371(94)90533-9).
- [Ger95] Wulfram Gerstner. “Time structure of the activity in neural network models”. In: *Physical review E* 51.1 (1995), p. 738.
- [Dea96] D. S. Dean. “Langevin equation for the density of a system of interacting Langevin processes”. In: *J. Phys. A* 29.24 (1996). doi: [10.1088/0305-4470/29/24/001](https://doi.org/10.1088/0305-4470/29/24/001).
- [KMS96] B. W. Knight, D. Manin, and L. Sirovich. “Dynamical models of interacting neuron populations in visual cortex”. In: *Symposium on Robotics and Cybernetics: Computational Engineering in Systems Applications*. Ed. by E.C. Gerf. Cite Scientifique, Lille, France: Cite Scientifique, 1996, pp. 1–5.
- [Ris96] Hannes Risken. “Fokker-planck equation”. In: *The Fokker-Planck Equation*. Springer, 1996, pp. 63–95.
- [VS96] Carl Van Vreeswijk and Haim Sompolinsky. “Chaos in neuronal networks with balanced excitatory and inhibitory activity”. In: *Science* 274.5293 (1996), pp. 1724–1726.
- [AB97] Daniel J Amit and Nicolas Brunel. “Model of global spontaneous activity and local structured activity during delay periods in the cerebral cortex.” In: *Cerebral cortex (New York, NY: 1991)* 7.3 (1997), pp. 237–252.
- [Che+97] C.-C. Chen et al. “Size dependence of structural metastability in semiconductor nanocrystals”. In: *Science* 276.5311 (1997), pp. 398–401. doi: [10.1126/science.276.5311.398](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.276.5311.398).
- [Mou97] Vernon B Mountcastle. “The columnar organization of the neocortex”. In: *Brain* 120 (1997), pp. 701–22.
- [Rei+97] Daniel S Reich et al. “Response variability and timing precision of neuronal spike trains in vivo”. In: *Journal of neurophysiology* 77.5 (1997), pp. 2836–2841.
- [Gam+98] Luca Gammaitoni et al. “Stochastic resonance”. In: *Rev. Mod. Phys.* 70.1 (1998), pp. 223–287. doi: [10.1103/RevModPhys.70.223](https://doi.org/10.1103/RevModPhys.70.223).
- [VS98] Carl van Vreeswijk and Haim Sompolinsky. “Chaotic balanced state in a model of cortical circuits”. In: *Neural computation* 10.6 (1998), pp. 1321–1371.
- [BH99] Nicolas Brunel and Vincent Hakim. “Fast global oscillations in networks of integrate-and-fire neurons with low firing rates”. In: *Neural computation* 11.7 (1999), pp. 1621–1671.
- [FM99] Stefano Fusi and Maurizio Mattia. “Collective behavior of networks with linear (VLSI) integrate-and-fire neurons”. In: *Neural Computation* 11.3 (1999), pp. 633–652.

- [MA99] Massimo Mascaró and Daniel J Amit. “Effective neural response function for collective population states”. In: *Network: Computation in Neural Systems* 10.4 (1999), pp. 351–373.
- [PL99] M. Pascual and S. A. Levin. “From individuals to population densities: Searching for the intermediate scale of nontrivial determinism”. In: *Ecology* 80.7 (1999), pp. 2225–2236. DOI: [10.1890/0012-9658\(1999\)080\[2225:FITPDS\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1890/0012-9658(1999)080[2225:FITPDS]2.0.CO;2).
- [Bru00] Nicolas Brunel. “Dynamics of sparsely connected networks of excitatory and inhibitory spiking neurons”. In: *Journal of computational neuroscience* 8.3 (2000), pp. 183–208.
- [Ger00] W. Gerstner. “Population dynamics of spiking neurons: fast transients, asynchronous states, and locking”. In: *Neural Comput.* 12.1 (2000), pp. 43–89. DOI: [10.1162/089976600300015899](https://doi.org/10.1162/089976600300015899).
- [Kni00] Bruce W Knight. “Dynamics of encoding in neuron populations: some general mathematical features”. In: *Neural Computation* 12.3 (2000), pp. 473–518.
- [Bru+01] Nicolas Brunel et al. “Effects of synaptic noise and filtering on the frequency response of spiking neurons.” In: *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 86.10 (2001), pp. 2186–9.
- [Des+01] Alain Destexhe et al. “Fluctuating synaptic conductances recreate in vivo-like activity in neocortical neurons”. In: *Neuroscience* 107.1 (2001), pp. 13–24.
- [EG01] Gerald M Edelman and Joseph A Gally. “Degeneracy and complexity in biological systems”. In: *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 98.24 (2001), pp. 13763–13768.
- [EFS01] Andreas K Engel, Pascal Fries, and Wolf Singer. “Dynamic predictions: oscillations and synchrony in top-down processing.” In: *Nat. Rev. Neurosci.* 2.10 (2001), pp. 704–16. DOI: [10.1038/35094565](https://doi.org/10.1038/35094565).
- [LS01] Benjamin Lindner and Lutz Schimansky-Geier. “Transmission of noise coded versus additive signals through a neuronal ensemble”. In: *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 86.14 (2001), pp. 2934–2937. DOI: [10.1103/PhysRevLett.86.2934](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.86.2934).
- [DAA02] J. DeFelipe, L. Alonso-Nanclares, and J. I. Arellano. “Microstructure of the neocortex: comparative aspects.” In: *J. Neurocytol.* 31.3-5 (2002), pp. 299–316.
- [Fus02] Stefano Fusi. “Hebbian spike-driven synaptic plasticity for learning patterns of mean firing rates”. In: *Biological cybernetics* 87.5 (2002), pp. 459–470.
- [MD02] Maurizio Mattia and Paolo Del Giudice. “Population dynamics of interacting spiking neurons”. In: *Physical Review E* 66.5 (2002), p. 051917.
- [Mor+02] Rubén Moreno et al. “Response of spiking neurons to correlated inputs”. In: *Physical Review Letters* 89.28 (2002), p. 288101.
- [Pes+02] Bijan Pesaran et al. “Temporal structure in neuronal activity during working memory in macaque parietal cortex.” In: *Nat. Neurosci.* 5.8 (2002), pp. 805–11. DOI: [10.1038/nn890](https://doi.org/10.1038/nn890).
- [Fou+03] Nicolas Fourcaud-Trocmé et al. “How spike generation mechanisms determine the neuronal response to fluctuating inputs”. In: *Journal of neuroscience* 23.37 (2003), pp. 11628–11640.

- [GM03] Paolo Del Giudice and Maurizio Mattia. “Stochastic population dynamics of spiking neurons”. In: 2003.
- [MG03] Maurizio Mattia and P Del Giudice. “A distribution of spike transmission delays affects the stability of interacting spiking neurons”. In: *Scientiae Mathematicae Japonicae* 58.2 (2003), pp. 335–342.
- [Rau+03] Alexander Rauch et al. “Neocortical pyramidal cells respond as integrate-and-fire neurons to in vivo-like input currents”. In: *Journal of neurophysiology* 90.3 (2003), pp. 1598–1612.
- [Hwa+04] I.-S. Hwang et al. “Observation of Finite-Size Effects on a Structural Phase Transition of 2D Nanoislands”. In: *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 93.10 (2004), p. 106101. DOI: [10.1103/PhysRevLett.93.106101](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.93.106101).
- [Lin+04] Benjamin Lindner et al. “Effects of noise in excitable systems”. In: *Physics reports* 392.6 (2004), pp. 321–424.
- [MD04] M. Mattia and P. Del Giudice. “Finite-size dynamics of inhibitory and excitatory interacting spiking neurons.” In: *Phys. Rev. E* 70.5 Pt 1 (2004), p. 052903. DOI: [10.1103/PhysRevE.70.052903](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevE.70.052903).
- [PBM04] Astrid A Prinz, Dirk Bucher, and Eve Marder. “Similar network activity from disparate circuit parameters”. In: *Nature neuroscience* 7.12 (2004), pp. 1345–1352.
- [RG05] Magnus JE Richardson and Wulfram Gerstner. “Synaptic shot noise and conductance fluctuations affect the membrane voltage with equal significance”. In: *Neural computation* 17.4 (2005), pp. 923–947.
- [Tuc05] Henry C Tuckwell. *Introduction to theoretical neurobiology: volume 2, non-linear and stochastic theories*. Vol. 8. Cambridge University Press, 2005.
- [Hai+06] Bilal Haider et al. “Neocortical network activity in vivo is generated through a dynamic balance of excitation and inhibition”. In: *Journal of Neuroscience* 26.17 (2006), pp. 4535–4545.
- [Lin06] B. Lindner. “Superposition of many independent spike trains is generally not a Poisson process”. In: *Phys. Rev. E* 73.2 (2006), p. 022901. DOI: [10.1103/PhysRevE.73.022901](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevE.73.022901).
- [MG06] Eve Marder and Jean-Marc Goaillard. “Variability, compensation and homeostasis in neuron and network function”. In: *Nature Reviews Neuroscience* 7.7 (2006), pp. 563–574.
- [WW06] Kong-Fatt Wong and Xiao-Jing Wang. “A recurrent network mechanism of time integration in perceptual decisions”. In: *Journal of Neuroscience* 26.4 (2006), pp. 1314–1328.
- [GMD07] Guido Gigante, Maurizio Mattia, and Paolo Del Giudice. “Diverse population-bursting modes of adapting spiking neurons”. In: *Physical Review Letters* 98.14 (2007), p. 148101.
- [Kam07] N. G. van Kampen. *Stochastic Processes in Physics and Chemistry*. 3rd. North Holland, 2007, p. 463. ISBN: 9780444529657. DOI: [10.1016/B978-0-444-52965-7.X5000-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-444-52965-7.X5000-4).
- [Ric07] Magnus JE Richardson. “Firing-rate response of linear and nonlinear integrate-and-fire neurons to modulated current-based and conductance-based synaptic drive”. In: *Phys Rev E* 76.2 Pt 1 (2007), p. 021919. DOI: [10.1103/PhysRevE.76.021919](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevE.76.021919).

- [Bad+08] Laurent Badel et al. “Extracting non-linear integrate-and-fire models from experimental data using dynamic I–V curves”. In: *Biological cybernetics* 99.4-5 (2008), p. 361.
- [Bry08] Yury A Brychkov. *Handbook of special functions: Derivatives, integrals, series and other formulas*. CRC Press, 2008, pp. 1–680. ISBN: 9781584889571. DOI: [10.1201/9781584889571](https://doi.org/10.1201/9781584889571).
- [Cha08] P.-H. Chavanis. “Hamiltonian and Brownian systems with long-range interactions: V. Stochastic kinetic equations and theory of fluctuations”. In: *Physica A* 387.23 (2008), pp. 5716–5740. DOI: [10.1016/j.physa.2008.06.016](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physa.2008.06.016).
- [Dec+08] Gustavo Deco et al. “The dynamic brain: from spiking neurons to neural masses and cortical fields”. In: *PLoS computational biology* 4.8 (2008), e1000092.
- [GT08] Marc A Gieselmann and Alexander Thiele. “Comparison of spatial integration and surround suppression characteristics in spiking activity and the local field potential in macaque V1.” In: *Eur. J. Neurosci.* 28.3 (2008), pp. 447–59. DOI: [10.1111/j.1460-9568.2008.06358.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1460-9568.2008.06358.x).
- [PI09] C. Poo and J. S. Isaacson. “Odor representations in olfactory cortex: "sparse" coding, global inhibition, and oscillations”. In: *Neuron* 62.6 (2009), pp. 850–861. DOI: [10.1016/j.neuron.2009.05.022](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2009.05.022).
- [Bre10] Paul C Bressloff. “Stochastic neural field theory and the system-size expansion”. In: *SIAM Journal on Applied Mathematics* 70.5 (2010), pp. 1488–1521.
- [Wan10] Xiao-Jing Wang. “Neurophysiological and computational principles of cortical rhythms in cognition”. In: *Physiological reviews* 90.3 (2010), pp. 1195–1268.
- [Bre11] Paul C Bressloff. “Spatiotemporal dynamics of continuum neural fields”. In: *Journal of Physics A: Mathematical and Theoretical* 45.3 (2011), p. 033001.
- [CL11] Matthew E Carter and Luis de Lecea. “Optogenetic investigation of neural circuits in vivo”. In: *Trends in molecular medicine* 17.4 (2011), pp. 197–206.
- [LSM11] Daniele Linaro, Marco Storace, and Maurizio Mattia. “Inferring network dynamics and neuron properties from population recordings”. In: *Frontiers in computational neuroscience* 5 (2011), p. 43.
- [Mor11] Cristinel Mortici. “The quotient of gamma functions by the psi function”. In: *Computational and Applied Mathematics* 30.3 (2011), pp. 627–638. DOI: [10.1590/S1807-03022011000300008](https://doi.org/10.1590/S1807-03022011000300008).
- [Ost11] Srdjan Ostojic. “Interspike interval distributions of spiking neurons driven by fluctuating inputs”. In: *Journal of neurophysiology* 106.1 (2011), pp. 361–373.
- [Can+12] Claudio Canuto et al. *Spectral methods in fluid dynamics*. Springer Science & Business Media, 2012.
- [Das+12] S. K. Das et al. “Finite-size effects in dynamics: Critical vs. coarsening phenomena”. In: *Europhys. Lett.* 97.6 (2012), p. 66006. DOI: [10.1209/0295-5075/97/66006](https://doi.org/10.1209/0295-5075/97/66006).

- [MS12] Maurizio Mattia and Maria V Sanchez-Vives. “Exploring the spectrum of dynamical regimes and timescales in spontaneous cortical activity”. In: *Cognitive neurodynamics* 6.3 (2012), pp. 239–250.
- [SM12] Donald L Snyder and Michael I Miller. *Random point processes in time and space*. Springer Science & Business Media, 2012.
- [VK12] John Von Neumann and Ray Kurzweil. *The computer and the brain*. Yale university press, 2012.
- [BC13] Michael A Buice and Carson C Chow. “Dynamic finite size effects in spiking neural networks”. In: *PLoS computational biology* 9.1 (2013), e1002872.
- [Mac+13] Benjamin B Machta et al. “Parameter space compression underlies emergent theories and predictive models”. In: *Science* 342.6158 (2013), pp. 604–607.
- [Rig+13] M. Rigotti et al. “The importance of mixed selectivity in complex cognitive tasks.” In: *Nature* 497.7451 (2013), pp. 585–90. doi: [10.1038/nature12160](https://doi.org/10.1038/nature12160).
- [San+13] Paula Sanz Leon et al. “The Virtual Brain: a simulator of primate brain network dynamics”. In: *Frontiers in neuroinformatics* 7 (2013), p. 10.
- [SOA13] Evan S Schaffer, Srdjan Ostojic, and Larry F Abbott. “A complex-valued firing-rate model that approximates the dynamics of spiking networks”. In: *PLoS computational biology* 9.10 (2013), e1003301.
- [SML13] T Schwalger, D Miklody, and B Lindner. “When the leak is weak—how the first-passage statistics of a biased random walk can approximate the ISI statistics of an adapting neuron”. In: *The European Physical Journal Special Topics* 222.10 (2013), pp. 2655–2666.
- [SSS13] Moira L Steyn-Ross, D Alistair Steyn-Ross, and James W Sleigh. “Interacting Turing-Hopf instabilities drive symmetry-breaking transitions in a mean-field model of the cortex: a mechanism for the slow oscillation”. In: *Physical Review X* 3.2 (2013), p. 021005.
- [Ger+14] Wulfram Gerstner et al. *Neuronal dynamics: From single neurons to networks and models of cognition*. Cambridge University Press, 2014.
- [GCR14] S. Gupta, A. Campa, and S. Ruffo. “Kuramoto model of synchronization: equilibrium and nonequilibrium aspects”. In: *J. Stat. Mech.* 2014.8 (2014), R08001. doi: [10.1088/1742-5468/14/08/R08001](https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-5468/14/08/R08001).
- [Cha15] P.-H. Chavanis. “Generalized stochastic Fokker-Planck equations”. In: *Entropy* 17.5 (2015), pp. 3205–3252. doi: [10.3390/e17053205](https://doi.org/10.3390/e17053205).
- [Fri15] Pascal Fries. “Rhythms for cognition: Communication through coherence”. In: *Neuron* 88.1 (2015), pp. 220–235. doi: [10.1016/j.neuron.2015.09.034](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2015.09.034).
- [Mar+15] H. Markram et al. “Reconstruction and simulation of neocortical microcircuitry”. In: *Cell* 163.2 (2015), pp. 456–492. doi: [10.1016/j.cell.2015.09.029](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2015.09.029).
- [MPR15] Ernest Montbrió, Diego Pazó, and Alex Roxin. “Macroscopic description for networks of spiking neurons”. In: *Physical Review X* 5.2 (2015), p. 021028.
- [Tra+15] Mark K Transtrum et al. “Perspective: Sloppiness and emergent theories in physics, biology, and beyond”. In: *The Journal of chemical physics* 143.1 (2015), 07B201_1.

- [Wu+15] Fan Wu et al. “Monolithically integrated μ LEDs on silicon neural probes for high-resolution optogenetic studies in behaving animals”. In: *Neuron* 88.6 (2015), pp. 1136–1148.
- [ZR15] Jiwei W Zhang and Aaditya V Rangan. “A reduction for spiking integrate-and-fire network dynamics ranging from homogeneity to synchrony”. In: *Journal of Computational Neuroscience* 38.2 (2015), pp. 355–404.
- [Kue16] Christian Kuehn. “Moment closure—a brief review”. In: *Control of self-organizing nonlinear systems* (2016), pp. 253–271.
- [Mat16] Maurizio Mattia. “Low-dimensional firing rate dynamics of spiking neuron networks”. In: *arXiv preprint arXiv:1609.08855* (2016).
- [ROG16] Horacio G Rotstein, Motolani Olarinre, and Jorge Golowasch. “Dynamic compensation mechanism gives rise to period and duty-cycle level sets in oscillatory neuronal models”. In: *Journal of neurophysiology* 116.5 (2016), pp. 2431–2452.
- [Wat+16] B. O. Watson et al. “Network homeostasis and state dynamics of neocortical sleep.” In: *Neuron* 90.4 (2016), pp. 839–52. DOI: [10.1016/j.neuron.2016.03.036](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2016.03.036).
- [Aug+17] Moritz Augustin et al. “Low-dimensional spike rate models derived from networks of adaptive integrate-and-fire neurons: comparison and implementation”. In: *PLoS computational biology* 13.6 (2017), e1005545.
- [DR17] Taşkın Deniz and Stefan Rotter. “Solving the two-dimensional Fokker-Planck equation for strongly correlated neurons”. In: *Physical Review E* 95.1 (2017), p. 012412.
- [DLM17] NIST DLMF. “Digital Library of Mathematical Functions”. In: *WJ Olver, AB Olde Daalhuis, DW Lozier, BI Schneider, RF Boisvert, CW Clark, BR Miller and BV Saunders, eds* (2017).
- [Dur+17] M. A. Durán-Olivencia et al. “General framework for fluctuating dynamic density functional theory”. In: *New J. Phys.* 19.12 (2017). DOI: [10.1088/1367-2630/aa9041](https://doi.org/10.1088/1367-2630/aa9041).
- [SDG17a] T. Schwalger, M. Deger, and W. Gerstner. “Towards a theory of cortical columns: From spiking neurons to interacting neural populations of finite size”. In: *PLoS Comput. Biol.* 13.4 (2017), e1005507. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pcbi.1005507](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1005507).
- [SDG17b] Tilo Schwalger, Moritz Deger, and Wulfram Gerstner. “Towards a theory of cortical columns: From spiking neurons to interacting neural populations of finite size”. In: *PLoS computational biology* 13.4 (2017), e1005507.
- [Mat+19] Maurizio Mattia et al. “Dimensional reduction in network of non-Markovian spiking neurons: equivalence of synaptic filtering and heterogeneous propagation delays”. In: *PLOS C.B. to be published* (2019).
- [SC19] T. Schwalger and A. V. Chizhov. “Mind the last spike — firing rate models for mesoscopic populations of spiking neurons”. In: *Curr. Opin. Neurobiol.* 58 (2019), pp. 155–166. DOI: [10.1016/j.conb.2019.08.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conb.2019.08.003).
- [VL19] S. Vellmer and B. Lindner. “Theory of spike-train power spectra for multidimensional integrate-and-fire neurons”. In: *Phys. Rev. Res.* 1.2 (2019), p. 023024. DOI: [10.1103/PhysRevResearch.1.023024](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevResearch.1.023024).

- [Far+20] T. Fardet et al. “NEST 2.20.0”. In: *Zenodo* (2020). DOI: [10 . 5281 / zenodo . 3605514](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3605514).
- [PGS20] Bastian Pietras, Noé Gallice, and Tilo Schwalger. “Low-dimensional firing-rate dynamics for populations of renewal-type spiking neurons”. In: *Physical Review E* 102.2 (2020), p. 022407.
- [SZT20] Yuxiu Shao, Jiwei Zhang, and Louis Tao. “Dimensional reduction of emergent spatiotemporal cortical dynamics via a maximum entropy moment closure”. In: *PLoS computational biology* 16.6 (2020), e1007265.
- [Lyn+21] Christopher W Lynn et al. “Broken detailed balance and entropy production in the human brain”. In: *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U S A* 118.47 (2021), pp. 1–7. DOI: [10 . 1073 / pnas . 2109889118](https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2109889118).
- [SLS21] V. Schmutz, E. Löcherbach, and T. Schwalger. “On a finite-size neuronal population equation”. In: *arXiv* (2021). 2106.14721. arXiv: [2106 . 14721](https://arxiv.org/abs/2106.14721).
- [Set21] James P Sethna. *Statistical mechanics: entropy, order parameters, and complexity*. Vol. 14. Oxford University Press, USA, 2021.
- [Bri+22] Braden AW Brinkman et al. “Metastable dynamics of neural circuits and networks”. In: *Applied Physics Reviews* 9.1 (2022), p. 011313.
- [KF22] Mikail Khona and Ila R Fiete. “Attractor and integrator networks in the brain”. In: *Nature Reviews Neuroscience* (2022), pp. 1–23.
- [Led+22] Dylan Lederman et al. “Parameter estimation in the age of degeneracy and unidentifiability”. In: *Mathematics* 10.2 (2022), p. 170.
- [Qui+22] Katherine N Quinn et al. “Information geometry for multiparameter models: New perspectives on the origin of simplicity”. In: *Reports on Progress in Physics* (2022).
- [SHB22] Alessandro Sanzeni, Mark H Histed, and Nicolas Brunel. “Emergence of irregular activity in networks of strongly coupled conductance-based neurons”. In: *Physical Review X* 12.1 (2022), p. 011044.
- [Tur+22] Nicholas L Turner et al. “Reconstruction of neocortex: Organelles, compartments, cells, circuits, and activity”. In: *Cell* 185.6 (2022), pp. 1082–1100.
- [Wis+22] Kevin J Wischnewski et al. “Towards an efficient validation of dynamical whole-brain models”. In: *Scientific reports* 12.1 (2022), pp. 1–21.